

Lectures on Advanced algebra

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CHAPTER ONE

SOME TYPES OF IDEALS ON RING

The present section is largely devoted to a study of certain special types of ideals, most notably maximal and prime ideals. On the whole, our hypothesis will restrict us to commutative rings with identity. The requirement is motivated to some extent by the fact that many of the standard examples of ring theory have this property. A further reason, which is perhaps more important from the conceptual point of view, is that the most satisfactory and complete results occur here.

1.1. MAXIMAL IDEALS ON RING

DEFINITION 1.1.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, let M be a proper ideal of R , then M is called **Maximal ideal** if and only if, \nexists ideal J of $R \ni M \subsetneq J \subsetneq R$. (i.e.) \exists ideal J of $R \ni M \subsetneq J \subsetneq R \Rightarrow J = R$.

EXAMPLES 1.1.2. Let $(Z, +, \cdot)$ be a ring,

$$M_1 = \langle 2 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 2, \pm 4, \dots \}.$$

$$M_2 = \langle 4 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 4, \pm 8, \dots \}.$$

$$M_3 = \langle 6 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 6, \pm 12, \dots \}.$$

$$M_4 = \langle 3 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 3, \pm 6, \dots \}.$$

$M_2 \subsetneq M_1 \subsetneq Z \therefore M_1$ is maximal ideal.

$M_3 \subsetneq M_4 \subsetneq Z \therefore M_4$ is maximal ideal.

EXAMPLES 1.1.3. Let $Z_{12} = \{ 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 11 \}$ be a ring, then the ideals of it is

$$Z_{12}, \{0\},$$

$$\langle 2 \rangle = \{ 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 \}; \langle 3 \rangle = \{ 0, 3, 6, 9 \}; \langle 4 \rangle = \{ 0, 4, 8 \}; \langle 6 \rangle = \{ 0, 6 \}.$$

$\langle 2 \rangle, \langle 3 \rangle$ are maximal ideals of Z_{12} and $\langle 4 \rangle, \langle 6 \rangle$ are not maximal ideals of Z_{12} .

EXAMPLES 1.1.4. In field F , $\{0\}$ is only maximal ideal of F .

THEOREM 1.1.5.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and M be a proper ideal of R , $a \in R$, then M is maximal ideal $\Leftrightarrow R/M$ is a field, where $\langle M, a \rangle = \{ m+ra : r \in R, m \in M \}$

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Since R commutative ring with unity $1 \Rightarrow R/M$ is commutative ring with unity $1+M$. Let $a+M \in R/M$, $a+M \neq M \Rightarrow a \notin M$

$\Rightarrow \langle M, a \rangle = R \because 1 \in R \Rightarrow 1 \in \langle M, a \rangle \Rightarrow 1 = m + ra$, for some $m \in M, r \in R$
 $1 - r.a = m \in M. \therefore 1+M = r.a+M = (r+M) \odot (a+M)$

$\therefore r+M$ is inverse element of $a+M$ in a ring R/M . Hence R/M is a field .

(\Leftarrow) If R/M is a field, to prove M is a maximal ideal. Let $a \notin M \therefore a+M \neq M \Rightarrow a+M$ is inverse element $\Rightarrow \exists b+M \in R/M \ni (a+M) \odot (b+M) = 1+M \Rightarrow 1 - a.b \in M$
 $\Rightarrow 1 - a.b = m \in M \Rightarrow 1 = m + a.b \in \langle M, a \rangle$.

$\therefore \langle M, a \rangle = R$. Hence M is maximal ideal of R .

THEOREM 1.1.6.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be a proper ideal of R , $a \in R$, then the following statements are equivalent:-

- 1- I is maximal ideal.
- 2- $\langle I, a \rangle = R = \{ x+ra : x \in I, r \in R \} = I + \langle a \rangle$, for all $a \notin I$.
- 3- R/I is a field.

REMARK 1.1.7.

The theorem (1.1.6) is not true for rings without unity, for example :

In the ring $(Z_e, +, \cdot)$, $I = \{0, \pm 4, \pm 8, \dots\}$ is a maximal ideal of Z_e , but Z_e/I is not a field.

COROLLARY 1.1.8. Let $n \in Z^+$, $\langle n \rangle$ is maximal ideal of $Z \Leftrightarrow n$ is prime number

Proof :

$\langle n \rangle$ is maximal ideal $\Leftrightarrow Z/\langle n \rangle$ is a field $\Leftrightarrow Z_n$ is a field $\Leftrightarrow n$ is prime number .

NOTE THAT:-

Prove the corollary (1.1.8) by another way.

EXAMPLES 1.1.9.

Consider $(Z_e, +, \cdot)$ is commutative ring without unity. Find maximal ideal of Z_e

Solution:- $M = \langle 4 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 4, \pm 8, \dots \}$. $M \neq \emptyset$, M is maximal ideal of Z_e .

EXAMPLES 1.1.10.

Consider the ring $R = Z \oplus Z$ (external direct sum $(Z, +, \cdot)$ with $(Z, +, \cdot)$). Let $I = Z \times Z_e$ and $J = Z \times \{0\}$. Find maximal ideal .

Solution:- It is easy I and J are ideals of R . J is not maximal ideal of R since $J \subsetneq I \subsetneq R$, but I is a maximal ideal since $R/I \cong Z_2$, which is a field.

Also, we can show that I is a maximal ideal of R , as follows:

For any $(a,b) \notin I, b \notin Z_e$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
I + \langle (a,b) \rangle &= \{ (x,y) + (n_1,n_2)(a,b) : x \in Z, y \in Z_e, n_1, n_2 \in Z \} \\
&= \{ (x+n_1a, y+n_2b) : x \in Z, y \in Z_e, n_1, n_2 \in Z \} \\
&= Z \oplus Z.
\end{aligned}$$

REMARK 1.1.11.

For ease of reference, let us recall that by a chain is meant a collection π of sets such that $A, B \in \pi$ implies either $A \subseteq B$ or $B \subseteq A$. We now state Zorn's Lemma in a form best suited to our present needs.

Zorn's Lemma. Let λ be a nonempty family of subsets of some fixed set with the property that for each chain π in λ , the union $\cup \pi$ also belongs to λ . Then λ contains a set which is maximal in the sense that it is not properly contained in any member of λ .

The significant point, needless to say, is that this lemma asserts the existence of a certain maximal element without actually giving a constructive process for finding it.

THEOREM 1.1.12. (Theorem of Krull Zorn)

Let R be a commutative ring with unity, each proper ideal is contained in a maximal ideal.

i.e., let R be a commutative ring with unity. If I is a proper ideal of R , then $\exists M$ is a maximal ideal of $R \ni I \subseteq M$.

Proof :

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be any proper ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$, a commutative ring with identity. Define a family of subsets of R by taking $\lambda = \{ J \mid I \subseteq J; (J, +, \cdot) \text{ is a proper ideal of } (R, +, \cdot) \}$. This family is obviously nonempty for I itself belongs to λ .

Now, consider an arbitrary chain $\{I_i\}$ in λ . Our aim, of course, is to establish that $\cup I_i$ is again a member of λ . Notice first that $\cup I_i \neq R$, since $1 \in I_i$, for any i .

Next, let the elements $a, b \in \cup I_i$ and $r \in R$. Then there exist indices i and j for which $a \in I_i, b \in I_j$. As the collection $\{I_i\}$ forms a chain, either $I_i \subseteq I_j$ or else $I_j \subseteq I_i$; say, for definiteness, $I_i \subseteq I_j$. But $(I_j, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal, so the difference $a - b \in I_j \subseteq \cup I_i$. For the same reason, $r \cdot a \in \cup I_i$. This shows the triple $(\cup I_i, +, \cdot)$ to be a proper ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Finally, $I \subseteq \cup I_i$, hence the union $\cup I_i \in \lambda$.

Thus, on the basis of Zorn's Lemma, the family λ contains a maximal element M . It follows directly from the definition of λ that the triple $(M, +, \cdot)$ is a proper ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ with $I \subseteq M$. We assert $(M, +, \cdot)$ is in fact It maximal ideal. To see this, suppose $(J, +, \cdot)$ is any ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ for which $M \subset J \subseteq R$. Since M is a maximal element of the family λ , the set J cannot belong to λ . Accordingly, the ideal $(J, +, \cdot)$

must be improper, which implies $J = R$. We therefore conclude $(M, +, \cdot)$ is a maximal ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$, completing the proof.

As an application of the Krull-Zorn Theorem, we next give an elementary proof of a somewhat special result.

THEOREM 1.1.13.

- 1- In a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ having exactly one maximal ideal $(M, +, \cdot)$, the only idempotent elements are 0 and 1.
- 2- An element is invertible if and only if, it belongs to no maximal ideal.

Proof : (H.W.).

THEOREM 1.1.14.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be a proper ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Then $(I, +, \cdot)$ is a maximal ideal if and only if, the quotient ring $(R/I, +, \cdot)$ is a field.

Proof : (H.W.).

THEOREM 1.1.15. Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be an epimorphism ring. Then

- 1) If M is a maximal ideal of $R \Rightarrow f(M)$ is a maximal ideal of R' .
- 2) If M' is a maximal ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f^{-1}(M')$ is a maximal ideal of R .

Proof:-

(1) Since M is a maximal ideal of R and f is onto, to prove $f(M)$ is maximal ideal of R' . $f(M) \neq \emptyset$, since $f(0) = 0'$ & $f(M) \subseteq R'$.

Suppose $\exists K$ proper ideal of R' such that $f(M) \subset K \subset R'$, then $M \subset f^{-1}(K)$ where $f^{-1}(K)$ is ideal of $R \Rightarrow f^{-1}(K) = R$, since M is maximal ideal of $R \Rightarrow K = f(R) = R'$. since f is onto $\Rightarrow K = R' \therefore f(M)$ is maximal ideal of R' .

(2) Since J is a maximal ideal of R' , to prove $f^{-1}(J)$ is maximal ideal of R .

$f^{-1}(J) \neq \emptyset$, since $f^{-1}(0') = 0$ & $f^{-1}(J) \subseteq R$.

Suppose $\exists H$ proper ideal of R such that $f^{-1}(J) \subset H \subset R$, then $f^{-1}(J) \subset H \Rightarrow J \subset f(H) \Rightarrow f(H) = R'$, since J is maximal ideal $\Rightarrow H = f^{-1}(R') = R$.

$\therefore f^{-1}(J)$ is maximal ideal of R .

DEFINITION 1.1.16.

Let R be a commutative ring with identity 1. R is called **local ring** if R has only one maximal ideal. i.e., A ring R has a unique maximal ideal.

EXAMPLES 1.1.17.

- 1) Every field is local ring.
- 2) $(\mathbb{Z}_6, +_6, \cdot_6)$ is not local ring.

- 3) $(\mathbb{Z}_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$ is local ring .
- 4) $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is not local ring .
- 5) $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ is not local ring .
- 6) $(\mathbb{Z}_8, +_8, \cdot_8)$ is local ring .

EXAMPLES 1.1.18.

The prime ideals of the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ are precisely the ideals $(\langle p \rangle, +, \cdot)$, where p is a prime number, is a local ring.

THEOREM 1.1.19.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 . R is local ring $\Rightarrow 0, 1$ are the only idempotent elements. (a is called idempotent element, if $a \in R, \exists a^2 = a$).

Proof :

Let $a \in R, a \neq 0 \wedge a \neq 1 \exists a^2 = a$

$$a^2 = a \Rightarrow a^2 - a = 0 \Rightarrow a \cdot (a-1) = 0 \Rightarrow a \neq 0 \wedge a \neq 1.$$

$\langle a \rangle, \langle a-1 \rangle, 1 \notin \langle a \rangle, 1 \notin \langle a-1 \rangle \Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \neq R \therefore \langle a-1 \rangle \neq R$

Since if $\langle a \rangle = R \therefore 1 \in R = \langle a \rangle$

$1 = r \cdot a$, but R is local ring. So R has a unique maximal ideal say M such that

$\langle a \rangle \subset M \subset R \wedge \langle a-1 \rangle \subset M \subset R$. By Theorem of Krull Zorn $\Rightarrow a \in \langle a \rangle \subset M$ and

$$a-1 \in \langle a-1 \rangle \subset M \Rightarrow a \in M \text{ and } a-1 \in M \Rightarrow a-(a-1) \in M \Rightarrow 1 \in M$$

$\therefore M = R$ which is contradicts. $\therefore R$ has only 0 and 1 idempotent elements of R .

COROLLARY 1.1.20.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 . Then R has at least one maximal ideal

EXAMPLES 1.1.21.

- 1) $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ has an infinite number of maximal ideals, since every ideal $I = \langle p \rangle$, where p is a prime number is a maximal ideal.
- 2) $(\mathbb{Z}_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$ has only one maximal ideal $I = \langle \bar{2} \rangle$.
- 3) $(\mathbb{Z}_6, +_6, \cdot_6)$ has two maximal ideals $I = \langle \bar{2} \rangle$ and $J = \langle \bar{3} \rangle$.
- 4) Every field has only one maximal ideal, namely $I = \langle \bar{0} \rangle$.

COROLLARY 1.1.22.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 . $a \in R$ such that a has an inverse element of $R \Leftrightarrow a \notin$ any maximal ideal of R .

Proof:-

(\Rightarrow) If $a \in I$ (I is maximal ideal). $\therefore 1 \in I \Rightarrow I = R$ contradicts. $\therefore a \notin$ any maximal ideal of R .

(\Leftarrow) Suppose a is not inverse element such that $\langle a \rangle \neq R, \exists M$ (M is maximal ideal of R), $\langle a \rangle \subseteq M$, by Theorem of Krull Zorn $\Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \subseteq M \Rightarrow a \in M$ and M is maximal.

$\therefore a$ is inverse element of R .

OR

(\Rightarrow) If a is an invertible element, then every ideal containing a is equal to R . Hence $a \notin$ any proper ideal of R . $a \notin$ any maximal ideal of R .

(\Leftarrow) Suppose a is not invertible element. Then $\langle a \rangle \neq R$ and so \exists a maximal ideal J such that $\langle a \rangle \subseteq J \Rightarrow a \in J$ & J is a maximal ideal, thus we get contradicts. Then a is an invertible element.

THEOREM 1.1.23.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1. The following statements are equivalent:-

- 1- $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a local ring with one maximal ideal.
- 2- The set of noninvertible elements of R is maximal ideal.
- 3- The set of noninvertible elements of R form an ideal of R .
- 4- For all $r \in R$, either r or $1-r$ is invertible elements.

Proof :

(1) \Rightarrow (2) Let S is set of all noninvertible elements of R , to prove $S=M$. Let $x \in M$, then x is not (since if x is invertible element and $x \in M$, then $M=R$). Thus $M \subseteq S \dots (A)$.

Now, let $x \in S$, so x is not invertible element, hence $\langle x \rangle \subset R$. Then by Krull Zorns, there exists a maximal ideal M' such that $\langle x \rangle \subseteq M'$. But by (1), R has a unique maximal ideal M , so $\langle x \rangle \subseteq M$; that is $x \in M$. Hence $S \subseteq M$. Therefore $M=S$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) It is clear.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) Let $r \in R$, then either r is an invertible element or r is not invertible element.

If r is an invertible element, then nothing to prove.

If r is not an invertible element, then $r \in S$. It follows that $1-r \notin S$ (Since $1-r \in S$, then $1 = r + (1-r) \in S \Rightarrow 1 \in S$, then $S=R$, which is contradicts. Thus $1-r$ is an invertible element of R).

(4) \Rightarrow (1) Suppose M_1 and M_2 are maximal ideals of R and $M_1 \neq M_2$. Hence $M_1 + M_2 = R$, so $1 = m_1 + m_2$, for some $m_1 \in M_1, m_2 \in M_2$. Since $m_1 \in M_1, m_1$ is not invertible element, $1-m_1$ is invertible element, by (4) $\Rightarrow m_2 = 1 - m_1$ is an invertible element of R , which is contradicts.

Since $m_2 \in M_2$, then m_2 is not invertible element. Thus R must have unique maximal ideal.

1.2. PRIME IDEALS ON RING

DEFINITION 1.2.1.

Let R be a ring and let I be an ideal of R . I is called a **prime ideal** $\Leftrightarrow \forall a, b \in R$, if $a \cdot b \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$ or $b \in I$.

EXAMPLES 1.2.2. In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, Find prime ideal.

* $I_1 = \langle 3 \rangle$ is a prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} , $3 = 3 \cdot 1 \in I_1 \Rightarrow 3 \in I_1 \wedge 1 \notin I_1$.

* $I_2 = \langle 6 \rangle$ is not prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} , $6 = 3 \cdot 2 \in I_2 \Rightarrow 3 \notin I_2 \wedge 2 \notin I_2$.

* $I_3 = \langle 5 \rangle$ is a prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} , $5 = 5 \cdot 1 \in I_3 \Rightarrow 5 \in I_3 \wedge 1 \notin I_3$.

* $I_4 = \langle 18 \rangle$ is not prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} , $18 = 3 \cdot 6 \in I_4 \Rightarrow 3 \notin I_4 \wedge 6 \notin I_4$.

EXAMPLES 1.2.3.

The prime ideals of the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ are precisely the ideals $(\langle p \rangle, +, \cdot)$, where p is a prime number, together with the trivial ideals $(\{0\}, +, \cdot)$ and $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$.

THEOREM 1.2.4.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $\langle n \rangle$ is prime ideal of $\mathbb{Z} \Leftrightarrow n$ is prime number .

Proof:-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose n is not prime number, $n = m \cdot k \in \langle n \rangle$, where $m, k \in \mathbb{Z} \Leftrightarrow m \in \langle n \rangle$ or $k \in \langle n \rangle \Leftrightarrow m = r_1 \cdot n$ or $k = r_2 \cdot n$, $r_1 \neq 0$, $r_2 \neq 0 \Leftrightarrow m > n$ or $k > n$ which is contradicts. $\therefore n$ is prime number.

(\Leftarrow) Let $a \cdot b \in \langle n \rangle \therefore a \cdot b = c \cdot n$ for some $c \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\therefore n \mid a \cdot b$. But n is prime number .

$\therefore n \mid a$ or $n \mid b \Rightarrow a = k_1 \cdot n$ or $b = k_2 \cdot n \Rightarrow a \in \langle n \rangle$ or $b \in \langle n \rangle$. $\therefore \langle n \rangle$ is prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

PROPOSITION 1.2.5 Let R is commutative ring with unity 1. R is an integral domain $\Leftrightarrow \{0\}$ is prime ideal of R .

Proof:-

(\Rightarrow) Let $a, b \in R \ni a \cdot b \in \{0\} \Rightarrow a \cdot b = 0 \Rightarrow a = 0$ or $b = 0 \Rightarrow \{0\}$ is prime ideal of R .

(\Leftarrow) Let $a, b \in R \ni a \cdot b = 0 \Rightarrow a \cdot b \in \{0\}$. Since $I = \{0\}$ is prime ideal $\Rightarrow a = 0$ or $b = 0$. $\therefore R$ is an integral domain.

THEOREM 1.2.6.

Let R be commutative ring with unity 1 and I be a proper ideal of R , then the following are equivalent:

- 1- I is a prime ideal .
- 2- $\forall a, b \in R$, $\langle a \rangle \cdot \langle b \rangle \subseteq I \Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \subseteq I$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq I$.
- 3- $\forall A$ and B are ideals in R such that $A \cdot B \subseteq I \Rightarrow A \subseteq I$ or $B \subseteq I$.

Proof:-

(1) \Rightarrow (2).

Since I is a prime ideal and $\forall a, b \in R, \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle b \rangle \subseteq I$, to prove $\langle a \rangle \subseteq I$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq I$.

$\exists a \in \langle a \rangle$ and $b \in \langle b \rangle$ such that $a \cdot b \in \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle b \rangle \subseteq I \Rightarrow a \cdot b \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$ or $b \in I$.

$\Rightarrow a \in \langle a \rangle \subseteq I$ or $b \in \langle b \rangle \subseteq I$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3). $\forall A$ and B are ideals in R such that $A \cdot B \subseteq I$, to prove $A \subseteq I$ or $B \subseteq I$.

$\forall a, b \in R, \exists a \in A$ and $b \in B$ such that $a \cdot b \in A \cdot B \subseteq I$, but $\exists a \in \langle a \rangle$ and $b \in \langle b \rangle$, then

$\exists a \in \langle a \rangle \subseteq A$ and $b \in \langle b \rangle \subseteq B$ such that $a \cdot b \in \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle b \rangle \subseteq A \cdot B \subseteq I$

$\Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \subseteq A \subseteq I$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq B \subseteq I \Rightarrow A \subseteq I$ or $B \subseteq I$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1).

$\forall a, b \in R$, if $a \cdot b \in I, \exists a \in A$ and $b \in B$ such that $a \cdot b \in A \cdot B \subseteq I$, but $\forall A$ and B are ideals in R such that $A \cdot B \subseteq I \Rightarrow a \in A \subseteq I$ or $b \in B \subseteq I$. Then $\Rightarrow a \in I$ or $b \in I$.

Hence I is a prime ideal.

EXAMPLES 1.2.7. Let $R = Z \times Z$ such that $(x,y) + (z,w) = (x+z, y+w)$ and

$(x,y) \cdot (z,w) = (x \cdot z, y \cdot w)$, for all $(x,y), (z,w) \in R = Z \times Z$.

1- Let $I = Z \times \{0\} = \{(x,0) : x \in Z\}$. Show that I is a prime ideal of R and is not maximal ideal of R .

2- Let $K = Z_e \times \{0\} = \{(x,0) : x \in Z_e\}$. Is K a prime ideal of R ?

THEOREM 1.2.8.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be an ideal of R . I is a prime ideal of $R \Leftrightarrow R/I$ is an integer domain.

COROLLARY 1.2.9.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 . $\{0\}$ is a prime ideal of $R \Leftrightarrow R$ is an integer domain.

Proof :

It follows by theorem (1.2.8).

THEOREM 1.2.10.

Let R be commutative ring with unity 1 and M be a proper ideal of R . Then M is maximal ideal of $R \Rightarrow M$ is a prime ideal of R .

Proof:-

Let $a, b \in R \exists a \cdot b \in M$, suppose $a \notin M$, to prove $b \in M$. Since M is maximal ideal and $a \notin M \Rightarrow \langle M, a \rangle = R$ (by Theorem of Krull Zorn).

$1 \in R \Rightarrow 1 \in \langle M, a \rangle \Rightarrow 1 = m + ra, \forall m \in M, r \in R$.

$\therefore b = b \cdot m + b \cdot r \cdot a \in M \Rightarrow b \in M$. $\therefore M$ is prime ideal of R .

Or

Since I is maximal ideal of $R \Rightarrow R/I$ is a field $\Rightarrow R/I$ is an integral domain $\Rightarrow I$ is a prime ideal of R .

(*) **Prime ideal \nrightarrow Maximal ideal.**

EXAMPLES 1.2.11.

Consider the ring $R = Z \oplus Z$ (external direct sum $(Z,+,.)$ with $(Z,+,.)$).

Let $I = Z \times \{0\}$. Find prime ideal not maximal ideal.

Solution:-It is easy I is prime ideal of R . I is not maximal ideal of R , since $I \subsetneq J \subsetneq R$, where $J = Z \times Z_e$ and J is a proper ideal of R .

THEOREM 1.2.12. Let $f:(R,+,.) \rightarrow (R',+',\cdot')$ be an epimorphism ring. Then

1) If I is a prime ideal of R with $\ker f \subseteq I \Rightarrow f(I)$ is a prime ideal of R' .

2) If J is a prime ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f^{-1}(J)$ is a prime ideal of R .

Proof :

(1) Since I is a prime ideal of R , $\ker f \subseteq I$ and f is onto , to prove $f(I)$ is prime ideal of R' . $f(I) \neq \emptyset$, since $f(0) = 0$ & $f(I) \subseteq R'$.

$\forall a, b \in R'$, if $a.b \in f(I) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a.b) \in I \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a). f^{-1}(b) \in I$. Since I is prime ideal of $R \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a) \in I$ or $f^{-1}(b) \in I \Rightarrow a \in f(I)$ or $b \in f(I) \therefore f(I)$ is prime ideal of R' .

(2) Since J is a prime ideal of R' , to prove $f^{-1}(J)$ is prime ideal of R .

$f^{-1}(J) \neq \emptyset$, since $f^{-1}(0') = 0$ & $f^{-1}(J) \subseteq R$.

$\forall a, b \in R$, if $a.b \in f^{-1}(J) \Rightarrow f(a.b) \in J \Rightarrow f(a). f(b) \in J$. Since J is prime ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f(a) \in J$ or $f(b) \in J \Rightarrow a \in f^{-1}(J)$ or $b \in f^{-1}(J) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(J)$ is a prime ideal of R .

PROPOSITION 1.2.13.

In the ring $(Z,+,.)$, $n \in Z_+$. Then $\langle n \rangle$ is a maximal ideal of Z if and only if, $\langle n \rangle$ is a prime ideal of Z .

Proof : (H.W.).

REMARK 1.2.14.

A maximal ideal in a ring without unity may not be prime ideal of it.

EXAMPLES 1.2.15.

Consider $(Z_e, +, .)$ is commutative ring without unity. Find maximal ideal not prime ideal of Z_e .

Solution:- $I = \langle 4 \rangle = \{ 0, \pm 4, \pm 8, \dots \}$. $I \neq \emptyset$, I is maximal ideal of Z_e , but I is not prime ideal of Z_e .

EXAMPLES 1.2.16. Show that: $Z_e \times \{0\}$ is not prime ideal in the ring $R = Z \oplus Z$.

THEOREM 1.2.17.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a principal ideal domain. A (nontrivial) ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ is prime if and only if, it is a maximal ideal.

Proof :

In view of Theorem (1.2.10), it is sufficient to show that if $((a), +, \cdot)$ is a prime ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$, then $((a), +, \cdot)$ is also maximal. To this end, suppose $(I, +, \cdot)$ is any ideal with $(a) \subset I \subseteq R$. Since $(R, +, \cdot)$ is principal ideal domain, there exists an element $b \in R$, for which $I = (b)$.

Now, $a \in I = (b)$, hence $a = r \cdot b$, for some choice of r in R . But $((a), +, \cdot)$ is a prime ideal, so either $r \in (a)$ or $b \in (a)$. The possibility that $b \in (a)$ immediately leads to the contradiction

$(b) \subseteq (a)$. Therefore $r \in (a)$, which implies $r = s \cdot a$ for suitable $s \in R$, or $a = r \cdot b = (s \cdot a) \cdot b$. Since

$a \neq 0$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an integral domain, we then have $1 = s \cdot b$. This means the identity $1 \in (b) = I$, or equivalently, $I = R$. Since no ideal lies between $((a), +, \cdot)$ and the whole ring, we conclude that $((a), +, \cdot)$ is a maximal ideal.

COROLLARY 1.2.18.

A nontrivial ideal of the ring $(Z, +, \cdot)$ is prime if and only if, it is maximal.

Proof : (H.W.).

Note that in asserting the equivalence of prime and maximal ideals, Theorem (1.2.17) fails to actually identify these ideals. The situation is easily remedied though by introducing the idea of a prime element.

DEFINITION 1.2.19.

A nonzero element a of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is called a prime element of R if a is not invertible and in every factorization $a = b \cdot c$, with $b, c \in R$, either b or c is invertible.

PROPOSITION 1.2.20.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a principal ideal domain. The ideal $((a), +, \cdot)$ is a prime (maximal) ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ if and only if a is a prime element of R .

Proof : (H.W.).

THEOREM 1.2.21.

1) Let R be a commutative ring with unity. If every proper ideal of R is a prime ideal of R . Prove that R is a field.

2) Let R be a Boolean ring. Prove that every prime ideal of R is a maximal ideal of R .

Proof : (H.W.).

1.3. SEMIPRIME IDEALS ON RING

DEFINITION 1.3.1.

Let R be a ring and I be an ideal of R . I is called **semiprime ideal** $\Leftrightarrow \forall a \in R, a^2 \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$.

EXAMPLE 1.3.2. In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $I = \langle 3 \rangle = \{0, \bar{3}, \bar{6}, \bar{9}, \bar{12}, \dots\}$

$$3^2 = 9 \in I \quad \therefore 3 \in I$$

$$6^2 = 36 \in I \quad \therefore 6 \in I$$

.

.

.

$\therefore I$ is a semiprime ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

$$I = \langle 8 \rangle = \{0, \bar{8}, \bar{16}, \dots\}$$

$$8^2 = 64 \in I \quad \therefore 8 \in I$$

$$16^2 = 256 \in I \quad \therefore 16 \in I$$

.

.

.

$$2^2 = 4 \notin I \quad \text{and} \quad 4^2 = 16 \in I \quad \Rightarrow 4 \notin I$$

$\therefore I$ is not semiprime ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

THEOREM 1.3.3. Every prime ideal of a ring R is semiprime ideal of R .

Proof :

Let $a, b \in R$ such that $a \cdot b \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$ or $b \in I$. If $a = b$, then $a^2 \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$.

REMARK 1.3.4.

The semiprime ideal is not necessary is a prime ideal as the following example:

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $I = \langle 6 \rangle$ is not prime ideal since $6 = 2 \cdot 3$ and $2 \notin I$ and $3 \notin I$.

But I is a semiprime ideal since $36 \in I$ and $6 \in I$ and $144 \in I$ and $12 \in I$.

THEOREM 1.3.5.

Let R be commutative ring with unity 1 and I be a proper ideal of R , then the following are equivalent:

- 1- I is a semiprime ideal .
- 2- $\forall a \in R, \langle a^2 \rangle \subseteq I \Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \subseteq I$.
- 3- $\forall A$ is ideal in $R, A^2 \subseteq I \Rightarrow A \subseteq I$.

Proof:-

(1) \Rightarrow (2).

Since I is a semiprime ideal and $\forall a \in R, \langle a^2 \rangle = \langle a \cdot a \rangle = \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle a \rangle \subseteq I$, to prove $\langle a \rangle \subseteq I$.
 $\exists a \in \langle a \rangle$ such that $a^2 = a \cdot a \in \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle a \rangle \subseteq I \Rightarrow a \cdot a = a^2 \in I \Rightarrow a \in I \Rightarrow a \in \langle a \rangle \subseteq I$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3). $\forall A$ is ideal in R such that $A \cdot A = A^2 \subseteq I$, to prove $A \subseteq I$.

$\forall a \in R, \exists a \in A$ such that $a^2 = a \cdot a \in A \cdot A = A^2 \subseteq I$, but $\exists a \in \langle a \rangle$, then $\exists a \in \langle a \rangle \subseteq A$ such that $a^2 \in \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle a \rangle = \langle a^2 \rangle \subseteq A \cdot A = A^2 \subseteq I \Rightarrow \langle a \rangle \subseteq A \subseteq I \Rightarrow A \subseteq I$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1).

$\forall a \in R$, if $a^2 \in I, \exists a \in A$ such that $a^2 \in A^2 \subseteq I$, but $\forall A$ is ideal in R such that $A^2 \subseteq I \Rightarrow a \in A \subseteq I$. Then $\Rightarrow a \in I$. Hence I is a semiprime ideal.

THEOREM 1.3.6.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be an ideal of R . I is a semiprime ideal of $R \Leftrightarrow R/I$ has no non nilpotent element.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Since R commutative ring with unity 1 $\Rightarrow R/I$ is commutative ring with unity $1+I$.

Let $a+I \in R/I$ such that $a+I$ is nilpotent element $\Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \exists (a+I)^n = ((a+I)^2)^{\frac{n}{2}} = I \Rightarrow a^2+I = I$ or $(a)^{\frac{n}{2}}+I \neq I \Rightarrow a^2 \in I, \Rightarrow a \in I \Rightarrow a+I = I$. $\therefore a+I$ is a zero element.

(\Leftarrow) If $a^2 \in I. \therefore a^2+I = I \Rightarrow (a+I)^2 = I. \therefore a+I$ is nilpotent element. But R/I has no non nilpotent element, then $a+I = I \Rightarrow a \in I$. Hence I is a semiprime ideal of R .

PROPOSITION 1.3.7.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be an ideal of R . I is a semiprime ideal of $R \Leftrightarrow R/I$ has no non zero nilpotent ideal.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Since B be a nilpotent ideal in R/I , then $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \exists B^n = 0_{R/I}$. But $B = J/I$, for some ideal J of $R, I \subseteq J$. Hence $(J/I)^n = 0_{R/I}$. But $(J/I)^n = (J^n + I)/I = 0_{R/I}$. So that $J^n + I = I \Rightarrow J^n \subseteq I$. But I is semiprime ideal of R , hence $J \subseteq I$, thus $J/I = 0_{R/I}$.

(\Leftarrow) Assume that J an ideal of R such that $J^2 \subseteq I$, hence $J^2+I = I$, so that $(J^2+I)/I = 0_{R/I}$. Hence $(J/I)^2 = 0_{R/I} \Rightarrow J/I = 0_{R/I}$; thus $J \subseteq I$.

EXERCISES 1.3.8.

$I = \{a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_nx^n : a_i \in \mathbb{Z}; i = 1, \dots, n \wedge n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$. Find the following:

- 1- I is an ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
- 2- I is a prime ideal of $\mathbb{Z}[x]$.
- 3- $I = \langle x \rangle$?
- 4- Is I a maximal ideal ?

5- $J = \langle 2x \rangle \subseteq \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Is J a prime ideal ?

THEOREM 1.3.9. Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be a ring homomorphism. Let I be an ideal of R and J be an ideal of R' . Then

- 1) If I is a semiprime ideal of R , $\ker f \subseteq I$ and f is onto $\Rightarrow f(I)$ is semiprime ideal of R' .
- 2) If J is a semiprime ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f^{-1}(J)$ is semiprime ideal of R .

Proof:-

(1) Since I is a semiprime ideal of R , $\ker f \subseteq I$ and f is onto, to prove $f(I)$ is semiprime ideal of R' . $f(I) \neq \emptyset$, since $f(0) = 0$ & $f(I) \subseteq R'$.

$\forall a \in R'$, if $a^2 = a \cdot a \in f(I) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a^2) \in I \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a) \cdot f^{-1}(a) \in I$. Since I is semiprime ideal of $R \Rightarrow f^{-1}(a) \in I \Rightarrow a \in f(I)$. $\therefore f(I)$ is semiprime ideal of R' .

(2) Since J is a semiprime ideal of R' , to prove $f^{-1}(J)$ is semiprime ideal of R .

$f^{-1}(J) \neq \emptyset$, since $f^{-1}(0') = 0$ & $f^{-1}(J) \subseteq R$.

$\forall a \in R$, if $a^2 = a \cdot a \in f^{-1}(J) \Rightarrow f(a^2) \in J \Rightarrow f(a) \cdot f(a) \in J$. Since J is semiprime ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f(a) \in J \Rightarrow a \in f^{-1}(J)$. $\therefore f^{-1}(J)$ is semiprime ideal of R .

1.4. NILRADICAL OF IDEALS ON RING

We define the prime radical as the intersection of all prime ideals of R , and we denote it by \sqrt{I} . We wish to characterize this internally. An element a of R will be called strongly nilpotent provided every sequence a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots , such that $a_0 = a$, $a_{i+1} \in a_i R$ a_n is ultimately zero.

REMARK 1.4.1.

Clearly, every strongly nilpotent element is nilpotent, in the sense that $a^n = 0$, for some natural number n .

If R is commutative, every nilpotent element is strongly nilpotent.

DEFINITION 1.4.2.

Let R be a commutative ring and I be an ideal of R . Then $\{x: x \in R \ni x^n \in I, \text{ for some } n \in \mathbb{Z}_+\}$ is called **the nilradical of I** and denoted by \sqrt{I} .

PROPOSITION 1.4.3. Let R be a commutative ring and I be an ideal of R . Then \sqrt{I} is ideal of R .

Proof :-

$\sqrt{I} \neq \emptyset$ since $0^n = 0 \in I \wedge \sqrt{I} \subseteq R$.

Let $x, y \in \sqrt{I} \therefore \exists n, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \ni x^n \in I \wedge y^m \in I$ and $\forall r \in R$, then

a- $(x-y)^{n+m} = x^{n+m} + x^{n+m-1} \cdot (-y) + \dots + (-y)^{n+m} \in I \Rightarrow x-y \in \sqrt{I}$.

b- $(r \cdot x)^n = r^n \cdot x^n \in I \Rightarrow r \cdot x \in \sqrt{I} \therefore \sqrt{I}$ is ideal of R .

EXAMPLES 1.4.4.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} = \{0\}$.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$, $\sqrt{\langle \bar{0} \rangle} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}\}$.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}_8, +_8, \cdot_8)$, $\sqrt{\langle \bar{0} \rangle} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}, \bar{6}\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.4.5.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, if $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, $n > 1$ such that $n = p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{k_r}$, where $p_i \neq p_j$, then

$$\sqrt{\langle n \rangle} = \langle p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r \rangle .$$

Proof :-

Let $a = p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r$, then if $k = \max \{ k_1, k_2, \dots, k_r \}$, then $a^k = p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{k_r} \in \langle n \rangle$,

thus $a \in \sqrt{\langle n \rangle}$

$$\langle p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r \rangle \in \sqrt{\langle n \rangle}, \text{ Hence } \langle a \rangle \subseteq \sqrt{\langle n \rangle} \dots (1)$$

To prove the reverse inclusion, let $m \in \sqrt{\langle n \rangle}$, then $m^t \in \langle n \rangle$, hence

$$m^t = c. (p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \dots p_r^{k_r}).$$

This implies $p_1/m^t, p_2/m^t, \dots, p_r/m^t$. So that p_i/m^t (since p_i is prime number), then m is a multiple of $p_i, 1 \leq i \leq r$. Thus $m \in \langle p_i \rangle, i=1, \dots, r$.

It follows that $m \in \langle p_1 \rangle \cap \langle p_2 \rangle \cap \dots \cap \langle p_r \rangle$, thus $m \in \langle p_1 \cdot p_2 \dots p_r \rangle = \langle a \rangle$.

Hence $\sqrt{\langle n \rangle} \subseteq \langle a \rangle \dots (2)$.

From (1) and (2), $\sqrt{\langle n \rangle} = \langle a \rangle$.

REMARK 1.4.6.

As special case, in the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $\sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle, \sqrt{\langle 8 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle, \sqrt{\langle 6 \rangle} = \langle 6 \rangle, \sqrt{\langle 24 \rangle} = \langle 6 \rangle$.

THEOREM 1.4.7. Let R be a commutative ring and I be an ideal of R . Then

1- $I \subseteq \sqrt{I}$.

2- $I \subseteq J$ and J is ideal of $R \Rightarrow \sqrt{I} \subseteq \sqrt{J}$.

3- $I^k \subseteq J, k \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \Rightarrow \sqrt{I} \subseteq \sqrt{J}$.

Proof :-

(1) $x \in \sqrt{I} \therefore I \subseteq \sqrt{I}$, then $x \in I$.

(2) Let $x \in \sqrt{I} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in I \subseteq J \Rightarrow x^n \in J \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{J}$.

PROPOSITION 1.4.8.

Let R be a commutative ring and let I and J be two ideal of R , then

1- $\sqrt{I \cdot J} = \sqrt{I \cap J} = \sqrt{I} \cap \sqrt{J}$,

2- $\sqrt{I+J} = \sqrt{\sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J}} \supseteq \sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J}$,

3- $\sqrt{\sqrt{I}} = \sqrt{I}$.

Proof :-

(1) Let $x \in \sqrt{I \cap J} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in I \cap J \Rightarrow x^n \in I \wedge x^n \in J \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I}$ and $x \in \sqrt{J} \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I} \cap \sqrt{J} \dots (1)$.

$x \in \sqrt{I} \cap \sqrt{J} \therefore x \in \sqrt{I}$ and $x \in \sqrt{J} \Rightarrow x^n \in I \wedge x^m \in J \Rightarrow x^{n+m} = x^n \cdot x^m \in I \cap J \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I \cap J} \dots (2)$.

From (1) and (2), $\sqrt{I \cap J} = \sqrt{I} \cap \sqrt{J}$.

To prove $\sqrt{I \cdot J} = \sqrt{I \cap J}$, since $I \cdot J \subseteq I \cap J \Rightarrow \sqrt{I \cdot J} \subseteq \sqrt{I \cap J} \dots (1)$.

Let $x \in \sqrt{I \cap J} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in I \cap J \Rightarrow x^n \in I \wedge x^n \in J \Rightarrow x^{2n} = x^n \cdot x^n \in I \cdot J \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I \cdot J} \dots (2)$.

From (1) and (2), $\sqrt{I \cdot J} = \sqrt{I \cap J}$.

(2) Let $x \in \sqrt{I+J} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in I+J \Rightarrow x^n \in \sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J} \Rightarrow$

$$x \in \sqrt{\sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J}} \dots (1).$$

$$x \in \sqrt{\sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J}} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in \sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J} \Rightarrow x^n = a + b, a \in \sqrt{I} \text{ and } b \in \sqrt{J}$$

$$\therefore \exists m, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists a^m \in I \ \& \ b^k \in J \Rightarrow (x^n)^{m+k} = (a+b)^{m+k} \in I+J \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I+J} \dots (2).$$

$$\text{From (1) and (2), } \sqrt{I+J} = \sqrt{\sqrt{I} + \sqrt{J}}.$$

(3) Since $I \subseteq \sqrt{I}$, then $x \in \sqrt{I} \subseteq \sqrt{\sqrt{I}}$.

$$\text{Let } x \in \sqrt{\sqrt{I}} \therefore \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists x^n \in \sqrt{I} \Rightarrow \exists m \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists (x^n)^m \in I \Rightarrow x^{n \cdot m} \in I \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{\sqrt{I}} \subseteq \sqrt{I}.$$

$$\text{Hence } \sqrt{I} = \sqrt{\sqrt{I}}.$$

THEOREM 1.4.9.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be an ideal of R. I is a nilradical of I ideal of R \Leftrightarrow R/I has no non nilpotent element.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Since R commutative ring with unity 1 \Rightarrow R/I is commutative ring with unity 1+I.

Let $a+I \in R/I$ such that $a+I$ is nilpotent element $\Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \exists (a+I)^n = I \Rightarrow a^n + I = I \Rightarrow a^n \in I, \Rightarrow a \in I \Rightarrow a+I = I$. $\therefore a+I$ is zero element.

(\Leftarrow) If $a^n \in I$. $\therefore a^n + I = I \Rightarrow (a+I)^n = I$. $\therefore a+I$ is nilpotent element. But R/I has no non nilpotent element, then $a+I = I \Rightarrow a \in I$. Hence I is a radical of ideal I of R.

PROPOSITION 1.4.10.

Let R be a commutative ring and let I be an ideal of R, then I is a semiprime ideal of R $\Leftrightarrow I = \sqrt{I}$.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) I is a semiprime ideal of R. $\therefore I \subseteq \sqrt{I}$, to prove $\sqrt{I} \subseteq I$.

Let $x \in \sqrt{I} \Rightarrow x^n \in I \wedge n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \Rightarrow x \in I$ (I is a semiprime ideal of R).

$$\therefore \sqrt{I} \subseteq I \Rightarrow I = \sqrt{I}.$$

(\Leftarrow) $\forall x \in R, x^2 \in I \ n=2 \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \therefore x \in \sqrt{I} = I \Rightarrow x \in I$. \therefore I is semiprime ideal of R.

1.5. JACOBSON RADICAL AND PRIME RADICALS

The intersection of all maximal ideals of R does not seem to be an important concept. However, the intersection of all maximal right ideals is called the (Perlis-) Jacobson radical or just the radical of R . The apparent asymmetry in this definition will be removed later. Let us recall now that there always are plenty of maximal (proper) right ideals, in fact every proper right ideal is contained in at least one such. We denote the radical of R by $\text{Rad } R$. Recall that an element r of R is right invertible if $rs = 1$ for some $s \in R$, that is to say if rR is not a proper right ideal.

DEFINITION 1.5.1.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity. The Jacobson radical of R , denoted by $J(R)$, is defined by $J(R) = \bigcap \{M \mid (M, +, \cdot) \text{ is a maximal ideal of } (R, +, \cdot)\}$.

REMARK 1.5.2.

If R is a ring without unity, then it is not necessary that R has a maximal ideal and so in this case $J(R)$ is defined to be R .

DEFINITION 1.5.3.

Let R be a commutative ring. The prime radical of R , denoted by $L(R)$, is defined by $L(R) = \bigcap \{I \mid (I, +, \cdot) \text{ is a prime ideal of } (R, +, \cdot)\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.5.4.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity. Then

- 1- $J(R)$ and $L(R)$ are ideals of R .
- 2- $L(R) \subseteq J(R)$.

Proof : (H.W.).

EXAMPLES 1.5.5.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $L(\mathbb{Z}) = J(\mathbb{Z}) = \langle 0 \rangle$.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$, $L(\mathbb{Z}_4) = J(\mathbb{Z}_4) = \sqrt{\langle \bar{2} \rangle} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}\}$.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12}, \cdot_{12})$, $L(\mathbb{Z}_{12}) = J(\mathbb{Z}_{12}) = \sqrt{\langle \bar{6} \rangle} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{6}\}$.

EXAMPLES 1.5.6.

Give example of a ring R such that $L(\mathbb{Z}) \neq J(\mathbb{Z})$.

PROPOSITION 1.5.7.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 and I be an ideal of R . Then $I \subseteq J(R)$ if and only if, any element of $1+I$ inverse in R .

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) We begin by assuming that $I \subseteq J(R)$ and that there is some element $a \in I$ for which $1 + a$ is not invertible. Our object, of course, is to derive a contradiction.

By the Theorem (1.1.13(2)), the element $1 + a$ must belong to some maximal ideal $(M, +, \cdot)$ of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Since $a \in J(R)$, a is also contained in M , and therefore $1 = (1 + a) - a$ is in M . But this means $M = R$, which is clearly impossible.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose each member of $1 + I$ has a multiplicative inverse, but $I \subseteq J(R)$. By definition of the Jacobson radical, there will exist a maximal ideal $(M, +, \cdot)$ of $(R, +, \cdot)$ with $I \not\subseteq M$.

If a is any element of I which is not in M , the maximality of $(M, +, \cdot)$ implies that $(M, a) = R$. The identity element 1 can therefore be expressed in the form $1 = m + r \cdot a$, for suitable choice of $m \in M$ and $r \in R$. But then $m = 1 - r \cdot a \in 1 + I$, so that m possesses an inverse. The conclusion is untenable, since no proper ideal contains an invertible element.

The form this result takes when $(I, +, \cdot)$ is the principal ideal generated by an element $a \in J(R)$ deserves special attention. While actually a corollary to the theorem just proved, it is important enough to be singled out as a theorem.

THEOREM 1.5.8.

In any ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, an element $a \in J(R)$ if and only if, $1 + r \cdot a$ has an inverse for each $r \in R$.

This theorem adapts itself to many uses. Three fairly short and instructive applications are presented

COROLLARY 1.5.9.

An element a is invertible in the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ if and only if, the coset $a + J(R)$ is invertible in the quotient ring $(R/J(R), +, \cdot)$.

Proof :

Assume the coset $a + J(R)$ has an inverse in $(R/J(R), +, \cdot)$, so that $(a + J(R)) \cdot (b + J(R)) = 1 + J(R)$, for some $b \in R$. Then $a \cdot b - 1$ lies in $J(R)$. We next appeal to Theorem (1.5.8), with $r = 1$, to conclude that the product $a \cdot b = 1 + 1 \cdot (a \cdot b - 1)$ is invertible; this, in turn, forces the element a to have an inverse. The other direction is essentially trivial.

COROLLARY 1.5.10.

The only idempotent elements in the Jacobson radical of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is 0 .

Proof :

Let the element $a \in R$ with $a^2 = a$. Taking $r = -1$ in the preceding theorem, we see that $1 - a$ has an inverse in R ; say, for purposes of argument, that $(1 - a) \cdot b = 1$, where $b \in R$. This leads to $a = a^2 + a \cdot b - a \cdot b = a \cdot (a + a \cdot b - b) = a \cdot (a - 1) = 0$, but $a \neq 1$ (M is maximal ideal), then $a=0$, which completes the proof.

COROLLARY 1.5.11.

Let N denote the set of all noninvertible elements of R . Then the triple $(N, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ if and only if, $N = J(R)$.

Proof :

The inclusion $J(R) \subseteq N$ clearly holds. Suppose, therefore, that the element $a \in N$.

If the system $(N, +, \cdot)$ forms an ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$, then $r \cdot a \in N$ for any $r \in R$. Moreover, the element $1 + r \cdot a \notin N$, for otherwise $1 = (1 + r \cdot a) - (r \cdot a)$ would be in N . From the definition of N , it follows that $1 + r \cdot a$ must be invertible, implying $a \in J(R)$. This shows $N \subseteq J(R)$, whence the equality $N = J(R)$.

THEOREM 1.5.12.

For any ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, the quotient ring $(R/J(R), +, \cdot)$ is semiprime.

Proof :

Before becoming involved in details, let us remark that since $(J(R), +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$, we may certainly form the quotient ring $(R/J(R), +, \cdot)$.

To simplify notation somewhat, we will denote $\text{rad } R$ by I .

Suppose the coset $a + I \in J(R)$. Our strategy is to show that $a \in I$, for then $a + I = I$, which would imply that $J(R/I)$, consists of only the zero coset. Since $a + I$ lies in $J(R/I)$, Theorem (1.5.8) asserts

$(1 + I) + (r + I) \cdot (a + I) = (1 + r \cdot a) + I$ is invertible in R/I for each $r \in R$.

Accordingly, there exists a coset $b + I$ (which, of course, depends on both r and a) such that $(1 + a \cdot r + I) \cdot (b + I) = 1 + I$. This is clearly equivalent to $b + a \cdot r \cdot b - 1 \in I = J(R)$.

Again appealing to Theorem (1.5.8), we conclude that the element $b + a \cdot r \cdot b = 1 + 1 \cdot (b + a \cdot r \cdot b - 1)$ has an inverse c in R . But then $(1 + r \cdot a) \cdot (b \cdot c) = (b + a \cdot r \cdot b) \cdot c = 1$,

So that $1 + r \cdot a$ is invertible in R . Because this argument holds for every $r \in R$, it follows that $a \in J(R)$, as desired. Hence $(R/J(R), +, \cdot)$ is semiprime.

1.6. PRIMARY IDEAL OF RING

DEFINITION 1.6.1.

An ideal I of the ring R is called **primary ideal of R** if the conditions $a.b \in I$ and $a \notin I \Rightarrow b^n \in I$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

EXAMPLES 1.6.2. In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, find primary ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

* $I_1 = \langle 2 \rangle$ is primary ideal, $2 = 2.1 \in I_1 \Rightarrow 2 \in I_1 \wedge 1 \notin I_1$.

* $I_2 = \langle 3 \rangle$ is primary ideal, $3 = 3.1 \in I_2 \Rightarrow 3 \in I_2 \wedge 1 \notin I_2$.

* $I_3 = \langle 6 \rangle$ is not primary ideal, $6 = 3.2 \in I_3 \Rightarrow 3 \notin I_3 \wedge 2 \notin I_3$.

* $I_4 = \langle 18 \rangle$ is not primary ideal, $18 = 3.6 \in I_4 \Rightarrow 3 \notin I_4 \wedge 6 \notin I_4$.

PROPOSITION 1.6.3.

If I is a prime ideal of a ring R , then I is primary ideal of R .

Proof:

I is prime ideal $\Rightarrow \forall a, b \in R$, if $a.b \in I \Rightarrow a \in I$ or $b \in I$. If $a.b \in I$ and $a \notin I \Rightarrow b = b^1 \in I$.

Thus I is a primary ideal of R .

REMARK 1.6.4. If I is a primary ideal of a ring $R \not\Rightarrow I$ is prime ideal of R , as the following example:

Let $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $I = \langle 4 \rangle$ is a primary ideal of \mathbb{Z} , but not prime ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

THEOREM 1.6.5. In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $\langle n \rangle$ is a primary ideal $\Leftrightarrow n$ is a prime number.

Proof:-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose n is not prime $n = m.k \in \langle n \rangle \Leftrightarrow m \in \langle n \rangle$ or $k \in \langle n \rangle$

$\Leftrightarrow m = r_1.n$ or $k = r_2.n$ which is contradicts. $\therefore n$ is prime number.

(\Leftarrow) Let $a.b \in \langle n \rangle \therefore a.b = c.n$ for some $c \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\therefore n \mid a.b$. But n is prime number

$\therefore n \mid a$ or $n \mid b$. If $n \nmid a \Rightarrow b = k_2.n \Rightarrow b \in \langle n \rangle$. $\therefore \langle n \rangle$ is a primary ideal.

REMARK 1.6.6.

- 1- Let R is commutative ring with unity 1. If R is an integral domain $\Leftrightarrow \{0\}$ is primary ideal.
- 2- Let R be commutative ring with unity 1 and M be a proper ideal of R . M is maximal ideal $\Rightarrow M$ is a primary ideal.
- 3- Let R be commutative ring with unity 1 and I be a proper ideal of R . I is primary ideal $\not\Rightarrow I$ is a maximal ideal.

THEOREM 1.6.7.

Let I be an ideal of the ring R . I is a primary ideal \Leftrightarrow every zero divisor of the quotient ring R/I is a nilpotent element ($a^n = 0$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$).

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) I is primary ideal of $R \exists a+I$ zero divisor of R/I , then $\exists b+I \in R/I, b+I \neq I \ni (a+I) \odot (b+I) = (a \cdot b) + I = I \Rightarrow a \cdot b \in I$ and $b+I \neq I \Rightarrow b \notin I \therefore a^n \in I$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \ni (a+I)^n = a^n + I = I \Rightarrow a+I$ is a nilpotent element.

(\Leftarrow) Any zero divisor of R/I is nilpotent element, let $a \cdot b \in I, b \notin I$

$(a+I) \odot (b+I) = I$, if $a+I$ is zero divisor in $R/I \ni (a+I)^n = I$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \Rightarrow I$ is primary ideal.

THEOREM 1.6.8.

Let I be an ideal of the ring R . I is a primary ideal $\Rightarrow \sqrt{I}$ is the smallest prime ideal containing I .

Proof :-

Let $ab \in \sqrt{I}$ and assume $a \notin \sqrt{I}$ (i.e., $a^n \notin I, n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$). Then $(ab)^n \in I$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, thus $a^n \cdot b^n \in I$. But I is a primary, $a^n \notin I$, so $(b^n)^m \in I$, for some $m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, hence $b \in \sqrt{I}$, thus \sqrt{I} , is prime ideal of R .

Now, if J is a prime ideal, $I \subseteq J$, we must prove $\sqrt{I} \subseteq J$. Since $I \subseteq J$, then $\sqrt{I} \subseteq \sqrt{J}$. But $\sqrt{I} = J$ (since J is a prime), then $\sqrt{I} \subseteq J$.

THEOREM 1.6.9.

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be a ring homomorphism. Let I be an ideal of R and J be an ideal of R' . Then

- 1) If I is a primary ideal of R , $\ker f \subseteq I$ and f is onto $\Rightarrow f(I)$ is primary ideal of R' .
- 2) If J is a primary ideal of $R' \Rightarrow f^{-1}(J)$ is primary ideal of R .

Proof:- H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.6.10.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, the primary ideals of \mathbb{Z} are $\langle p^n \rangle$ where p is a prime number, $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+, n \geq 1$, with trivial ideal $\langle 0 \rangle$.

Proof :-

Let $I = \langle m \rangle$ be a primary ideal $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, thus $m = p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{k_r}$, implies that $\sqrt{I} = \langle p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r \rangle$.

But I is a primary ideal of R implies that \sqrt{I} is the smallest prime ideal, $p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_r$ are prime numbers, which is contradicts.

Hence $\exists p$ is a prime number such that $m = p^n$ and so $\sqrt{\langle m \rangle} = \sqrt{\langle p^n \rangle} = \langle p \rangle$.

Hence $I = \langle p^n \rangle$.

1.7. ANNIHILATOR OF IDEAL ON RING .

DEFINITION 1.7.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity 1 and $\phi \neq I$ be an ideal of R . The **annihilator of R** is denoted by $(\text{ann } I)$, it is defined to the set $\text{ann } I = \{r \in R: a \cdot r = 0, \forall a \in I\}$

EXAMPLE 1.7. 2.

* In the ring $(Z, +, \cdot)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z: a \cdot r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z$.

let $\langle 3 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 3 \rangle = \{r \in Z: a \cdot r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 3 \rangle\} = \langle 0 \rangle$.

* In the ring $(Z_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_4 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_4: a \cdot_4 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_4 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z_4: a \cdot_4 r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z_4$.

* In the ring $(Z_8, +_8, \cdot_8)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8: a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 4 \rangle$.

let $\langle 4 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 4 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8: a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8: a \cdot_8 r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z_8$.

PROPOSITION 1.7.3.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . $\text{ann } I$ is an ideal in R .

Proof :-

Since $\text{ann } I \neq \phi$, since $\exists 0 \in R$ and $0 \cdot a = 0$, and $\text{ann } I \subseteq R$.

1) Let $a_1, a_2 \in \text{ann } I$, then $r \cdot (a_1 - a_2) = r \cdot a_1 - r \cdot a_2 = 0 - 0 = 0, \forall r \in R, a_1 - a_2 \in \text{ann } I$.

2) Let $b \in R$ and $a_1 \in \text{ann } I$, then $r \cdot (b \cdot a_1) = (r \cdot a_1) \cdot b = 0 \cdot b = 0$, and

$r \cdot (a_1 \cdot b) = (r \cdot a_1) \cdot b = 0 \cdot b = 0. \Rightarrow b \cdot a_1 \in \text{ann } I$ and $a_1 \cdot b \in \text{ann } I, \forall r \in R, \forall a_1 \in \text{ann } I$.

$\therefore \text{ann } I$ is an ideal in R .

PROPOSITION 1.7.4.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity 1 and $a \in R$. If $J = \{a \mid r \cdot a = 0, r \in R\}$, then $(J, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R & containing a .

Proof:-

Since $0 \in J$, $0 \cdot a = 0 \quad \forall a \in R \Rightarrow \emptyset \neq J \subseteq R$. Let $x, y \in J, x = r_1 \cdot a, y = r_2 \cdot a$.

1. $x - y = r_1 \cdot a - r_2 \cdot a = (r_1 - r_2) \cdot a \in J$,

2. Let $n \in R$, $n \cdot x = n \cdot (r_1 \cdot a) = (n \cdot r_1) \cdot a \in J$, then $(J, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R

3- $a = 1 \cdot a = a \cdot 1 \Rightarrow a \in J$. $\therefore J$ is an ideal of R & containing a .

REMARK 1.7.5.

If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring, then $\text{ann } I$ is an ideal of $R \Rightarrow R/\text{ann } I$ is a ring.

PROPOSITION 1.7.6.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . $I \subseteq \text{ann } \text{ann } I$.

Proof:- H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.7.7.

Let I and J be two ideals of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Then

- 1- $\text{ann } I \cap \text{ann } J = \text{ann } (I+J)$.
- 2- $\text{ann } I + \text{ann } J \subseteq \text{ann } (I \cap J)$.
- 3- $I \subseteq J$ implies that $\text{ann } J \subseteq \text{ann } I$.

Proof:- H.W.

DEFINITION 1.7.8. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of R . I is called **faithful ideal** if and only if, $\text{ann } I = \langle 0 \rangle$.

EXAMPLE 1.7.9.

1- Let Z be a ring, let $\langle 5 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow (Z/\langle 5 \rangle, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.
 $\Rightarrow (Z/\langle 5 \rangle, \oplus)$ is commutative group and $Z/\langle 5 \rangle \cong Z_5 \Rightarrow Z_5$ is a ring,
 $\text{ann } Z_5 = \{a \in Z : r.a = 0, \forall r \in Z_5\} = \langle 5 \rangle = \{5k : k \in Z\} \neq \langle 0 \rangle$.

Hence $Z/\langle 5 \rangle \cong Z_5$ is not faithful ideal.

In general, $\text{ann } Z_n = \langle n \rangle = \{n \in Z : n.a = 0, \forall a \in Z_n\}$

2- Let $(Z, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow$
 $\text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z : a.r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 0 \rangle \Rightarrow \langle 2 \rangle$ is a faithful ideal.

PROPOSITION 1.7.10.

Let R be a ring and I be an ideal of R which contained I in $\text{ann } I$. (i.e., $I \subseteq \text{ann } I$). Then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

Proof :-

Since R is a ring $\Rightarrow (R, +)$ is an abelian group .

To Proof $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring:-

1- a- Closure, $a+I, b+I \in R/I$, for all $a, b \in R$. $(a+I) \oplus (b+I) = (a+b)+I \in R/I$, then \oplus is closure .

b- Well-defined, $(a+I) = (b+I)$ and $(c+I) = (d+I)$,
 $(a+I) \oplus (b+I) = ((a+b)+I) = ((c+d)+I) = (c+I) \oplus (d+I)$.

2- Assuasive , Let $a+I, b+I, c+I \in R/I$,
 $((a+I) \oplus (b+I)) \oplus (c+I) = ((a+b)+I) \oplus (c+I) = ((a+b)+c)+I = (a+(b+c))+I$

$= (a+I) \oplus ((b+c)+I) = (a+I) \oplus ((b+I) \oplus (c+I)) \in R/I$, then \oplus is assuasive .

3- Identity, since $0+I = I$, $a+I \in R/I$,

$$(a+I) \oplus (0+I) = (a+0) + I = (a+I) = (0+a) + I = (0+I) \oplus (a+I) .$$

4- Inverse, $(a+I) \oplus ((-a)+I) = (a+(-a)) + I = 0 + I = ((-a)+a) + I = ((-a)+I) \oplus (a+I)$.

5- Commutative, $(a+I) \oplus (b+I) = (a+b) + I = (b+a) + I = (b+I) \oplus (a+I)$.

$(R/I, \oplus)$ is commutative group.

6- Closure, let $a+I, b+I \in R/I$, for all $a, b \in R$. $(a+I) \odot (b+I) = (a.b) + I \in R/I$, then \odot is closure .

7- Assuasive , Let $a+I, b+I, c+I \in R/I$,

$$\begin{aligned} ((a+I) \odot (b+I)) \odot (c+I) &= ((a.b) + I) \odot (c+I) = ((a.b).c) + I = (a.(b.c)) + I \\ &= a+I \odot ((b.c)+I) = (a+I) \odot ((b+I) \odot (c+I)) \in R/I, \text{ then } \odot \text{ is assuasive.} \end{aligned}$$

8- \odot distractive over \oplus , Let $a+I, b+I, c+I \in R/I$,

$$\begin{aligned} ((a+I) \oplus (b+I)) \odot (c+I) &= ((a+b) + I) \odot (c+I) = ((a+b).c) + I = ((a.c) + (b.c)) + I \\ &= ((a+I) \odot (c+I)) \oplus ((b+I) \odot (c+I)), \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$(a+I) \odot ((b+I) \oplus (c+I)) = ((a+I) \odot (b+I)) \oplus ((a+I) \odot (c+I)), \text{ then } \odot \text{ dist. over } \oplus$$

Hence, $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

COROLLARY 1.7.11.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of R . , then $(R/\text{ann } I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

Proof:-

$J = \text{ann } I$, since $\text{ann } I$ is an ideal in R . By theorem above $(R/\text{ann } I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

DEFINITION 1.7.12.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity 1 and $\phi \neq I$ be an ideal of R . I is called **The annihilator ideal of R** if $I = \text{ann ann } I$.

EXAMPLE 1.7.13.

* In the ring $(Z, +, \cdot)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z: a.r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z$.

$$\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \text{ann } Z = \{r \in Z: a.r = 0, \forall a \in Z\} = \langle 0 \rangle .$$

Then $\langle 0 \rangle$ is an annihilator ideal of Z .

let $\langle 3 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 3 \rangle = \{r \in Z: a.r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 3 \rangle\} = \langle 0 \rangle$.

$$\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 3 \rangle = \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z: a.r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z .$$

Then $\langle 3 \rangle$ is not annihilator ideal of Z .

* In the ring $(Z_4, +_4, \cdot_4)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_4 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z_4: a._4r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z_4$.

$$\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \text{ann } Z_4 = \{r \in Z_4: a._4r = 0, \forall a \in Z_4\} = \langle 0 \rangle .$$

Then $\langle 0 \rangle$ is an annihilator ideal of Z_4 .

let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_4 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_4 : a \cdot_4 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.
 $\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_4 : a \cdot_4 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.
 Then $\langle 2 \rangle$ is an annihilator ideal of Z_4 .

* In the ring $(Z_8, +_8, \cdot_8)$, be a ring ,

let $\langle 0 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, 0 \in \langle 0 \rangle\} = Z_8$.
 $\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 0 \rangle = \text{ann } Z_8 = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in Z_8\} = \langle 0 \rangle$.

Then $\langle 0 \rangle$ is an annihilator ideal of Z_4 .

let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 4 \rangle$.
 $\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \text{ann } \langle 4 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 4 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.

Then $\langle 2 \rangle$ is an annihilator ideal of Z_4 .

let $\langle 4 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z_8 \Rightarrow \text{ann } \langle 4 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 4 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.
 $\Rightarrow \text{ann ann } \langle 4 \rangle = \text{ann } \langle 2 \rangle = \{r \in Z_8 : a \cdot_8 r = 0, \forall a \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle$.

Then $\langle 4 \rangle$ is not annihilator ideal of Z_4 .

PROPOSITION 1.7.14.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . $\text{ann ann } I$ is an ideal in R .

Proof :- H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.7.15.

Let I and J be two ideals of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. If every ideal of R is an annihilator ideal , then $\text{ann } I + \text{ann } J = \text{ann } (I \cap J)$.

Proof :- H.W.

CHAPTER TWO

REGULAR RING AND BOOLEAN RING

2.1. REGULAR RING

DEFINITION 2.1.1.

A ring R is regular if every element of R is regular, where an element $a \in R$ is called regular if $\exists x \in R$ such that $a = a.x.a = axa$.

Note that If R is a commutative ring, then for any $a \in R$, a is regular if $\exists x \in R$ such that $a = a^2x$

EXAMPLES 2.1.2.

1- $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is not regular ring, since $\nexists 2 \neq 2^2x$.

2- $(\mathbb{Z}_6, +_6, \cdot_6)$ is regular ring.

$$2^2 \cdot 2 = 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 = 8 = 2, 3^2 \cdot 5 = 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 3 = 45 = 3, 4^2 \cdot 4 = 4 \cdot 4 \cdot 4 = 64 = 4, 5^2 \cdot 5 = 5 \cdot 5 \cdot 5 = 125 = 5.$$

3- $(\mathbb{Z}_8, +_8, \cdot_8)$ is not regular ring .

$$2^2 \cdot 0 = 0, 2^2 \cdot 1 = 4, 2^2 \cdot 2 = 8 = 0, 2^2 \cdot 3 = 12 = 4, 2^2 \cdot 4 = 16 = 0, 2^2 \cdot 5 = 20 = 4. (2^2 \cdot x \neq 2, \text{ for all } x \in \mathbb{Z}_6).$$

4- Every field is a regular ring .

PROPOSITION 2.1.3.

If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a regular ring and $(I, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R , then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a regular ring .

Proof :

Let $\bar{a} = a + I \in R/I$, then $a \in R$. Since R is regular ring , then $\exists x \in R$ such that $a = axa$.

Hence $\bar{a} = axa + I = (a + I) \odot (x + I) \odot (a + I)$. Thus \bar{a} is regular element, R/I is a regular ring .

THEOREM 2.1.4.

Let R be a regular ring ,and J an Ideal of R . If I is an ideal in J , then I is an ideal of R .

Proof :

It is enough to show that $rx \in I \wedge xr \in I, \forall r \in R$ and $\forall x \in I$. Since $x \in I \wedge I \subseteq J$, then $x \in J$ and so $rx \in J$.

But R is a regular ring, hence $\exists y \in R$ such that $rx = (rx)y(rx)$, so that $rx = (rx)y(rx) \in I$ (since I ideal in J) Similarly $xr \in I$. I is an ideal of R .

NOTE THAT

Give example of a nonregular ring R and J ideal of R such that if I ideal in J , but I is not ideal in R .

THEOREM 2.1.5.

Let R_1 and R_2 be two rings, let $R = R_1 \oplus R_2$, then R is regular ring $\Leftrightarrow R_1$ and R_2 are regular rings.

Proof:

(\Rightarrow) Let $a \in R_1$. Then $(a, 0) \in R$, but R is regular ring, so $\exists (x, y) \in R$ such that $(a, 0) = (a, 0)(x, y)(a, 0)$. Then $(a, 0) = (axa, 0)$, thus $a = axa$, so a is regular ring.
 $\therefore R_1$ is regular ring.

Similarly R_2 is regular ring.

(\Leftarrow) Let $(a, b) \in R$. Since $a \in R_1$ & $b \in R_2 \wedge R_1, R_2$ are regular rings, $\exists x \in R_1, y \in R_2$ such that $a = axa, b = byb$. Hence $(a, b) = (axa, byb)$ implies that $(a, b) = (a, b) \odot (x, y) \odot (a, b)$. Hence $R = R_1 \oplus R_2$, then R is regular ring.

THEOREM 2.1.6.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1, if R is a regular ring, then $J(R) = (0)$.

Proof:

Let $a \in J(R)$, since R is regular ring and commutative, $\exists x \in R$ such that $a = a^2x$. Hence $a(1-ax) = 0$, but $a \in J(R)$, so $1-ax$ is an invertible element, i.e., $\exists b \in R$ such that $(1-ax)b = 1 \Rightarrow a(1-ax)b = 0 \cdot b$. Thus $a = 0$. Hence $J(R) = (0)$.

COROLLARY 2.1.7.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1, If R is regular ring, then $L(R) = (0)$

Proof: H.W.

PROPOSITION 2.1.8.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1. Then R is regular \Leftrightarrow every ideal of R is semiprime ideal.

Proof:

(\Rightarrow) Let J be an ideal of R such that $J^2 \subseteq I$.

Let $a \in R$. Assume $a \in J$. Then $a = a^2x$, for some $x \in R$, (since R is regular ring), but $a^2 \in J^2$, so $a^2 \in I$.

Hence $a = a^2x \in I$. $\therefore I$ is semiprime ideal.

$$1=(r_1a+j)(r_2b+k) = r_1 r_2ab+r_2jb+r_1ka+jk = r_1 r_2ab+r_1ka+r_2jb+jk$$

$$=(r_1 r_2b+r_1k)a+(r_2j)b+jk \quad (r_1 r_2b+r_1k)a+(r_2j)b \in \langle a, b \rangle, \text{ and } jk \in J \cap K.$$

Thus $\langle a, b \rangle + (J \cap K) = R \dots (C)$.

Moreover, we claim that $\langle a, b \rangle \cap (J \cap K) = (0)$.

If $x \in \langle a, b \rangle \cap (J \cap K)$, by (C), $1 = r_1a + r_2b + y$ for some $r_1, r_2 \in R, y \in J \cap K$. Thus $x = r_1ax + r_2bx + yx$. But $ax \in \langle a \rangle \cap J = (0)$, $bx \in \langle b \rangle \cap K = (0)$, $\therefore x = yx$. But $x \in \langle a, b \rangle$, $\therefore x = c_1a + c_2b$.

Then $x = y(c_1a + c_2b) = yc_1a + c_2b$, but, $yb \in K \cap \langle b \rangle = 0$, $ya \in J \cap \langle a \rangle = 0$.

Hence, $x = 0 \Rightarrow \langle a, b \rangle$ is a direct summand of R .

$I = \langle a, b \rangle$ is a direct summand of R . But every direct summand of R is a principle ideal of R . To show this assume $I \oplus J = R$, $\therefore 1 = i + j$, for some $i \in I, j \in J \Rightarrow i = i^2 + ij$, so that $i = i^2$, $ij \in I \cap J = (0)$. We claim that $I = \langle i \rangle$, it is clear $\langle i \rangle \subseteq I$.

Let $x \in I$, since $1 = i + j \Rightarrow x = xi + xj$. Thus $x \in \langle i \rangle$. $I = \langle i \rangle$ and I is an idempotent element.

Therefore, I is a generated ideal of R is a direct summand

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Any finite generated ideal of R is a direct summand, to prove R is regular ring.

Let $a \in R$, $\langle a \rangle$ is the generated ideal of R , then $\langle a \rangle \oplus J = R$, for some $J \subseteq R$, $\Rightarrow 1 = r_1a + j$, for some $r_1 \in R, j \in J \Rightarrow a = r_1a^2 + ja$, ($ja = 0$, since $ja \in J \cap \langle a \rangle = (0)$). $\therefore a = r_1a^2$.

Hence R is regular ring.

THEOREM 2.1.10.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1. R is a regular ring $\Leftrightarrow IJ = I \cap J$, for all ideals I and J of R .

Proof:

\Rightarrow) R is a regular ring, to prove $IJ = I \cap J$.

$IJ \subseteq I \cap J$ (obvious). Let $a \in I \cap J$, then $a \in I \wedge a \in J$. Since R is regular ring, $a = a^2x$, for some $x \in R$. So $a = a \cdot ax$ $a \in I$, $ax \in J$, then $a \in I \cdot J$. Thus $I \cap J \subseteq I \cdot J$. Hence $IJ = I \cap J$.

\Leftarrow) Let $a \in R$, $\langle a \rangle \cdot \langle a \rangle = \langle a \rangle \cap \langle a \rangle = \langle a \rangle$. But $a \in \langle a \rangle$, then $a \in \langle a \rangle \cdot \langle a \rangle = \langle a^2 \rangle$.

$\therefore a = ra^2$, for some $r \in R$. Hence R is regular ring.

COROLLARY 2.1.11.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1, R is a regular ring $\Leftrightarrow I^2 = I$, for all ideal $I \subseteq R$.

Proof:

\Rightarrow) By theorem (2.1.10), $I \cap I = I \cdot I$, that is $I = I^2$.

\Leftarrow) Let $a \in R$, then $\langle a^2 \rangle = \langle a \rangle$. Thus $\langle a^2 \rangle = \langle a \rangle \Rightarrow a \in \langle a^2 \rangle$.

$\therefore a = ra^2$, for some $r \in R$, hence R is a regular ring.

COROLLARY 2.1.12.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1, R is a regular ring $\Leftrightarrow \langle a \rangle \cap \langle b \rangle = \langle ab \rangle$ for all $a, b \in R$.

Proof:

\Rightarrow) It follows directly by theorem(2.1.10).

\Leftarrow) Let $a \in R$. Then $\langle a \rangle \cap \langle a \rangle = \langle a^2 \rangle$. Thus $\langle a \rangle = \langle a^2 \rangle \Rightarrow a \in \langle a^2 \rangle \Rightarrow a = ra^2$, for some $r \in R$. Hence R is regular ring.

THEOREM 2.1.13.

If R is a commutative ring with unity 1, then every regular integral domain is a field.

Proof:

Let R be a regular ring integral domain, let $a \in R$, $a \neq 0$, then $a = a^2x$, for some $x \in R$.

$a(1-ax) = 0 \Rightarrow a = 0$ or $1-ax = 0$, since R is an integral domain.

But $a \neq 0$, so $1-ax = 0$, then $1 = ax$; that is a is invertible element. Thus R is a field.

COROLLARY 2.1.14.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1. If R is a regular, then every prime ideal I of R is a maximal ideal.

Proof:

Since I is a prime ideal of R, then R/I is an integral domain.

But R is regular ring $\Rightarrow R/I$ is a regular ring.

Thus R/I is a regular ring integral domain, so that R/I is a field.

Hence I is a maximal ideal of R.

BOOLEAN RINGS

2.2. Boolean rings

The theory of Boolean algebras is an algebraic counterpart to the logical theory of the calculus of proposition . Its origins lie in the work of the English mathematician George Boole , who first attempted to give a systematic treatment of logic by abstract methods. Since such a structure may be viewed as the postulational abstraction of the rules governing the algebra of sets, it provides a suitable topic with which to conclude our discussion of two operational systems. Indeed, as will be evidenced shortly, Boolean algebras may be subsumed under the general theory of rings.

We begin by studying the properties of a special class of rings, which we shall designate as Boolean rings.

DEFINITION 2.2.1.

A Boolean ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring with identity every element of which is idempotent; that is, $a^2 = a$, for every $a \in R$.

It should be pointed out that the existence of an identity is frequently omitted in the definition of a Boolean ring. (One can show that if the number of elements in a Boolean ring is finite, then an identity element always exists.) The definition given here, however, will be more convenient for the applications we have in mind.

Let us pause to give several examples of the concept just introduced.

EXAMPLE 2.2.2.

- 1- The ring of integers modulo 2, $(Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$, forms a Boolean ring, since $0 \cdot_2 0 = 0$ and $1 \cdot_2 1 = 1$.
- 2- The ring $(P(X), \Delta, \cap)$ of subsets of a nonempty set X is easily verified to be a Boolean ring. In this case, we have $A \cap A = A$, for every subset $A \subseteq X$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.3.

R consist of all functions from an arbitrary nonempty set X to Z_2 with the operations defined point wise ; specifically, if f and g are in R , then $(f + g)(x) = f(x) +_2 g(x)$, $(f \cdot g)(x) = f(x) \cdot_2 g(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Under these operations, the triple $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a commutative ring with identity; the proof is straightforward and will not be given in detail. To establish the idempotency condition, we proceed as follows: If the function $f \in R$ is such that $f(x) = 0$, then $(f^2)(x) = f(x) \cdot f(x) = 0 \cdot 0 = 0$. While if $f(x) = 1$, then $(f^2)(x) = f(x) \cdot f(x) = 1 \cdot 1 = 1$. In any event, $(f^2)(x) = f(x)$, for every x in X , whence $f^2 = f$.

THEOREM 2.2.4.

Every Boolean ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a commutative ring of characteristic 2.

Proof:

If a and b are arbitrary elements of R , then

$a + b = (a + b)^2 = a^2 + a \cdot b + b \cdot a + b^2 = a + a \cdot b + b \cdot a + b$, and hence $a \cdot b + b \cdot a = 0$. In particular, setting $a = b$, we obtain $2a = a + a = a^2 + a^2 = 0$, for every $a \in R$. This shows that $(R, +, \cdot)$ is of characteristic 2. But then by adding $a \cdot b$ to both sides of the equation $a \cdot b + b \cdot a = 0$, we obtain $a \cdot b = a \cdot b + a \cdot b + b \cdot a = b \cdot a$.

THEOREM 2.2.5.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a Boolean ring. A proper ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ of $(R, +, \cdot)$ is prime if and only if, it is a maximal ideal.

Proof:

It is sufficient to show that if the ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ is prime ideal, then $(I, +, \cdot)$ is also maximal. To see this, suppose $(J, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ with the property $I \subseteq J \subseteq R$; what we must prove is that $J = R$. If a is any element of J not in I , then $a \cdot (1 - a) = 0 \in I$. Using the fact that $(I, +, \cdot)$ is a prime ideal with $a \notin I$, we conclude $1 - a \in I \subseteq J$.

As both the elements a and $1 - a$ lie in J , it follows that $1 = a + (1 - a) \in J$. The ideal $(J, +, \cdot)$ thus contains the identity, and consequently $J = R$.

THEOREM 2.2.6.

A Boolean ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a field if and only if, $(R, +, \cdot) \cong (Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$.

Proof:

\Rightarrow) Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a Boolean field. For any nonzero element $a \in R$, we then have for any $a \in R, a \neq 0, a = a \cdot 1 = a \cdot (aa^{-1}) = a^2 a^{-1} = aa^{-1} = 1$.

Thus R has only 2-element 0,1 Therefore $(R, +, \cdot) \cong (Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$.

\Leftarrow) It is clear.

COROLLARY 2.2.7.

A proper ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ of the Boolean ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a maximal ideal if and only if, $(R/I, +, \cdot) \cong (Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$.

Proof:

\Rightarrow) Since R is Boolean ring, R/I is a Boolean ring, But I is a maximal ideal of R , so R/I is a field.

Thus R/I is a Boolean field, hence by the theorem (2.2.6) $(R/I, +, \cdot) \cong (Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$.

\Leftarrow) Since $(R/I, +, \cdot) \cong (Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$. & Z_2 is a field, so R/I is a field. Hence I is a maximal ideal.

LEMMA 2.2.8.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a Boolean ring. For each nonzero element $a \in R$, there exists a homomorphism f from $(R, +, \cdot)$ onto the field $(Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$ such that $f(a) = 1$.

COROLLARY 2.2.9.

Every Boolean ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a semisimple ring; that is to say, $J(R) = \{0\}$.

Proof:

In order to arrive at a contradiction, we assume that $a \in J(R)$ with $a \neq 0$. Then there exists a homomorphism f from $(R, +, \cdot)$ onto $(Z_2, +_2, \cdot_2)$, for which $f(a) = 1$.

It follows that the ideal $(\ker(f), +, \cdot)$ must be a proper ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$.

Hence there is some maximal ideal $(M, +, \cdot)$ of $(R, +, \cdot)$ with $\ker(f) \subseteq M$.

In particular, the element $1 - a \in \ker(f) \subseteq M$. But also $a \in J(R) \subseteq M$, which implies $1 = a + (1 - a) \in M$. This leads at once to $M = R$, the desired contradiction.

THEOREM 2.2.10.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a Boolean ring. If I is a proper ideal of R , then the following statements are equivalent

- 1) I is a maximal ideal of R .
- 2) I is a prime ideal of R .
- 3) For all $a \in R$, either $a \in I$ or $1 - a \in I$ (but not both).

Proof:

(1) \Rightarrow (2) it is clear by above.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) $\forall a \in R$, $a = a^2$, $\therefore a(1 - a) = 0 \in I$. But I is a prime ideal, so either $a \in I$ or $1 - a \in I$, (Note not both $a, 1 - a$ in I , because if $a \in I, 1 - a \in I$, we get $1 \in I$ and so $I = R$ which is contradiction).

(3) \Rightarrow (1) To prove I is a maximal ideal of R .

Let $a \in R$ and $a \notin I$, by (3), $1 - a \in I$, Then $1 = (1 - a) + a \in I + \langle a \rangle$. So that $R = I + \langle a \rangle$.

Thus I is a maximal ideal of R .

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(3) \Rightarrow (2) Let $ab \in I$, suppose $a \notin I$. \therefore by (3), $1 - a \in I$. Hence $(1 - a)b \in I \Rightarrow b - ab \in I$.

But $ab \in I$, hence $b \in I$. $\therefore I$ is a prime ideal of R .

COROLLARY 2.2.11.

Let R be commutative ring with unity such that $a=a^3$, $\forall a \in R$. Is every prime ideal of R maximal ideal.

DEFINITION 2.2.12.

A Boolean algebra is a mathematical system (B, \vee, \wedge) consisting of a nonempty set B and two binary operations \vee and \wedge defined on B such that

(P1) Each of the operations \vee and \wedge is commutative; that is, $a \vee b = b \vee a$, $a \wedge b = b \wedge a$, for all $a, b \in B$.

(P2) Each operation is distributive over the other; that is,

$$a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c), \quad a \wedge (b \vee c) = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c), \text{ for all } a, b, c \in B.$$

(P3) There exist distinct identity elements 0 and 1 relative to the operations \vee and \wedge , respectively; that is, $a \vee 0 = a$, $a \wedge 1 = a$, for all $a \in B$.

(P4) For each element $a \in B$, there exists an element $a' \in B$, called the complement of a, such that $a \vee a' = 1$, $a \wedge a' = 0$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.13.

An obvious example of a Boolean algebra, but nonetheless an important one, is the system $(P(X), \cup, \cap)$, where X is a nonempty set. It is apparent that we should take $0 = \emptyset$, $1 = X$, and whenever $A \subseteq X$, $A' = X - A$.

More generally, if B is any family of subsets of X, including \emptyset , which is closed under unions and complements, then (B, \cup, \cap) , will be a Boolean algebra, in fact, a Boolean subalgebra of $(P(X), \cap, \cup)$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.14.

For an illustration quite removed from the algebra of sets, consider the set B of positive integral divisors of 10, that is, $B = \{1, 2, 5, 10\}$.

Given elements $a, b \in B$, we define $a \vee b$ to be the least common multiple (lcm) of a and b, $a \wedge b$ to be the greatest common divisor (gcd) of a and b: $a \vee b = \text{lcm}(a, b)$, $a \wedge b = \text{gcd}(a, b)$. The tables for these operations are given below.

\vee	1	2	5	10
1	1	2	5	10
2	2	2	10	10
5	5	10	5	10
10	10	10	10	10

\wedge	1	2	5	10
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	1	2
5	1	1	5	5
10	1	2	5	10

The formal verification that the triple (B, \vee, \wedge) constitutes a Boolean algebra is left as an exercise. (We should caution the reader that in this example the integer 1 plays the role of the identity element for the operation \vee , while the integer 10 serves as the identity element for the operation \wedge .)

A quick inspection of the foregoing tables will reveal the various complements to be $1' = 10, 2' = 5, 5' = 2, 10' = 1$.

We call attention to the fact that a' is simply the quotient when 10 is divided by a .

LEMMA 2.2.15.

A mathematical system $(S, *)$ has at most one identity element.

THEOREM 2.2.16.

In any Boolean algebra (B, \vee, \wedge) , the following properties hold:

- 1) The elements 0 and 1 are unique,
- 2) For each element $a \in B$, $a \vee a = a, a \wedge a = a$,
- 3) For each element $a \in B$, $a \vee 1 = 1, a \wedge 0 = 0$,
- 4) For each pair of elements $a, b \in B$, $a \vee (a \wedge b) = a, a \wedge (a \vee b) = a$.

Proof:

To establish (1), we need only appeal to Lemma (2.2.15).

The proof of (2) is indicated below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= a \vee 0 && \text{(by P3)} \\
 &= a \vee (a \wedge a') && \text{(by P4)} \\
 &= (a \vee a) \wedge (a \vee a') && \text{(by P2)} \\
 &= (a \vee a) \wedge 1 && \text{(by P4)} \\
 &= a \vee a && \text{(by P3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

We obtain (3) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &= a \vee a' && \text{(by P3)} \\
 &= a \vee (a' \wedge 1) && \text{(by P4)} \\
 &= (a \vee a') \wedge (a \vee 1) && \text{(by P2)} \\
 &= 1 \wedge (a \vee 1) && \text{(by P4)} \\
 &= a \vee 1 && \text{(by P3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (4) requires the use of (3):

$$\begin{aligned}
a &= a \wedge 1 && \text{(by P3)} \\
&= a \wedge (b \vee 1) && \text{(by 3)} \\
&= (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge 1) && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= (a \wedge b) \vee a && \text{(by P3)} \\
&= a \vee (a \wedge b) && \text{(by P1)}
\end{aligned}$$

THEOREM 2.2.17.

In any Boolean algebra (B, \vee, \wedge) , each of the operations \vee and \wedge is associative ; that is, for every triple of elements $a, b, c \in B$,
 $a \vee (b \vee c) = (a \vee b) \vee c$, $a \wedge (b \wedge c) = (a \wedge b) \wedge c$.

Proof:

First, set $x = a \vee (b \vee c)$ and $y = (a \vee b) \vee c$. We wish, of course, to prove that $x = y$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
a \wedge x &= (a \wedge a) \vee [a \wedge (b \vee c)] && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= a \vee [a \wedge (b \vee c)] && \text{(by theorem (2.2.16,(2)))} \\
&= a && \text{(by theorem (2.2.16,(4)))}
\end{aligned}$$

and also

$$\begin{aligned}
a \wedge y &= [a \wedge (a \vee b)] \vee (a \wedge c) && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= a \vee (a \wedge c) && \text{(by theorem (2.2.16,(4)))} \\
&= a && \text{(by theorem (2.2.16,(4)))}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $a \wedge x = a \wedge y$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
a' \wedge x &= (a' \wedge a) \vee [a' \wedge (b \vee c)] && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= 0 \vee [a' \wedge (b \vee c)] && \text{(by P1, P4)} \\
&= a' \wedge (b \vee c) && \text{(by P3)}
\end{aligned}$$

and also

$$\begin{aligned}
a' \wedge y &= [a' \wedge (a \vee b)] \vee (a' \wedge c) && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= [(a' \wedge a) \vee (a' \wedge b)] \vee (a' \wedge c) && \text{(by P2)} \\
&= [0 \vee (a' \wedge b)] \vee (a' \wedge c) && \text{(by P1, P4)} \\
&= (a' \wedge b) \vee (a' \wedge c) && \text{(by P3)}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $a' \wedge x = a' \wedge y$. From these observations, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
(a \wedge x) \vee (a' \wedge x) &= (a \wedge y) \vee (a' \wedge y) \\
(a \wedge a') \vee x &= (a \wedge a') \vee y && \text{(by P1, P2)} \\
1 \vee x &= 1 \vee y && \text{(by P4)} \\
x &= y && \text{(by P3)}
\end{aligned}$$

proving the associative law for the operation \vee ; that \wedge is also associative follows by a dual argument.

THEOREM 2.2.18.

In any $a \in B$ Boolean algebra (B, \vee, \wedge) , the following hold:

- 1) Each element $a \in B$ has a unique complement.
- 2) For each element $a \in B$, $a'' = a$.
- 3) $0' = 1$ and $1' = 0$.
- 4) For all $a, b \in B$, $(a \vee b)' = a' \wedge b'$, $(a \wedge b)' = a' \vee b'$.

Proof: H.W.

THEOREM 2.2.19.

Every Boolean algebra (B, \vee, \wedge) , becomes a Boolean ring $(B, +, \cdot)$ on defining addition and multiplication by the formulas

$$a + b = (a \wedge b') \vee (a' \wedge b), a \cdot b = a \wedge b, a, b \in B.$$

Proof: H.W.

THEOREM 2.2.20.

Every Boolean ring $(B, +, \cdot)$ becomes a Boolean algebra (B, \vee, \wedge) on defining $a \vee b = a + b + a \cdot b$, $a \wedge b = a \cdot b$, $(a, b \in B)$.

Proof: H.W.

CHAPTER THREE

POLYNOMIAL RINGS

3.1. Polynomial rings

DEFINITION 3.1.1.

Let R be an arbitrary ring. Let S be a sequence from N to R , $S = \{f : f = (a_0, a_1, \dots) : a_i \in R \text{ such that all but finite number of the } a_i\text{'s are zero's}\}$.

REMARK 3.1.2.

Any two sequences (a_0, a_1, \dots) and (b_0, b_1, \dots) are equal if $a_i = b_i, \forall i = 0, 1, \dots$.

DEFINITION 3.1.3.

Let $(+)$, (\cdot) be two operations on S defined by $(a_0, a_1, \dots) + (b_0, b_1, \dots) = (a_0 + b_0, a_1 + b_1, \dots)$ and $(a_0, a_1, \dots) \cdot (b_0, b_1, \dots) = (d_0, d_1, d_2, \dots)$ where $d_i = \sum_{j+k=i} a_j b_k, \forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

REMARK 3.1.4.

The $(+)$, (\cdot) are binary operations on S , because if $(a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots), (b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots) \in S$, then $\exists m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$,

$a_i = 0 \forall i > m$, and $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $b_i = 0, \forall i > n$. Hence $a_i + b_i = 0 \forall i > m$ and $i > n$, that is

$a_i + b_i = 0, \forall i > \max\{m, n\}$. Hence $(a_0, a_1, \dots) + (b_0, b_1, \dots) \in S$.

Also, since $d_i = \sum_{j+k=i} a_j b_k, \forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, hence $d_i = 0$ for all $i > m+n$, because $d_0 = a_0 b_0, d_1 = a_0 b_1 + a_1 b_0, \dots$

$d_{m+n} = a_0 b_{m+n} + a_1 b_{m+n-1} + \dots + a_m b_n + a_{m+1} b_{n-1} + \dots + a_{m+n} b_0$,

Since $(b_{m+n} = 0, b_{m+n-1} = 0, \dots, a_{m+1} = 0, \dots, a_{m+n} = 0)$, then $d_{m+n} = a_m b_n$.

And $d_{m+n+t} = a_0 b_{m+n+t} + a_1 b_{m+n+t-1} + \dots + a_m b_{n+t} + a_{m+1} b_{n+t-1} + \dots + a_{m+n+t} b_0 = 0$

PROPOSITION 3.1.5.

Let R be an arbitrary ring. Let S be a sequence from N to R . $(S, +, \cdot)$ is a ring and the zero polynomial $(0, 0, \dots)$ is the zero $(+)$ and $-f = (-a_0, -a_1, -a_2, \dots)$ is the additive inverse of $f = (a_0, a_1, \dots)$.

Proof: H.W.

PROPOSITION 3.1.6.

Let R be an arbitrary ring . Let S be a sequence from N to R , $(S,+,\cdot)$ is a ring. Then

- 1) R is commutative ring $\Leftrightarrow S$ is commutative ring.
- 2) R has unity $\Leftrightarrow S$ has unity .

Proof:

(1)

(\Rightarrow) Let $f = (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots)$, $g = (b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots)$ $f \cdot g = (d_0, d_1, \dots)$, $g \cdot f = (c_0, c_1, \dots)$.

since $d_i = \sum_{j+k=i} a_j b_k = \sum_{j+k=i} b_k a_j = c_i$, $\forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots \Rightarrow d_i = c_i$, $\forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Hence S is a commutative ring.

(\Leftarrow) Let $a, b \in R$, then let $f = (a, 0, \dots)$, $g = (b, 0, \dots)$,

$f \cdot g = (ab, 0, 0, \dots) = (ba, 0, 0, \dots) = g \cdot f \Rightarrow ab = ba$. Hence R is a commutative ring.

(2)

(\Rightarrow) Let I is an identity of R , if $f = (1, 0, \dots)$, then $\forall g \in S$, $gf = f \cdot g = g$.

Hence S is a ring with unity.

(\Leftarrow) Let S has unity , to prove R has unity . Assume $\langle a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots \rangle$ is an unity of S , for any $b \in R$.

$\langle a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots \rangle \cdot \langle b, 0, 0, \dots \rangle = \langle b, 0, 0, \dots \rangle = \langle b, 0, 0, \dots \rangle \cdot \langle a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots \rangle \Rightarrow a_0 b = b a_0 = b$ and hence a_0 is an identity of R .

Also, we have $a_1 b = a_2 b = a_3 b = \dots = 0$, we claim that $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = 0$.

By (1), a_0 is an identity of R , thus $\langle a_0, 0, \dots \rangle$ is an identity of S , implies that S has two identity $\langle a_0, 0, \dots \rangle$ and $\langle a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots \rangle$. But S has unique identity , so that $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = 0$. Hence S is a ring with unity.

REMARK 3.1.7.

1- The ring S is called the polynomial ring over R .

2- The map $a \rightarrow (a, 0, \dots)$ is monomorphism , form R to S . Hence R can be embedded in S and we can identify the poly $(a, 0, \dots)$ by a .

3- For any $f = (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots)$, $f = (a_0, 0, 0, \dots) + (0, a_1, \dots) + (0, 0, a_2, 0, \dots) + \dots$

Use the symbol a_0 for $(a_0, 0, 0, \dots)$, $a_1 x$ for $(0, a_1, \dots)$, $a_2 x^2$ for $(0, 0, a_2, 0, \dots)$,.....

Thus f can be written as $f = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots$,

If $a_i = 0$, $\forall i = n+1, n+2, \dots$, we can written as $\sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$.

Thus $S = \{ \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i : a_i \in R, n \text{ is nonnegative integer} \}$, a_i is called the coefficient of f .

REMARK 3.1.8.

1- The polynomial ring is denoted by $R[x]$ and any element of $R[x]$ is denoted by $f(x)$ and $R[x]$ is the polynomial ring with one indeterminable.

2- Let R be a ring, let $R' = R[x]$, we may construct

$$R'[y] = (R[x])[y] = \{ \sum_{i=0}^n b_i y^i, b_i \in R[x] \}$$

i.e., $\sum_{i=0}^n b_i y^i = (a_0 + a_1 x + \dots) + (c_0 + c_1 x + \dots) y^1 + \dots$. $R[y]$ is denoted by $R[x, y]$.

Similarly, we can construct a polynomial ring over R with any number of indeterminates.

DEFINITION 3.1.9.

- (1) $f(x) \in R[x]$ such that $f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, if $a_n \neq 0$, we say that f has degree n denoted by $\deg(f)$.
- (2) If $f(x) = c \neq 0$, then we say that $f(x)$ has degree zero.
- (3) The degree of zero polynomial ring is undefined.

THEOREM 3.1.10.

Let R be a ring and $f(x), g(x)$ be polynomial ring $R[x]$ such that $f(x) \neq 0, g(x) \neq 0$, then

- (1) $\deg(f(x) \cdot g(x)) \leq \deg f(x) + \deg g(x)$ or $f(x)g(x) = 0$
- (2) Either $f(x) + g(x) = 0$ or $\deg(f(x) + g(x)) \leq \max\{\deg f(x), \deg g(x)\}$

Proof:

- (1) Let $f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$, $a_n \neq 0$ such that $a_i = 0 \forall i > n$ and $g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^m b_i x^i$, $b_m \neq 0$ such that $b_i = 0, \forall i > m$.

But $f(x)g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{m+n} c_i x^i$ & $c_i = 0, \forall i > m+n$ and $c_{m+n} = a_n b_m$.

Hence $\deg(f(x)g(x)) = \begin{cases} n + m & \text{if } a_n b_m \neq 0 \\ < n + m & \text{if } a_n b_m = 0 \end{cases}$.

- (2) If $a_i = -b_i, \forall i = 0, 1, \dots$, then $f(x) + g(x) = 0$

If $n \geq m$, $f(x) + g(x) = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)x + \dots + (a_m + b_m)x^m + a_{m+1}x^{m+1} + \dots + a_n x^n$.

Hence $\deg(f(x) + g(x)) = n = \max\{n, m\}$.

If $n = m$ and $a_n + b_n \neq 0$, then $\deg(f(x) + g(x)) = n = \max\{n, m\}$.

If $n = m$ and $a_n + b_n = 0$, then $\deg(f(x) + g(x)) < n = \max\{n, m\}$.

COROLLARY 3.1.11.

The polynomial ring $R[x]$ over ring R . R be an integral domain $\Leftrightarrow R[x]$ is an integral domain.

Proof:

- (\Rightarrow) Let $f(x), g(x) \in R[x], f(x) \neq 0, g(x) \neq 0$ such that $\deg f(x) = n, \deg g(x) = m$.

So $f(x) = a_0 + \dots + a_n x^n, g(x) = b_0 + b_1 x + \dots + b_m x^m \Rightarrow a_n \neq 0$ and $b_m \neq 0 \Rightarrow a_n b_m \neq 0$

(since R is an integral domain), hence $\deg(f(x) + g(x)) = n + m$ by theorem (3.1.10)

$\Rightarrow f(x)g(x) \neq 0$

If $f(x) = a_0, g(x) = b_0 \Rightarrow f(x)g(x) = a_0 b_0 \neq 0$. Therefore, $R[x]$ is an integral domain.

(\Leftarrow) $R[x]$ commutative with unity $\Rightarrow R$ is commutative ring with unity.

Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, $a \neq 0$, $b \neq 0$, but $f(x)=a$, $g(x)=b$, thus $f(x)g(x) \neq 0$. That is $ab \neq 0$. Hence \mathbb{R} is an integer domain.

EXERCISE 3.1.12.

Let $f(x)=x^2+2x+3$, $g(x)=3x^2+2x$, $k(x)=2x+2$, $h(x)=2x^2+x$, $f(x), g(x), h(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_4[x]$

- (1) Show that $\deg(f(x)+g(x))=0$.
- (2) $\deg(h(x).k(x)) \neq \deg h(x)+\deg k(x)$
- (3) Show that $g(x).g(x)=x^4$.
- (4) Show that $k(x).k(x)=0$.

REMARK 3.1.13.

If F is a field, then $F[x]$ is not a field.

Proof:

Since F is a field $\Rightarrow F[x]$ is an integer domain. So any polynomial $f(x)$ of degree greater than zero is not invertible, because if $\exists g(x) \in R[x]$ such that $f(x)g(x)=1$
 $\Rightarrow \deg(f(x).g(x))=0$, but $\deg f(x)+\deg g(x) \neq 0$ which implies to contradict.

Hence then $F[x]$ is not a field.

DIVISION ALGORITHM THEOREM OF POLYNOMIAL

3.2. Division algorithm theorem of polynomial

THEOREM 3.2.1. (Division Algorithm theorem)

Let $f(x)$, $g(x)$ be two polynomials over R , $f(x)$ and $g(x) \in R[x]$, $g(x) \neq 0$. (R is a field or R is commutative ring with unity such that the leading coefficient of $g(x)$ is a invertible element). Then $\exists!$ Two polynomials $q(x), r(x) \in R[x]$ such that $f(x) = g(x)q(x) + r(x)$, where $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg r(x) < \deg g(x)$.

Proof. (H.W.)

EXAMPLE 3.2.2.

1- Let $f(x) = x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

1 is a zero of $f(x)$, since $f(1) = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 0 \pmod{5}$

Divide $f(x)$ by $(x-1)$, we get $f(x) = (x-1)(x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1)$.

But 1 is a root of $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1$, since $1 + 4 + 4 + 1 = 0 \pmod{5}$

Divide $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1$, by $x-1$, we get $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1 = (x-1)(x^2 + 4)$.

Thus $f(x) = (x-1)^2(x^2 + 4)$, but 1 is a root of $x^2 + 4$.

Divide $x^2 + 4$ by $x-1$, we get $x^2 + 4 = (x-1)(x+1)$, thus $f(x) = (x-1)^3(x+1)$.

2- Let's find the quotient and the remainder when we divide

$f(x) = x^7 + 2x^6 + 3x^5 + 4x^4 + x^3 + 4x + 3$ by $g(x) = x^3 + 2x + 1$, where we consider these polynomials inside the polynomial ring $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$.

We present this the usual way:

So the remainder is $x^2 + x + 1$ and the quotient is $x^4 + 2x^3 + x^2 + 4x + 2$,

$$x^7 + 2x^6 + 3x^5 + 4x^4 + x^3 + 4x + 3 = (x^4 + 2x^3 + x^2 + 4x + 2)(x^3 + 2x + 1) + (x^2 + x + 1):$$

COROLLARY 3.2.3.

Let $\alpha \in F$ is a zero of $f(x) \in F[x]$ if and only if, $x - \alpha$ is a factor of $f(x)$.

Proof.

Suppose that $x - \alpha$ is a factor of $f(x)$. Then we may find $g(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(x) = (x - \alpha)g(x)$. If we apply the function ϕ_α , evaluation at α , then we get $\phi_\alpha(f(x)) = \phi_\alpha((x - \alpha)g(x)) = \phi_\alpha(x - \alpha) \phi_\alpha(g(x)) = (\alpha - \alpha) \phi_\alpha(g(x)) = 0 \phi_\alpha(g(x)) = 0$:

Conversely, suppose that α is a zero of $f(x)$. By the division algorithm, we may find $q(x)$ and $r(x)$ such that $f(x) = q(x)(x - \alpha) + r(x)$; where either $r(x)$ is zero or its degree is zero. Thus $r(x) = r_0$ is a constant, possibly zero.

If we apply the function ϕ_α , evaluation at α , then we get

$$\phi_\alpha(f(x)) = \phi_\alpha(q(x)(x - \alpha) + r(x)) = \phi_\alpha(x - \alpha) \phi_\alpha(q(x)) + \phi_\alpha(r(x)) = r_0 = 0:$$

Thus $r(x) = 0$ and so $x - \alpha$ is a factor of $f(x)$.

THEOREM 3.2.4.

Let F be a field, then $F[x]$ is a principle integral domain.

Proof.

F is a field $\Rightarrow F$ is an integral domain $\Rightarrow F[x]$ is an integral domain.

Let I be an ideal of $F[x]$.

If $I = \langle 0 \rangle$, then I is a principle integral.

If $I \neq \langle 0 \rangle$, then $g(x)$ be a nonzero polynomial of I of minimal degree

If $\deg(g(x)) = 0$, then $g(x) = a \neq 0$. But a is invertible element of F , thus $g(x) \in I$, $g(x)$ invertible element. Hence $I = F[x] = \langle 1 \rangle$.

If $\deg(g(x)) \geq 1$, let $f(x) \in I$, then by Division Algorithm theorem, $\exists q(x)$, $r(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(x) = g(x)q(x) + r(x)$, where $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg(r(x)) < \deg(g(x))$.

Now, $r(x) = f(x) - g(x)q(x) \in I$, so if $\deg(r(x)) < \deg(g(x))$, we get contradicts, since $g(x)$ is a nonzero element of I with lowest degree.

Thus $r(x) = 0$ and so $f(x) = g(x)q(x)$ that is $f(x) \in \langle g(x) \rangle$. i.e., $\forall f(x) \in I \Rightarrow f(x) \in \langle g(x) \rangle$. $\therefore I \subseteq \langle g(x) \rangle$. But $\langle g(x) \rangle \subseteq I$. Hence $\langle g(x) \rangle = I$.

DEFINITION 3.2.5.

Let R be a ring, let $f(x)$ polynomial over R , let $a \in R$. a is called a root of $f(x)$ (or a is a zero of $f(x)$), if $f(a) = 0$.

THEOREM 3.2.6. (Factor theorem)

An element a in a field F is a zero element of $f(x) \in F[x]$ if and only if, $x - a$ is a factor of $f(x)$ in $F[x]$. i.e., $f(x) = (x - a)g(x)$, for some $g(x) \in F[x]$.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Suppose $a \in F$ and $f(a) = 0$. By Division Algorithm theorem, $\exists q(x)$, $r(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(x) = (x - a)q(x) + r(x)$, $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg(r(x)) < \deg(x - a)$, (since $\deg r(x) = 0$ and $\deg(x - a) = 1$), hence either $r(x) = 0$ or $r(x) = c \neq 0$.

Hence if $r(x) = 0$, then $f(x) = (x - a)q(x)$, thus $x - a$ factor of $q(x)$.

If $r(x) = c \neq 0$, then $0 = f(a) = (a - a)q(a) + r(x) = 0 + c$. Hence $c = 0$, we get contradicts.

Thus $r(x) = 0$ and $x - a$ is a factor of $f(x)$.

(\Leftarrow) Conversely, suppose that $(x - a) | f(x)$, then $f(x) = (x - a)g(x)$, for some $g(x) \in F[x]$, thus $f(a) = 0$. Hence a is a zero of $f(x)$. Therefore a is zero element of $f(x) \in F[x]$.

COROLLARY 3.2.7.

A nonzero polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ of degree n can have at most n distinct zeros in a field F .

Proof :

Suppose $a \in F$ and $a \neq 0$. If $f(x) = ax + b \neq 0$, then $x = -ba^{-1}$ is a zero of $f(x)$.

i.e., $\deg f(x) = 1$

If a_1 is a root of $f(x)$, then $f(x) = (x - a_1)q_1(x)$ and hence $\deg q_1(x) = n - 1$, it follows that $q_1(x)$ has at most $(n - 1)$ roots. It follows that $f(x)$ has at most n -roots.

EXAMPLE 3.2.8.

Let $f(x) = x^4 + 3x^3 + 2x + 4 \in \mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. 1 is a zero of $f(x)$, since $f(1) = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 0 \pmod{5}$

Divide $f(x)$ by $(x - 1)$, we get $f(x) = (x - 1)(x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1)$.

But 1 is a root of $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1$, since $1 + 4 + 4 + 1 = 0 \pmod{5}$

Divide $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1$, by $x - 1$, we get $x^3 + 4x^2 + 4x + 1 = (x - 1)(x^2 + 4)$.

Thus $f(x) = (x - 1)^2(x^2 + 4)$, but 1 is a root of $x^2 + 4$.

Divide $x^2 + 4$ by $x - 1$, we get $x^2 + 4 = (x - 1)(x + 1)$, thus $f(x) = (x - 1)^3(x + 1)$.

DEFINITION 3.2.9.

A non constant polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ is an irreducible polynomial, if $f(x)$ **can not** be expressed as a product $g(x)h(x)$ of two polynomials $g(x)$, $h(x)$ in $F[x]$ both of lower degree than degree of $f(x)$. $f(x)$ is reducible polynomial, if it is not irreducible.

REMARK 3.2.10.

A polynomial $f(x)$ may be irreducible over F , but not irreducible over larger field E containing F .

EXAMPLE 3.2.11.

Let $f(x) = x^2 - 2 \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$. $f(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , because if $f(x)$ is reducible, then $f(x) = (ax + b)(cx + d)$, $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Q} \Rightarrow x^2 - 2 = acx^2 + (bc + ad)x + bd$.

$1 = ac$, $0 = bc + ad$, $-2 = bd$, thus $c = 1/a$, $b/a + ad = 0 \Rightarrow -b/a = ad \Rightarrow d = -b/a^2$.

$\therefore -2 = b(-b/a^2) \Rightarrow 2 = b^2/a^2$. i.e., $2 = (b/a)^2$ which is contradicts, since \nexists rational number x such that $x^2 = 2$.

On the other hand, $x^2 - 2 \in \mathbb{R}[x]$, then $(x^2 - 2) = (x - \sqrt{2})(x + \sqrt{2})$, thus $x^2 - 2$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} and $x^2 - 2$ is reducible over \mathbb{R} .

PROPOSITION 3.2.12.

A non zero polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ such that $\deg f(x) > 1$. If $f(x)$ has a zero element in F , then $f(x)$ is reducible polynomial.

Proof :

If a is a root of $f(x)$, then $x-a$ is a factor of $f(x)$. Thus $f(x)=(x-a)q(x)$, for some $q(x) \in F[x]$. Then $f(x)$ is reducible.

REMARK 3.2.13.

The converse of proposition (3.2.12) is not true in general.

EXAMPLE 3.2.14.

Let $f(x)=x^4+5x^2+6 \in \mathbb{Q}[x]$, $f(x)=(x^2+2)(x^2+3)$. Hence $f(x)$ is reducible over \mathbb{Q} . However $f(x)$ has no roots in \mathbb{Q} , since $f(x) \geq 6, \forall x \in \mathbb{Q}$.

PROPOSITION 3.2.15.

A non zero polynomial $f(x) \in F[x]$ and let $f(x)$ be of degree 2 or 3. Then $f(x)$ is reducible polynomial over $F \Leftrightarrow$ it has zero element in F .

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) If $f(x)$ is reducible, then $f(x)=g(x)h(x)$, where $g(x), h(x) \in F[x]$. Since $\deg f(x)=2$ or 3 and $\deg f(x) = \deg g(x) + \deg h(x)$, then at least one of the polynomials $g(x)$ or $h(x)$ has degree one, say $\deg(g(x))=1$.

Hence, we put $g(x) = ax+b$. It follows that $-a^{-1}b$ is a root of $g(x)$, then $-a^{-1}b$ is a root of $f(x)$, since $f(-a^{-1}b) = g(-a^{-1}b).h(-a^{-1}b) = 0.h(-a^{-1}b) = 0$.

(\Leftarrow) If a is a zero element in F , then $f(x)$ is reducible polynomial, by remark (3.2.13).

PROPOSITION 3.2.16.

A non zero polynomial $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$, $\deg f(x) > 1$, then $f(x)$ factors in to product of two polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ of degree r and s , where $r < \deg f(x)$, $s < \deg f(x) \Leftrightarrow f(x)$ has such factorization with polynomials of the same degrees r and s in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Proof: H.W.

EXAMPLE 3.2.17.

1- Let $f(x) = x^4-4 = (x^2-2)(x^2+2)$, $f(x)$ factors in $\mathbb{Z}[x] \Leftrightarrow f(x)$ factors in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

2- Let $f(x) = 9x^2-4 = (3x-2)(3x+2)$, $f(x)$ factors in $\mathbb{Z}[x] \Leftrightarrow f(x)$ factors in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

THEOREM 3.2.18. (Eisenstein theorem) نظرية انشتاين

Let p be a prime number. Suppose $f(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_0$ in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$ and $p|a_0, p|a_1, \dots, p|a_{n-1}, p \nmid a_n, p^2 \nmid a_0$, then $f(x)$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Proof: H.W.

EXAMPLE 3.2.19.

1- Let $f(x) = x^2 - 2 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ and let $p = 2$, $p \nmid 2$, $p \nmid 1$, $p^2 = 4$, $p^2 \nmid 1$. $\therefore f(x)$ is irreducible polynomial over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

2- Let $f(x) = 25x^5 - 9x^4 + 3x^2 - 12 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Taking $P=3$, $3 \nmid (-12)$, $3 \nmid 3$, $3 \nmid -9$, $3 \nmid 25$, $3^2 \nmid (-12)$. $\therefore f(x)$ is irreducible polynomial over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

COROLLARY 3.2.20. (The cyclotomic polynomial)

$\phi_p(x) = (x^p - 1) / (x - 1) = x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \dots + x + 1$ is an irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, for any prime number p .

Proof: H.W.

THEOREM 3.2.21.

Let non zero polynomial $p(x) \in F[x]$, F is a field. Then $\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal $\Leftrightarrow p(x)$ is irreducible polynomial over F .

Proof:

(\Rightarrow) if $\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal, so $(0) \neq \langle p(x) \rangle \neq F[x]$. $\therefore p(x)$ is not constant Assume $p(x) = g(x) \cdot h(x)$, $g(x)$ and $h(x) \in F[x]$ such that $\deg g(x) < \deg p(x)$, $\deg p(x) > \deg h(x)$. Since $g(x)h(x) = p(x)$, so $g(x)h(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$.

$\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal, hence it is a prime. It follows that either $g(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$ or $h(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$.

If $g(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$, then $g(x) = r(x)p(x)$, for some $r(x) \in F[x]$ and so $\deg g(x) = \deg r(x) + \deg p(x) > \deg p(x)$, which is contradicts, since $\deg g(x) < \deg p(x)$. Since, $h(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$ implies contradicts. Thus $p(x)$ is irreducible over F .

(\Leftarrow) If $\langle p(x) \rangle$ is irreducible over F , suppose $\langle p(x) \rangle \subset I \subseteq F[x]$. Since F is a field, $F[x]$ is a principle integral domain. Hence $I = \langle g(x) \rangle$, for some $g(x) \in F[x]$. Thus $\langle p(x) \rangle \subset \langle g(x) \rangle \subseteq F[x]$.

It follows that $p(x) = h(x)g(x)$, for some $h(x) \in F[x]$, but $p(x)$ is irreducible over F , so either $h(x)$ or $g(x)$ is a constant polynomial.

If $h(x) = c \in F[x]$, then $g(x) = c^{-1}p(x) \in \langle p(x) \rangle$ and so $\langle g(x) \rangle \subseteq \langle p(x) \rangle$, which is a contradicts.

Thus $g(x) = c$, but c is an invertible element in F , hence $\langle g(x) \rangle = F[x]$ and $\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal.

COROLLARY 3.2.22.

Let F be a field, let non zero polynomial $p(x) \in F[x]$. Then the following are equivalent

- 1- $p(x)$ is irreducible polynomial.
- 2- $\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal in $F[x]$.

3- $F[x]/\langle p(x) \rangle$ is a field.

Proof: H.W.

EXAMPLE 3.2.23.

Consider the polynomial ring $Z[x]$.

- (1) Show that $\langle x \rangle$ is a prime ideal .
- (2) Show that $\langle x \rangle$ is not maximal ideal .
- (3) Show that $Z[x]$ is not a principle integral field.

Answer

(1) Let $f(x)=a_0+\dots+a_nx^n$, $g(x)=b_0+\dots+b_mx^m \in Z[x]$.

If $f(x)g(x) \in \langle x \rangle = \{xh(x): h(x) \in Z[x]\} = \{x(c_0+\dots+c_kx^k): c_i \in Z\} = \{xc_0+x^2c_1+\dots+c_kx^{k+1} : c_i \in Z\}$. Hence $f(x)g(x) \in \langle x \rangle \Rightarrow a_0b_0=0 \Rightarrow a_0=0$ or $b_0=0$.

If $a_0=0$, then $f(x)=a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n=x(a_1+a_2x+\dots+a_nx^{n-1}) \in \langle x \rangle$

Similarly, if $b_0=0$, then $g(x) \in \langle x \rangle$. Thus $\langle x \rangle$ is prime ideal.

(2) $\langle x \rangle \subset \langle x, 2 \rangle \subset Z[x]$. It is clear $\langle x \rangle \subseteq \langle x, 2 \rangle$, but $2 \in \langle x, 2 \rangle$, $2 \notin \langle x \rangle$, also $g(x)=1 \in Z[x]$ and $g(x) \notin \langle x, 2 \rangle$. Thus $\langle x \rangle$ is not maximal ideal.

(3) $Z[x]$ is not a principle integral domain (by theorem a non trivial proper ideal of a principle integral domain, I is prime ideal $\Leftrightarrow I$ is maximal ideal).

EXAMPLE 3.2.24.

(1) Show that $Z[x]/\langle x \rangle \cong Z$.

Answer

Define $\phi: Z[x] \rightarrow Z$ defined by: $\phi(a_0+a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n)=a_0$, $\forall (a_0+\dots+a_nx^n) \in Z[x]$.

Note that ϕ is a ring homomorphism and onto. $\Rightarrow Z[x]/\ker\phi \cong Z$, (by theorem) .

But $\ker \phi = \{a_0+a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n: \phi(a_0+a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n)=0\} = \{a_0+a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n: a_0=0\} = \{a_1x+\dots+a_nx^n: a_i \in Z\} = \langle x \rangle \Rightarrow Z[x]/\langle x \rangle \cong Z$.

(2) Show that $\langle x^2+1 \rangle \subset Z_3[x]$ is a maximal ideal.

Answer

Let $f(x) = x^2+1$, we shall show that $f(x)$ is an irreducible polynomial in $Z_3[x]$. Since $\deg f(x) = 2$, then $f(x)$ has a root in $Z_3[x] \Leftrightarrow f(x)$ is reducible, by 1st fund. theorem.

But $f(x)$ has no root in $Z_3[x]$, because $f(0)=0^2+1=1 \neq 0$, $f(1) = 1^2+1=2 \neq 0$, $f(2)=2^2+1=2 \neq 0$. Thus $f(x)$ is irreducible $\Rightarrow \langle f(x) \rangle$ is maximal ideal.

(3) Show that $Z_3[x]/\langle x^2+1 \rangle$ is a field.

Answer

By (2), $\langle x^2+1 \rangle$ is a maximal ideal in $Z_3[x] \Rightarrow Z_3[x]/\langle x^2+1 \rangle$ is a field.

(4) Show that x^3+3x^2-8 is an irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Answer

We can not apply Eisenstein theorem, since $\nexists p$ (prime number) such that $p|8$, $p|3$, $p \nmid 1$, $p^2 \nmid 8$.

Suppose x^3+3x^2-8 is reducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, \Rightarrow
 $x^3+3x^2-8=(x+a)(x^2+bx+c) = x^3+(a+b)x^2+(ab+c)x+ac \Rightarrow 2=a+b$, $0=ab+c$, $-8=ac$,
which is a contradicts.

EXAMPLE 3.2.25.

1- Let $I=\{\sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i : a_i \in \mathbb{Z}_e , n \in \mathbb{Z}_+\}$. Show that I is a prime ideal.(H.W.).

2- Show that the polynomial x^4+4 can be factored in to linear factors in $\mathbb{Z}_5[x]$. Find this factorization.

Answer

Let $f(x)=x^4+4$

0 is not a root of $f(x)$, since $0^4+4 = 4 \neq 0 \pmod{5}$.

1 is a root of $f(x)$, since $1^4+4=0 \pmod{5}$.

2 is a root of $f(x)$, since $2^4+4=0 \pmod{5}$.

3 is a root of $f(x)$, since $3^4+4=0 \pmod{5}$.

4 is a root of $f(x)$, since $4^4+4=0 \pmod{5}$.

$\therefore f(x)=(x-1)(x-2)(x-3)(x-4)$.

In another way

1 is a root of $f(x)$, so divide x^4+4 by $x-1$, so that $x^4+4=(x-1)(x^3+x^2+x+1)$, by division Algorithm theorem, 2 is a root of x^3+x^2+x+1 , so that divide x^3+x^2+x+1 by $x-2$, we get $x^3+x^2+x+1=(x-2)(x^2+3x-3)$.

But 4 is a root of x^2+3x-3 , so that divide x^2+3x-3 by $x-4$, we get

$x^2+3x-3=(x-4)(x+2)$. Thus $x^4+4=(x-1)(x-2)(x-4)(x+2)=(x-1)(x-2)(x-4)(x-3)$.

3- Let $f(x)= 8x^3+6x^2-9x+24 \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Show that $f(x)$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$.

Answer

Let $p=3$, $3|24$, $3|-9$, $3|-6$, $3 \nmid 8$, $3^2=9 \nmid 24$.

$\therefore f(x)$ is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, by Eisenstein theorem.

3.3. Extension of Fields

DEFINITION 3.3.1.

Let $(F, +, \cdot)$ be a subfield of a field $(F', +, \cdot)$. Then $(F', +, \cdot)$ is called an extension field of $(F, +, \cdot)$.

EXAMPLES 3.3.2.

- (1) $(\mathbb{Q}, +, \cdot)$ is a subfield of $(\mathbb{R}, +, \cdot)$, i.e., $(\mathbb{R}, +, \cdot)$ is an extension field of $(\mathbb{Q}, +, \cdot)$.
- (2) $(\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ is an extension field of $(\mathbb{Q}, +, \cdot)$.
- (3) $(\mathbb{C}, +, \cdot)$ is an extension field of $(\mathbb{R}, +, \cdot)$.

DEFINITION 4.3.3.

An ideal I of a ring R . I is called **reducible ideal** if \exists two ideals J and K of R such that $I \subset J$ and $I \subset K$ and $I = J \cap K$. I is called **irreducible ideal**, if I is not reducible

EXAMPLES 3.3.4.

In a ring Z , $\langle 6 \rangle$ is reducible ideal of Z , since \exists two ideals $\langle 2 \rangle$ and $\langle 3 \rangle$ of Z and $\langle 6 \rangle \subset \langle 2 \rangle$ and $\langle 6 \rangle \subset \langle 3 \rangle$ and $\langle 6 \rangle = \langle 2 \rangle \cap \langle 3 \rangle$.

In a ring Z , $\langle 5 \rangle$ is irreducible ideal of Z , since \nexists two ideals two ideals J and K of R such that $\langle 5 \rangle \subset J$ and $\langle 5 \rangle \subset K$ and $\langle 5 \rangle = J \cap K$.

QUESTION 3.3.5.

Given a field $(F, +, \cdot)$ and an irreducible polynomial over F . Can we construct an extension field $(F', +, \cdot)$ of $(F, +, \cdot)$ such that $f(x) \in F[x] \subseteq F'[x]$ and $f(x)$ has roots in F' .

EXAMPLES 3.3.6.

Let $f(x) = x^2 + 1 \in \mathbb{R}[x]$, $f(x)$ has no roots in \mathbb{R} , but has roots in $\mathbb{R}[x]$.

LEMMA 3.3.7.

Let $(F, +, \cdot), (F', +, \cdot)$ are fields and $f: (F, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (F', +, \cdot)$ be homomorphism ring. Then either f is a trivial mapping or F is isomorphic to $\text{Im } f$.

Proof:

Since f is a homomorphism ring, $\ker f$ is an ideal in F . Hence $\ker f = \{0\}$ or $\ker f = F$ (since F is a field). But by 1st fund. theorem, $F/\ker f \cong \text{Im } f$, so either $F/F = \{0\}$ or $F/\{0\} = F$. Thus either $\{0\} = F/F \cong \text{Im } f$ is trivial mapping or $F = F/\{0\} \cong \text{Im } f$. Thus either f is trivial mapping or $F \cong \text{Im } f$.

Note that: when f is onto, then either $F \cong F'$ or f is trivial mapping.

THEOREM 3.3.8.

Let F is a field. If $f(x)$ is an irreducible polynomial in $F[x]$, then there exists an extension field F' of F in which $f(x)$ has roots.

Proof:

Let $I = \langle f(x) \rangle$, since F is a field and $f(x)$ is irreducible, I is a maximal ideal (by theorem : $f(x)$ is irreducible $f(x) \in F[x] \Leftrightarrow \langle f(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal $\Leftrightarrow F[x]/\langle f(x) \rangle$ is a field.)

Consider $\text{nat}_I: F[x] \Rightarrow F[x]/I$, nat_I is an epimorphism ring. Consider $\text{nat}_{I|F}: F \Rightarrow F[x]/I$, $F \subseteq F[x]$, so by Lemma (3.3.6), either $\text{nat}_{I|F}$ is a trivial mapping or $\text{nat}_{I|F}(F) \cong F$.

If $\text{nat}_{I|F}$ is a zero mapping, then $\text{nat}_{I|F}(1) = 1+I = I$, that $1 \in I \Rightarrow I = F$, which is contradicts. Hence $\text{nat}_{I|F}(F) \cong F$.

That F isomorphic to subring of $F[x]/I$, thus F can be embedded in $F[x]/I$, and so $F[x]/I$ is an extension field of F . To show that $f(x)$ has roots in $F[x]/I$.

Let $f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_nx^n$, then $f(x)+I = a_0 + \dots + a_nx^n + I = 0_{F[x]/I}$.
 $f(x)+I = (a_0+I) + (a_1+I)(x+I) + \dots + (a_n+I)(x+I)^n = I$. By using identification of a_k+I by a_k , then $f(x)+I = a_0 + a_1(x+I) + \dots + a_n(x+I)^n = I$. Thus $f(x+I) = 0_{F[x]/I} = I$.

Hence $x+I$ is a root of $f(x)$ in $F[x]/I$.

To found $F[x]/I$:

Let $F[x]/I = \{g(x)+I: g(x) \in F[x]\}$, by division Algorithm theorem,
 $g(x) = q_1(x)f(x) + r(x)$, where $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg r(x) < \deg f(x)$ and some $q_1(x)$ in $F[x]$.

Thus $g(x)+I = q_1(x)f(x) + r(x)+I$, but $q_1(x)f(x) \in I$, then $g(x)+I = r(x)+I$. But $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg r(x) < \deg f(x) = n$, then

$$g(x)+I = b_0 + b_1x + \dots + b_{n-1}x^{n-1} + I, b_i \in F.$$
$$= b_0 + b_1(x+I) + \dots + b_{n-1}(x+I)^{n-1},$$

Put $x+I = \lambda$. Thus $F[x]/I = \{b_0 + b_1\lambda + \dots + b_{n-1}\lambda^{n-1} : b_i \in F\}$, λ is a root $F(x)$ in $F[x]/I$.

If $f(x)$ is irr in $Z_p[x]$, $\deg f(x) = n$, then $Z_p[x]/\langle f(x) \rangle = \{a_0 + a_1\lambda + \dots + a_{n-1}\lambda^{n-1} : a_i \in Z_p\}$, λ is a root of $f(x)$ in $Z_p[x]/\langle f(x) \rangle$ and since there are only p -choices for each coefficient a_k , we obtain a finite field with p^n elements.

EXAMPLES 3.3.9.

1) Let $f(x) = x^2 + 1 \in Z_3[x]$ has no root $f(x)$ is irreducible over Z_3 , so $I = \langle f(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal and $Z_3[x]/I$ is a field, so by prev. theorem $F' = Z_3[x]/I = \{a_0 + a_1\lambda \mid a_0, a_1 \in Z_3, \lambda = x+I \text{ is a root of } f(x) \text{ in } F'\}$.

2) Let $f(x) = x^3 + x + 1 \in Z_2[x]$ has no root $f(x)$ is irreducible over Z_2 , so $I = \langle f(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal and $Z_2[x]/I$ is a field, so by theorem $F' = Z_2[x]/I = \{a_0 + a_1\lambda + a_2\lambda^2 \mid a_0, a_1, a_2 \in Z_2, \lambda = x+I \text{ is a root of } f(x) \text{ in } F'\}$.

3) Let $f(x) = x^2+1 \in \mathbb{R}[x]$ has no root $f(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{R} , so $I = \langle f(x) \rangle$ is a maximal ideal and $\mathbb{R}[x]/I$ is a field, so by theorem $F' = \mathbb{Z}_2[x]/I = \{ a_0 + a_1 \lambda \mid a_0, a_1 \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda = x + I \text{ is a root of } f(x) \text{ in } F' \}$.

THEOREM 3.3.10. (Unique Factorization theorem)

Each polynomial ring $f(x) \in F[x]$ of positive degree can be written as a product on non zero elements of F and irreducible polynomial's of $F[x]$. A part from the order of the factors, this factorization is unique

Proof: H.W.

COROLLARY 3.3.11.

If $f(x) \in F[x]$ of positive degree and it has no root in F , then there exists an extensions field of F containing all roots of $f(x)$; that is $f(x)$ factored completely in to linear polynomial's of $F[x]$.

Proof:

The proof by induction on degree $f(x)=n$.

If $n=1$, then F is an extensions field of F .

If $n>1$, assume the theorem true for all polynomial's of degree less than n .

If $f(x)$ has an irreducible factor say $g(x)$, so $\deg g(x) < n$. Hence \exists an extensions field F_1 of F such that F_1 has roots of $g(x)$, by theorem (3.3.9).

If there exists another irreducible factor of $f(x)$, say $h(x)$, we can repute this argumen, we get F_2 extension field of F_1 such that F_2 has roots of $h(x)$ and so by repeating this argumen, we get field has all roots of $f(x)$.

EXAMPLES 3.3.12.

Let $f(x) = x^4-5x^2+6 \in \mathbb{Q}[x] \Rightarrow f(x) = (x^2-2)(x^2-3)$, $(x^2-2), (x^2-3)$ are irreducible in $\mathbb{Q}[x]$, put $F_1 = \mathbb{Q}[x]/\langle x^2-2 \rangle = \{ b_0+b_1\lambda : b_0, b_1 \in \mathbb{Q}, \lambda^2-2=0 \} \simeq \{ b_0+b_1\sqrt{2} : b_0, b_1 \in \mathbb{Q} \}$. $\lambda^2-2=0 \Leftrightarrow \lambda, -\lambda$ are root of x^2-2 in F_1 .

Thus $f(x)=(x-\lambda)(x+\lambda)(x^2-3)$. In fact $F_1 \cong \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{2}]$, since $\exists \psi_1 : F_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{2}]$ is defined by $\psi_1(b_0+b_1\lambda) = b_0+b_1\sqrt{2}$, ψ_1 is an isomorphism.

Now, put $F_2 = \mathbb{Q}[x]/\langle x^2-3 \rangle = \{ c_0+c_1\mu : c_0, c_1 \in \mathbb{Q}, \mu^2-3=0 \} \simeq \{ c_0+c_1\sqrt{3} : c_0, c_1 \in \mathbb{Q} \}$. $\mu^2-3=0 \Leftrightarrow \mu, -\mu$ are root of x^2-3 in F_2 .

Thus $f(x) = (x^2-2)(x-\mu)(x+\mu)$. In fact $F_2 \cong \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}]$, since $\exists \psi_2 : F_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{3}]$ is defined by $\psi_2(c_0+c_1\mu) = c_0+c_1\sqrt{3}$, ψ_2 is an isomorphism.

Thus $f(x)=(x-\lambda)(x+\lambda)(x-\mu)(x+\mu)$, i.e., $f(x)=(x-\sqrt{2})(x+\sqrt{2})(x-\sqrt{3})(x+\sqrt{3})$.

CHAPTER FOUR

Noetherian, Artinian and Rings with chain condition

4.1 Noetherian rings

DEFINITION 4.1.1.

A ring R is called Noetherian (or R satisfies ascending chain condition, simply R satisfies (a.c.c) or (ACC)), if every ascending chain of ideals : $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$, terminates. i.e., $\exists k \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $I_k = I_{k+1} = \dots$.

EXAMPLES 4.1.2.

1- $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is Noetherian ring, since any ascending chain of ideals of \mathbb{Z} is of the form $\langle n \rangle \subseteq \langle n_1 \rangle \subseteq \langle n_2 \rangle \subseteq \dots$, where $n_i \in \mathbb{Z}_+$.

(Note that, n_1/n , n_2/n_1 , n_3/n_2 , ..., so n_1/n , n_2/n , n_3/n , ..., , but for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, n has an only finite number of factors). Hence, the ascending chain of ideals must terminates.

2- Every field is a Noetherian ring.

3- Every finite ring is a Noetherian ring.

THEOREM 4.1.3.

For any ring R , the following statements are equivalent :

1- R is a Noetherian ring.

2- Every ideal of R is finite generated ideal.

3- Every nonempty collection S of ideals of R has a maximal element .(i.e., \exists ideal I_0 of S such that for each ideal J of S , $I_0 \subseteq J$).

Proof :

(1) \Rightarrow (2) Let I be any ideal of R and $a_0 \in I$.

If $I = \langle a_0 \rangle$, then I is principle ideal , so I is finite generated ideal.

If $I \neq \langle a_0 \rangle$, then $\exists a_1 \in I$, $a_1 \notin \langle a_0 \rangle$. Hence $\langle a_0 \rangle \subset \langle a_0, a_1 \rangle$. Proceeding in this manner, we get an ascending sequence of ideals of R , namely

$\langle a_0 \rangle \subset \langle a_0, a_1 \rangle \subset \langle a_0, a_1, a_2 \rangle \subset \dots$ does not terminates.

But this is contradicts, since R is a Noetherian ring. Hence I is finite generated ideal of R .

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Let S be a collection of ideals of R . Let $I_0 \in S$.

If I_0 is not maximal element of S , then $\exists I_1 \in S$ such that $I_0 \subset I_1$.

If I_1 is not maximal element of S , then $\exists I_2 \in S$ such that $I_1 \subseteq I_2$.

And so on we can construct an infinite ascending chain $I_0 \subset I_1 \subset I_2 \subset \dots$.

Let $I = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} I_i$, then I is an ideal of R (check). By (2), I is a finite generated ideal of R , so

$\exists a_1, \dots, a_n \in I$ such that $I = \langle a_1, \dots, a_n \rangle$. Now, for each $a_j, j=1, \dots, n$ such that $a_j \in I$, $\exists i_j \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $a_j \in I_{i_j}$ (since $I = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} I_i$). Let $K = \max \{ i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n \}$. Hence $a_j \in I_K \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and this implies $I \subseteq I_K$. But $I_K \subseteq I$. Hence $I = I_K$.

Now, for all $m \geq k$, $I_m \subseteq I = I_K$ which implies $I_m = I_K$. Hence S has a maximal element.

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Suppose $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$, be an ascending chain of ideals of R , let $S = \{ I_i \}, i = 1, 2, \dots$. By (3), S has a maximal element say I_k , thus for any $m \geq k$, $I_m = I_k$, since $\forall m \geq k$, $I_k \subseteq I_m$. But I_k is maximal element, so $I_m \subseteq I_k$. Thus $I_m = I_k, \forall m \geq k$; that is R is a Noetherian ring.

EXAMPLE 4.1.4.

Let X be an infinite set, the ring $(P(X), \Delta, \cap)$ is not Noetherian ring, since $\exists I$ is ideal of $P(X)$ where $I = \{ A \in P(X); A \text{ is a finite set} \}$ and I is not finite generated.

REMARK 4.1.5.

1- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a Noetherian ring, S is a subring of R , then it may be that S is not Noetherian ring. (Give example).

2- For any rings $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(R', +', \cdot')$, if $(R, +, \cdot) \cong (R', +', \cdot')$, then $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a Noetherian ring. $\Leftrightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ is a Noetherian ring.

PROPOSITION 4.1.6.

Every epimorphism image of Noetherian is a Noetherian ring.

Proof :

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be an epimorphism and R be a Noetherian ring, then $R/\ker f \cong R'$. But we can show that $R/\ker f$ is a Noetherian ring, by setting $\ker f = K$ as follows. Since R is Noetherian, for any ideal I of R , I is a finite generated ideal. But every ideal of R/K has the form I/K , where I is an ideal of R and $K \subseteq I$.

Assume

$I = \langle a_1, \dots, a_n \rangle$, for some $a_1, \dots, a_n \in I$, then $I/K = \langle a_1+K, \dots, a_n+K \rangle$, so I/K is a finite generated ideal, hence $R/\ker f$ is a Noetherian ring. By remark(4.1.4), R' is a Noetherian ring.

COROLLARY 4.1.7.

Let R be a ring and I be an ideal of R . Then R is a Noetherian $\Rightarrow R/I$ is a Noetherian ring.

Proof : H.W.

PROPOSITION 4.1.8.

Every homomorphism preimage of Noetherian is a Noetherian ring .

Proof : H.W.

PROPOSITION 4.1.9.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(R', +', \cdot')$ be rings , I is ideal of R , J is ideal of R' . $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be an homomorphism ring . Then

- 1) $f^{-1}(J) = J \cap \text{Im } f$ & $f(f^{-1}(J)) = J$ if f is onto.
- 2) $f^{-1}(f(I)) = I + \ker f$ & $f(f^{-1}(f(I))) = I$ if f is 1-1.

Proof :

1) Let $y \in f^{-1}(J)$, then $y = f(x)$, for some $x \in f^{-1}(J)$, thus $y = f(x) \in J$, then $y \in J \cap \text{Im } f$.

Conversely , $y \in J \cap \text{Im } f$, so that $y = f(x) \in J$, thus $x \in f^{-1}(J)$. Hence $y \in f^{-1}(J)$.

2) Let $x \in f^{-1}(f(I))$, then $f(x) \in f(I)$, thus $f(x) = f(i)$, for some $i \in I \Rightarrow f(x) - f(i) = 0' \Rightarrow f(x-i) = 0'$, then $x-i \in \ker f$. So $x = I + (x-i) \in I + \ker f$.

Conversely, $x \in I + \ker f$, so that $x = I + a$, $I \in I$, $a \in \ker f$, thus $f(x) = f(i) + f(a) = f(i) + 0' = f(i) \in f(I)$. Hence $x \in f^{-1}(f(I))$.

LEMMA 4.1.10. (Modular Law)

Let R be a ring and I, J and K be ideals of R such that $J \subseteq I$. Then $I \cap (J+K) = J+(I \cap K)$.

Proof :

Since $J \subseteq I$ and $I \cap K \subseteq I$ and $I \cap K \subseteq K$. Since $I \cap K \subseteq I$ implies that $J+(I \cap K) \subseteq I$. But $J+(I \cap K) \subseteq J+K$, since $I \cap K \subseteq K$. Hence $J+(I \cap K) \subseteq I \cap (J+K) \dots (1)$.

Now, let $x \in I \cap (J+K)$, thus $x \in I$ and $x \in J+K$ and $x = a+b$, for some $a \in J$, $b \in K$, this implies $x-a = b \in I \cap K$. Thus $x = a+b \in J+(I \cap K)$, then $I \cap (J+K) \subseteq J+(I \cap K) \dots (2)$.

By (1) and (2), we get $J+(I \cap K) = I \cap (J+K)$.

DEFINITION 4.1.11.

An ideal I of a ring R . I is a Noetherian ideal of R if every ascending chain of ideals of R contained in I terminates.

THEOREM 4.1.12.

Let R be a ring and I be an ideal of R . Then R is a Noetherian $\Leftrightarrow I$ and R/I are Noetherian .

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) If R is a Noetherian, then R/I is a Noetherian by corollary (4.1.7). Also, I is Noetherian by definition (4.1.11).

(\Leftarrow) Let $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$, be an ascending chain of ideals of R , then $I_1 \cap I \subseteq I_2 \cap I \subseteq \dots$, be an ascending chain of ideals of R contained in I . Hence $\exists m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $I_m \cap I = I_n \cap I, \forall n \geq m$.

On the other hand, $(I_1+I)/I \subseteq (I_2+I)/I \subseteq \dots$ (1).

is ascending chain of ideals of R/I , so that $\exists t \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $(I_t+I)/I = (I_s+I)/I, \forall s \geq t$ (2).

Hence, $I_t+I = I_s \cap I$.

Let $r = \max \{t, m\}$, then, $\forall k \geq r, I_k = I_k \cap (I_k+I)$, since $I_k \subseteq I_k+I$,
 $= I_k \cap (I_t+I) = I_t + (I_k \cap I) = I_t + (I_m \cap I) = I_m \cap (I_t+I) = I_m \cap (I_r+I) = I_r + (I_m \cap I) = I_r + (I_r \cap I) = I_r$.

THEOREM 4.1.13. (Hilbert Basis Theorem)

Let R be a Noetherian ring with unity, then $R[x]$ is a Noetherian ring, where $R[x]$ is the ring of polynomial with one index x over R .

Proof : H.W.

COROLLARY 4.1.14.

Let R be a Noetherian ring with unity, then $R[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ is a Noetherian ring.

DEFINITION 4.1.15.

An ideal I of a ring R is called reducible if \exists two ideals J and K of R such that $I \subset J$ and $I \subset K$ and $I = J \cap K$. I is called irreducible if I is not reducible.

THEOREM 4.1.16.

In Noetherian ring, every ideal is a finite intersection of irreducible ideals.

Proof :

Suppose there exists an ideal for which the assertion is false. Let F be the family of all ideals which can not be represented as a finite intersection of irreducible ideals.

Hence $F \neq \emptyset$. Since R is Noetherian, F has a maximal element say A .

Now, A can not be irreducible, so A is reducible, thus $A = B \cap C, A \subset B$ and $C \subset A$.

Hence by maximality of $A, B \notin F, C \notin F$ and so $B = B_1 \cap \dots \cap B_n, C = C_1 \cap \dots \cap C_m$, where $B_1, \dots, B_n, C_1, \dots, C_m$ are irreducible ideals of R . Thus

$A = B_1 \cap \dots \cap B_n \cap C_1 \cap \dots \cap C_m$; that is A is a finite intersection of irreducible ideals contradicts. Thus $F = \emptyset$.

THEOREM 4.1.17.

If R is a Noetherian ring, then every irreducible ideal of R is a primary ideal.

Proof :

It is enough to prove , if I is a proper ideal of R such that I is not primary, then I is reducible.

Since I is not primary, $\exists a, b \in R$ such that $ab \in I, a \notin I, b^n \notin I, \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$.

Let $J = I + \langle a \rangle \dots(1)$.

Thus $I \subset J$. For each $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, let $K_n = \{ r \in R: rb^n \in I \}$, then K_n is an ideal of R (check?) and $I \subseteq K, \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$.

Moreover, $K_1 \subseteq K_2 \subseteq \dots$, since R is a Noetherian ring, $\exists m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $K_m \subseteq K_{m+1} = \dots$. That is if $rb^{m+1} \in I$, then $rb^m \in I$.

Let $K = I + \langle b^m \rangle$, so $I \subset K$. Thus $I \subset J \cap K$. In fact $I = J \cap K$ and to see this, let $x \in J \cap K$, $x \in J$ & $x \in K$

$$\Rightarrow x = i_1 + r_1a = i_2 + r_2b^m .$$

Hence $i_1b + r_1ab = i_2b + r_2b^{m+1} \Rightarrow r_2b^{m+1} = i_1b + r_1ab - i_2b \in I \Rightarrow r_2 \in K_{m+1} = K_m$. Thus $r_2 \in K_m$ and so $r_2b^m \in I$ implies that $x \in I$. Hence $I = J \cap K$ and I is a reducible ideal.

COROLLARY 4.1.18.

If R is a Noetherian ring, then every proper ideal of R can be represented as a finite intersection of primary ideals.

Proof :

It is clear by theorem (4.1.16) and theorem (4.1.17). Enough to prove , if I is a proper ideal of R such that I is not primary, then I is reducible. Since I is not primary, $\exists a, b \in R$ such that $ab \in I, a \notin I, b^n \notin I, \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$.

LEMMA 4.1.19.

Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings with unity 1. If $R = R_1 \oplus R_2$ and I is ideal of R $\Leftrightarrow \exists I_1$ is ideal of R_1 and I_2 is ideal of R_2 such that $I = I_1 \oplus I_2$

Proof : H.W.

THEOREM 4.1.20.

Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings with unity 1 and $R = R_1 \oplus R_2$. Then R is a Noetherian ring $\Leftrightarrow R_1$ and R_2 are Noetherian rings.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Let $f_1 : R \rightarrow R_1, f_2 : R \rightarrow R_2$ be nat. proj., so R_1 and R_2 are Noetherian rings.

(\Leftarrow) Let $I_1 \subseteq I_2 \subseteq \dots$, be an ascending chain of ideals of R. But $I_i = J_i \oplus K_i, \forall i = 1, \dots$ (check?).

Hence $J_1 \oplus K_1 \subseteq J_2 \oplus K_2 \subseteq \dots$, thus $J_1 \subseteq J_2 \subseteq \dots$, and $K_1 \subseteq K_2 \subseteq \dots, \Rightarrow \exists m, n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $J_m = J_{m+1} = \dots$ and $K_n = K_{n+1} = \dots$. Let $r = \max \{ m, n \}$, then

$I_r = I_{r+1} = \dots$. Hence R is a Noetherian ring .

LEMMA 4.1.21.

Let R be a ring, let $C = \{ I : I \text{ is not finite generated ideal} \}$. If M is a maximal ideal of C , then M is a prime ideal of C .

Proof : H.W.

THEOREM 4.1.22. (Cohen Theorem)

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1. R is a Noetherian ring \Leftrightarrow every prime ideal of R is a finite generated .

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) It is clear.

(\Leftarrow) Let $C = \{ I : I \text{ is not finite generated ideal, } I \subseteq R \}$. Suppose $C \neq \emptyset$, then C has a maximal ideal say M , by Zorns lemma $\Rightarrow M$ is a prime ideal by lemma(4.1.21) $\Rightarrow M$ is a finite generated ideal, by hyp. , so we get contradicts. Thus $C = \emptyset$, i.e., $\forall I \subseteq R, I$ is a finite generated ideal .Therefore, R is a Noetherian ring.

PROPOSITION 4.1.23.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity. $f : (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be a homomorphism ring and onto. If R is a Noetherian ring, then f is 1-1.

Proof :

Let $a \in \ker f$ and suppose $a \neq 0, \{0\} \subseteq \ker f \subseteq \ker f^2 \subseteq \dots \Rightarrow$ Since R is a Noetherian $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $\ker f^n = \ker f^{n+1} = \dots, .$

Since f is onto, $f^n(b) = f(a) = 0$, thus $b \in \ker f^{n+1}$. But $\ker f^n = \ker f^{n+1}$, so that $b \in \ker f^n$. Thus $f^n(b) = 0$, which is contradicts, since $f^n(b) = a \neq 0$.

Therefore, $\ker f = 0$, then f is 1-1.

THEOREM 4.1.24.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity and I be an ideal of R . If R is a Noetherian ring, then \sqrt{I}/I is nilpotent ideal of R .

Proof :

Since R is a Noetherian ring, R/I is a Noetherian ring, hence \sqrt{I}/I is finite generated ideal.

Let $\bar{x} = x + I \in \sqrt{I}/I$, so $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $x^n \in I \Rightarrow (\bar{x})^n = x^n + I = I = 0_{R/I}$, thus \bar{x} is a nilpotent element. Hence every ideal of \sqrt{I}/I is a nilpotent ideal, but \sqrt{I}/I is a finite generated. So \sqrt{I}/I is a nilpotent ideal.

4.2 Artinian rings

DEFINITION 4.2.1.

A ring R is called Artinian (or R satisfies descending chain condition, simply R satisfies (d.c.c) or (DCC)), if every ascending chain of ideals : $I_1 \supseteq I_2 \supseteq \dots$, terminates. i.e.,

$\exists k \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $I_k = I_{k+1} = \dots$.

EXAMPLES 4.2.2.

- 1- Every finite ring satisfies descending chain of ideals . i.e., R is an Artinian ring.
- 2- $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is not Artinian ring, since any descending chain of ideals of \mathbb{Z} is of the form $\langle 2 \rangle \supset \langle 2^2 \rangle \supset \langle 2^3 \rangle \supset \dots$.
- 3- The ring $F[x]$ is not Artinian ring, since the chain $\langle x \rangle \supset \langle x^2 \rangle \supset \langle x^3 \rangle \supset \dots$, does not terminate.

THEOREM 4.2.3.

For any ring R , the following statements are equivalent :

- 1- R is an Artinian ring.
- 2- Every nonempty collection S of ideals of R has a minimal element .(i.e., \exists ideal B_0 of S such that for each ideal A of S , $A \subseteq B_0$ implies that $A = B_0$).

Proof :

(1) \Rightarrow (2) Let $N_0 \in S$, if N_0 is not minimal element, then there exists an ideal $N_1 \in S$ such that $N_0 \supset N_1$.

If N_1 is not minimal element, then there exists an ideal $N_2 \in S$ such that $N_1 \supset N_2$.
In case S has no minimal element, we can construct a sequence of ideals of R

$N_0 \supset N_1 \supset N_2 \supset \dots$

i.e., we get an infinite descending chain of ideals of R which is a contradiction .
Hence R has a minimal element.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Suppose we have an infinite descending chain of ideals of R , $I_1 \supset I_2 \supset I_3 \supset \dots$.

Let $S = \{ I_i \}$, where $i=1,2,\dots$. S has a minimal element say I_m , but $I_m \supseteq I_{m+1} \supseteq \dots$.
Hence $I_m = I_{m+1} = \dots$. Therefore, R is an Artinian ring.

REMARK 4.2.4.

- 1- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an Artinian ring, S is a subring of R , then it may be that S is not an Artinian ring. (Give example).
(Q is an Artinian ring, but the subring Z of Q is not Artinian).

2- For any rings $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(R', +', \cdot')$, if $(R, +, \cdot) \cong (R', +', \cdot')$, then $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an Artinian ring. $\Leftrightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ is an Artinian ring.

PROPOSITION 4.2.5.

Every epimorphism image of Artinian is an Artinian ring .

Proof :

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be an epimorphism and R be an Artinian ring, then $R/\ker f \cong R'$. But we can show that $R/\ker f$ is an Artinian ring, by setting $\ker f = K$ as follows . Since R is Artinian, for any ideal I of R , I is a finite generated ideal. But every ideal of R/K has the form I/K , where I is an ideal of R and $K \subseteq I$. Assume $I = \langle a_1, \dots, a_n \rangle$, for some $a_1, \dots, a_n \in I$, then $I/K = \langle a_1+K, \dots, a_n+K \rangle$, so I/K is a finite generated ideal, hence $R/\ker f$ is an Artinian ring . By remark (4.2.4), R' is an Artinian ring .

PROPOSITION 4.2.6.

Let I be an ideal of an Artinian ring R . Then R/I is an Artinian ring .

Proof :

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be an epimorphism and R be an Artinian ring. Let $J_1/I \supseteq J_2/I \supseteq \dots$ be a descending chain of ideals of R/I . Then $J_1 \supseteq J_2 \supseteq \dots$ be a descending chain of ideals of R , so $\exists m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $J_m = J_{m+1} = \dots$. Hence R/I is an Artinian ring .

PROPOSITION 4.2.7.

Every homomorphism preimage of Artinian is an Artinian ring .

Proof : H.W.

PROPOSITION 4.2.8.

Let R be commutative ring with unity. If R is an Artinian and integral domain, then R is a field .

Proof :

Let $a \in R$, $a \neq 0$, then $\langle a \rangle \supseteq \langle a^2 \rangle \supseteq \langle a^3 \rangle \dots$. Since R is an Artinian, $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $\langle a^n \rangle = \langle a^{n+1} \rangle \dots = \dots$. Hence $a^n = r a^{n+1} \Rightarrow a^n (1 - r a) = 0$. But R is integral domain, so that R has no zero divisors, hence $a^n \neq 0$, it follows that $1 - r a = 0$. i.e., $1 = r a$, thus a is an invertible element, then R is a field .

COROLLARY 4.2.9.

Let R be commutative ring with unity. If R is an Artinian and I is an ideal of R , then I is maximal ideal if and only if, I is a prime ideal.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) it is clear.

(\Leftarrow) Let I is a prime ideal. To prove I is maximal ideal.

Since R is an Artinian ring, then R/I is an Artinian . Also I is prime ideal implies that R/I is integral domain, thus R/I is an Artinian and integral domain, by proposition (4.2.8), R/I is a field. Hence I is a prime ideal.

THEOREM 4.2.10.

Let R_1 and R_2 be two commutative rings with unities and $R = R_1 \oplus R_2$. Then R is an Artinian ring $\Leftrightarrow R_1$ and R_2 are Artinian rings.

Proof :

(\Rightarrow) Let $f_1 : R_1 \oplus R_2 \rightarrow R_1$, $f_2 : R_1 \oplus R_2 \rightarrow R_2$ be nat. proj., so R_1 and R_2 are Artinian rings.

(\Leftarrow) Let $I_1 \supseteq I_2 \supseteq \dots$, be an ascending chain of ideals of R . But $I_i = J_i \oplus K_i$, $\forall i = 1, \dots$ (check?).

Hence $J_1 \oplus K_1 \supseteq J_2 \oplus K_2 \supseteq \dots$, thus $J_1 \supseteq J_2 \supseteq \dots$, and $K_1 \supseteq K_2 \supseteq \dots$,

$\Rightarrow \exists m, n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $J_m = J_{m+1} = \dots$ and $K_n = K_{n+1} = \dots$. Let $r = \max \{ n, m \}$, then $I_r = I_{r+1} = \dots$. Hence R is an Artinian ring.

4.3 Rings with chain condition

PROPOSITION 4.3.1.

The radical of an Artinian ring is nilpotent.

Proof :

Among the powers of $J(R)$ there is a smallest, say $B = (\sqrt{R})^n$. Then $B^2 = B$. Assume that $B \neq 0$ and let A be minimal in the set of ideals contained in B such that $AB \neq 0$. Then $aB \neq 0$, for some $a \in A$. Now $aB \subset A \subset B$, $(aB)B = aB^2 = aB \neq 0$, hence $aB = A$.

Therefore $ab = a$, for some $b \in B$. Now $b \in B \subset \sqrt{R}$, hence there exists $c \in R$ such that $(1 - b)c = 1$, hence $a = a(1 - b)c = 0$. This is a contradiction, and so $B = 0$, as required.

COROLLARY 4.3.2.

In an Artinian ring, the radical is the largest nilpotent ideal.

Proof :

Any nilpotent ideal is contained in the prime radical $J(R)$, and this is contained in \sqrt{R} . ($J(R) \subset \sqrt{R}$)

COROLLARY 4.3.3.

If R is an Artinian then $\sqrt{R} = J(R)$.

Proof : H.W.

We recall that a regular ring is a ring in which for every element a there exists an element a' such that $aa'a = a$. Putting $e = aa'$, we see that $e^2 = e$ and that $aR = eR$, hence that every principal ideal is a direct summand.

Conversely, this property implies that the ring is regular. For from $aR = eR$ we deduce that $e = aa'$ for some $a' \in R$, hence that $aa'a = ea = a$.

LEMMA 4.3.4. (von Neumann).

In a regular ring every finitely generated ideal is principal.

Proof :

It suffices to consider a ideal $aR + bR$. Now $aR = eR$, where $e^2 = e$, and $bR = ebR + (1 - e)bR$. Therefore $aR + bR = eR + (1 - e)bR = eR + fR$, where $f^2 = f$ and $ef = 0$.

Put $g = f(1 - e)$,

Then $gf = f(1 - e)f = f(f - ef) = f^2 = f$, $g^2 = gf(1 - e) = f(1 - e) = g$, $eg = 0 = ge$.

Now, $g \in fR$ and $f \in gR$, hence $fR = gR$. Therefore $aR + bR = eR + gR$.

We claim that this is the same as $(e + g)R$. Indeed, $er + gr' = (e + g)(er + gr')$, hence $eR + gR \subset (e + g)R$, and the converse is obvious. Thus $aR + bR = (e + g)R$, as required.

PROPOSITION 4.3.5.

The following statements concerning the ring R are equivalent:

- (1) R is completely reducible.
- (2) R is Artinian and regular.
- (3) R is Artinian and semiprimitive.
- (4) R is Artinian and semiprime.
- (5) R is Noetherian and regular.

Note that :- the word " " in conditions (2) to (5) can be replaced by "left," since condition (1) is symmetrical.

Proof :

Since every regular ring is semiprimitive (for $1 - aa'$ is a zero-divisor for every $a \neq 0$) and every semiprimitive ring is semiprime, therefore $(2) \Rightarrow (3) \Rightarrow (4)$.

Assume (1), then R is a direct sum of finitely many minimal ideals A_1, \dots, A_n . We thus have a composition series $A_1 \subset A_1 + A_2 \subset \dots \subset R$, hence R is Artinian and Noetherian.

Moreover, every ideal is a direct summand, in particular every principal ideal, hence R is regular. Thus $(1) \Rightarrow (2)$ and $(1) \Rightarrow (5)$.

Assume (4). By Proposition (2.2.1), the intersection of all maximal ideals is 0. Since R is Artinian, already a finite number of these have zero intersection :

$$M_1 \cap M_2 \cap \dots \cap M_n = 0$$

We may assume that M_i does not contain $A = \bigcap_{j \neq i} M_j$ (or else M_i could have been omitted in the first place). Therefore $M_i + A_i = R$.

On the other hand, $M_i \cap A_i = 0$, hence $A_i \cong R/M_i$, and this is an irreducible R -module. Thus $A_i = e_i R$, $e_i^2 = e_i \in R$, and $M_i = (1 - e_i)R$. Let $e = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i$, then $e - 1 = (e_i - 1) + \sum_{i \neq j} e_i \in M_i + M_i$, for $j \neq i \Rightarrow e_j \in A_j \subset M_i$.

Therefore $e - 1 \in \bigcap_{i=1}^n M_i = 0$.

Therefore $1 = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i$, and so $R = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i$ is completely reducible. Thus $(4) \Rightarrow (1)$.

Assume (5). Since R is Noetherian, every ideal is finitely generated. Since R is regular, every finitely generated ideal is principal, by the above lemma, hence a direct summand. Therefore every ideal is a direct summand, hence R is completely reducible. Thus $(5) \Rightarrow (1)$.

PROPOSITION 4.3.6.

If R is Artinian ring, then any R -module is Noetherian if and only if, it is Artinian.

Proof :

Let $N = \sqrt{R}$, then $N^p = 0$, for some positive integer p , by Proposition (2.2.1). Now, consider any Artinian R -module. This has a chain of submodules $A \supset AN \supset AN^2 \supset \dots \supset AN^p = 0$, with factor modules $F_k = AN^{k-1}/AN^k$, $k = 1, \dots, p$. Now F_k is annihilated by N , hence may be regarded as an R/N -module. By Proposition(2.2.5), R/N is completely reducible, hence F_k is completely reducible as an R/N -module and therefore also as an R -module. Being Artinian, F_k is the direct sum of a finite number of irreducible R -modules, hence F_k is also Noetherian. Thus $AN^{p-1}(= F_p)$ and $AN^{p-2}/AN^{p-1} (= F_{p-1})$ are Noetherian, hence so is AN^{p-2} . Continuing in this fashion, we see that A is Noetherian.

Interchanging the words "Artinian" and "Noetherian" in this proof we get the converse result.

COROLLARY 4.3.7.

Every Artinian ring is Noetherian.

Proof : H.W.

The ring of integers shows that the converse of this does not hold.

LEMMA 4.2.8.

The prime radical of R is the smallest ideal K such that R/K is semiprime.

PROPOSITION 4.3.9.

In a Noetherian ring the prime radical is the largest nilpotent ideal.

Proof :

Let R be Noetherian, N any maximal nilpotent ideal, say $N^k = 0$. In view of the binomial theorem, $(N^k=0 \ \& \ N^{k'}=0) \Rightarrow (N+N')^{k+k'}=0$. Therefore, N is the largest nilpotent ideal. Being nilpotent, N is contained in $\text{rad } R$. Now, suppose A is any ideal such that $A^m \subset N$, m some positive integer. Then A is nilpotent, hence $A \subset N$. Thus R/N is semiprime, and so $N = J(R)$, by lemma (4.3.8).

DEFINITION 4.3.10.

A subset of a ring is called nil if every element is nilpotent.

We know that the prime radical of any ring is nil.

THEOREM 4.3.11. (Levitzki theorem).

In a Noetherian ring the prime radical is the largest nil left ideal.

Proof : (Utumi).

Let R be Noetherian, N any nil left ideal in R . We claim that $N \subset J(R)$.

First let us assume that R is semiprime; we shall show that $N = 0$. Otherwise pick $n \in N, n \neq 0$, so that $n^r = \{s \in R \mid ns = 0\}$ is maximal.

Consider any $x \in R$ such that $xn \neq 0$, and let $k = k(x)$ be the smallest positive integer for which $(xn)^k = 0$. Then $k > 1$ and $(xn)^{k-1} \neq 0$.

Now, any annihilator of n also annihilates $(xn)^{k-1}$, hence $n^r = ((xn)^{k-1})^r$, by maximality of n^r . Therefore, $xn \in n^r$, that is $nxn = 0$. Thus $nRn = 0$, and so $n = 0$, since R is semiprime.

Next, consider the general situation where R is no longer assumed to be semiprime. The canonical image of N in the Noetherian ring $R/J(R)$ is zero by the above, hence $N \subset J(R)$, as was to be proved.

COROLLARY 4.3.12.

In a Noetherian ring every nil ideal is nilpotent.

Proof : H.W.

The following important result is known as the Hilbert Basis Theorem.

PROPOSITION 4.3.13.

Let $R[x]$ be the ring obtained from R by adjoining an indeterminate x which commutes with all elements of R . Then $R[x]$ is Noetherian if R is.

Proof : H.W.

COROLLARY 4.3.14.

Let $R[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ be the ring obtained from R by adjoining n indeterminates x_i which commute with all elements of R and with each other. Then this is Noetherian if R is.

Proof : H.W.

EXERCISES

1. Show that every factor ring of a Noetherian (Artinian) ring is Noetherian (Artinian).
2. Show that a finite direct product of Noetherian (Artinian) rings is Noetherian (Artinian).
3. If R contains a division ring D as a subring so that R_D is finite dimensional, show that R is Artinian.
4. If R is Noetherian (Artinian) then every finitely generated R -module is Noetherian (Artinian).

5. Show that an Artinian ring without zero-divisors is a division ring.

CHAPTER FIVE

GREATEST COMMON DIVISOR

5.1. Greatest common divisor

DEFINITION 5.1.1.

Let R be a ring and $a, b \in R$,

- (1) We say a divides b (written $a|b$), if $\exists c \in R$ such that $b=ac$.
- (2) Let $d \in R$. if $d|a$ and $d|b$, then d is called a greatest common divisor (g.c.d) of a and b . If for any $c \in R$, $c|a$ and $c|b \Rightarrow c|d$.

REMARK 5.1.2.

- (1) If $a|b$ and $b|c$ in a ring R , then $a|c$
- (2) If $a|b$ and $a|c$, then $a|bx+cy$ for any $x, y \in R$, where R is a commutative ring.

DEFINITION 5.1.3.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1 .

- (1) Let $u \in R$ is called unit if $\exists v \in R$ such that $u.v = v.u = 1$.
- (2) Let $a, b \in R$. a, b are associates, if \exists unit u such that $a=ub$.
- (3) Let $\pi \in R$. π is called irreducible if $\pi \neq 0$, π is not a unit and if $\pi = \alpha.\beta$ (with $\alpha, \beta \in R$), then either α or β is a unit.
- (4) Let $\pi \in R$. π is called prime if $\pi \neq 0$, π is not unit and if $\pi|\alpha.\beta$ (with $\alpha, \beta \in R$). It follows that either $\pi|\alpha$ or $\pi|\beta$ (or both).
- (6) Let $a, b \in R$. a, b are relatively prime if g.c.d. of a, b is 1 .

EXAMPLES 5.1.4.

- (1) $\bar{2}$ is unit $(\mathbb{Z}_3, +_3, \cdot_3)$, $\bar{2} \cdot \bar{2} = \bar{1}$.
- (2) $1, -1$ are the only units in $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $1 \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot 1 = 1$ and $(-1) \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot (-1) = -1$.
- (3) $1, -1$ are associate in $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$, $1 = (1) \cdot (1)$ and $-1 = (1) \cdot (-1)$.
- (4) $\bar{2}, \bar{4}$ are associate in $(\mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12}, \cdot_{12})$, $\bar{2} = (\bar{1}) \cdot (\bar{2})$ and $\bar{4} = (\bar{1}) \cdot (\bar{4})$.

DEFINITION 5.1.6.

Let $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$ be a ring and $\alpha = a + b\sqrt{d} \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$. The norm of α , denoted by $N(\alpha)$, is defined by

$$N(\alpha) = |a^2 - db^2|.$$

LEMMA 5.1.6.

- 1- $N(\alpha)$ is nonnegative integer.
- 2- $N(\alpha) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \alpha = 0$.
- 3- For $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$, $N(\alpha.\beta) = N(\alpha) .N(\beta)$.

Proof: H.W.

THEOREM 5.1.6.

Let $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$ be a ring. Units are

- i- 1, -1, i, -i if $d = -1$;
- ii- 1, -1 if $d < -1$;
- iii- 1, -1 and infinitely many others if $d > 1$.

Proof:

Suppose $u = \delta + t\sqrt{d}$ is a unite in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$. Then for some $v \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$, $uv = 1$. Hence $N(uv) = N(1) = 1$. So $N(u) .N(v) = 1$, but $N(u), N(v) \geq 0$, so that $N(u) = 1$.

If $d = -1$, then $N(u) = s^2 + t^2 = s^2 - (-1)t^2 = 1$, implies that $s = \pm 1, t = 0$, or $s = 0, t = \pm 1$.

Hence $u = 1 + 0.\sqrt{-1} = 1$ or $u = -1$ or $u = 0 + \sqrt{-1} = i$ or $u = 0 - \sqrt{-1} = -i$, that is 1, -1, i, -i are the units of $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{d}]$.

If $d = -1$, . If $d > 0$, $N(u) = s^2 - (d)t^2 = 1$,

But for d is not perfect square (for example: $d = 3, 2, 5, \dots$, the equation $s^2 - dt^2 = 1$ has infinitely many solutions as $2 + \sqrt{3}$ is unit in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{3}]$, since

$$(2 + \sqrt{3})(2 - \sqrt{3}) = 1).$$

Further, u^n is unite, $\forall n \geq 1$, since $u^n .(u^{-1})^n = (u . u^{-1})^n = 1$.

If $d < -1$, $N(u) = s^2 - (d)t^2 = 1$, but $s^2 \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, $-dt^2 \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, implies that $s = \pm 1, t = 0$ or $s = 0, t = \pm 1$, thus $u = 1$ or $u = -1$.

EXAMPLES 5.1.7.

- 1- In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-3}], +, \cdot)$, $(1 + \sqrt{-3})(1 - \sqrt{-3}) = 4 = 2.2$. Thus 4 has two factorizations.

We can show that $(1 + \sqrt{-3})$ is irreducible element in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-3}]$.

$(1 + \sqrt{-3}) = (a + b\sqrt{-3})(c + d\sqrt{-3})$, then $N(1 + \sqrt{-3}) = N(a + b\sqrt{-3}) N(c + d\sqrt{-3}) \Rightarrow 4 = (a^2 + 3b^2)(c^2 + 3d^2)$. Then $a^2 + 3b^2 = 2$ has no solution in \mathbb{Z} , we see that $a^2 + 3b^2 = 1$ or $a^2 + 3b^2 = 4$.

If $a^2 + 3b^2 = 1$, then $a = \pm 1, b = 0$, thus $a + b\sqrt{-3} = 1$ or $a + b\sqrt{-3} = -1$; that is $a + b\sqrt{-3}$ is unit.

If $a^2 + 3b^2 = 4$, then $c^2 + 3d^2 = 1$, so we get $c + d\sqrt{-3} = 1$ or $c + d\sqrt{-3} = -1$; that is $c + d\sqrt{-3}$ is unit.

Thus if $(1 + \sqrt{-3}) = (a + b\sqrt{-3})(c + d\sqrt{-3})$, then either $a + b\sqrt{-3}$ is unit or $c + d\sqrt{-3}$ is unit.

Also, $1 + \sqrt{-3} \neq 0$ and $1 + \sqrt{-3}$ is not unit. Hence $1 + \sqrt{-3}$ is irreducible element in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-3}]$.

Similarly, $1 - \sqrt{-3}$, 2 are irreducible elements in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-3}]$.

2- In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}], +, \cdot)$, prove that a) $3 \nmid (1 + 2\sqrt{-5})$ b) 3 is irreducible element, but not prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$.

a) Suppose $3 \mid (1 + 2\sqrt{-5})$, thus $\exists a + b\sqrt{-5} \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$ such that

$$1 + 2\sqrt{-5} = 3(a + b\sqrt{-5})$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 + 2\sqrt{-5} = 3a + 3b\sqrt{-5} \Rightarrow 1 = 3a, 2 = 3b \Rightarrow a = 1/3 \notin \mathbb{Z}, b = 2/3 \notin \mathbb{Z}. \text{ Then } 3 \nmid (1 + 2\sqrt{-5}).$$

Hence $a + b\sqrt{-5} \notin \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$, which is contradicts.

$$\text{b) Let } (1 + 2\sqrt{-5})(1 - 2\sqrt{-5}) = 1 - 4(-5) = 1 + 20 = 21.$$

Since $3 \mid 21$, so that $3 \mid (1 + 2\sqrt{-5})(1 - 2\sqrt{-5})$, but $3 \nmid (1 + 2\sqrt{-5})$, and

$3 \nmid (1 - 2\sqrt{-5})$, thus 3 is not prime in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$.

$3 \neq 0$, 3 is not unit. Suppose $3 = (a + b\sqrt{-5})(c + d\sqrt{-5})$, then $N(3) = N(a + b\sqrt{-5})$

$$N(c + d\sqrt{-5}) \Rightarrow$$

$3 \cdot 3 = 3^2 = (a^2 + 5b^2)(c^2 + 5d^2)$. Then $a^2 + 5b^2 = 3$ has no solution in \mathbb{Z} , we see that $a^2 + 5b^2 \geq 5$. Thus $a^2 + 5b^2 = 1$ and so $a = \pm 1, b = 0$, thus $a + b\sqrt{-5} = 1$ or $a + b\sqrt{-5} = -1$; that is $a + b\sqrt{-5}$ is unit.

So that $3 = (\text{unit})(c + d\sqrt{-5})$, then $3 = 1(c + d\sqrt{-5})$ and thus $c = 3, d = 0$ or $3 = (-1)(c + d\sqrt{-5})$ and thus $c = -3, d = 0$.

Similarly, $c^2 + 5d^2 = 3$ has no solution in \mathbb{Z} , so $c^2 + 5d^2 = 1$, which implies $c + d\sqrt{-5}$ is unit, i.e., $c + d\sqrt{-5} = 1$ or $c + d\sqrt{-5} = -1$. Thus $3 = (a + b\sqrt{-5}) \cdot 1$ or $3 = (a + b\sqrt{-5}) \cdot (-1)$. Hence 3 is irreducible element in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$.

THEOREM 5.1.8.

Every prime element in an integral domain in R is an irreducible element.

Proof:

Let a be prime element in an integral domain in R , then $a \neq 0$ and a is not unit. To prove a is irreducible, suppose $a = bc$, we must prove b or c unit but not both its.

Since $a = bc$, $a/bc \Rightarrow a/b$ or a/c .

If a/b , then $b = at$, for some $t \in R$, thus $bc = act$, but $a = bc$, so that $a = act$, implies that $1 = ct$. thus c is unit and a is an irreducible element.

EXAMPLES 5.1.9.

If $a^2 + 5b^2$ is a prime element in Z . Show that $a+b\sqrt{-5}$ is an irreducible element in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$, but not conversely.

Solution:

Suppose $a+b\sqrt{-5} = (c+d\sqrt{-5})(e+f\sqrt{-5})$, then

$N(a+b\sqrt{-5})=N(c+d\sqrt{-5}).N(e+f\sqrt{-5})$ implies that $a^2+5b^2 = (c^2+5d^2)(e^2+5f^2)$.

But a^2+5b^2 is a prime element in Z , so that a^2+5b^2 is an irreducible element, thus either c^2+5d^2 is unit or e^2+5f^2 is unit, implies that $c = \pm 1, d=0$ or $e = \pm 1, f=0$.

If $c = \pm 1, d=0$, then $c+d\sqrt{-5} = \pm 1$ which is unit in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$.

If $e = \pm 1, f=0$, then $e+f\sqrt{-5} = \pm 1$ which is unit in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$.

Hence $a+b\sqrt{-5}$ is an irreducible element in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$.

Now, note that $3 = 3+0\sqrt{-5}$ is an irreducible element in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$, but $3^2+5(0)^2=9$ is not prime element in Z .

ECSERSISES 5.1.10.

- 1- Find the irreducible elements and prime elements in Z_{12}, Q .
- 2- If a/b and b/a in ring R , prove or disprove a, b are associates.
- 3- Let $c \in R \subseteq R[x]$, R is an integral domain. Prove that c is a unit (respective prime, irreducible) in $R[x]$ if and only if c is a unit(respective prime , irreducible) in R .
- 4- In the ring $Z[i]$. Show that 26 is not irreducible element in $Z[i]$. Also show that 26 is not a prime element in $Z[i]$.
- 5- In the ring $(Z[\sqrt{-5}], +, \cdot)$, show that $\sqrt{-5}$ is a prime element in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$.
- 6- In the ring $(Z[\sqrt{-5}], +, \cdot)$, show that $2+\sqrt{-5}$ is an irreducible element, but not prime element in $Z[\sqrt{-5}]$.

THEOREM 5.1.11.

Let R be a principle ideal domain. If p is an irreducible element, then p is a prime element in R and conversely.

Proof:

Since p is an irreducible element in R , $p \neq 0$, p is not invertible element, assume p/ab , then $ab=pc$, for some $c \in R$. Since R is a principle ideal domain, $\langle p, a \rangle$ is a principle

ideal say $\langle d \rangle$; that is $\langle p, a \rangle = \langle d \rangle$. Hence $p = rd$, for some $r \in R$, but p is an irreducible, so either r is an invertible element or d is an invertible element. If d is invertible element (unit), then $\langle d \rangle = R$, thus $\langle p, a \rangle = R$ and so $1 = r_1 p + r_2 a$, for some $r_1, r_2 \in R$. So that $b = r_1 p b + r_2 a b = r_1 p b + r_2 p c = p(r_1 b + r_2 c)$. implies that p/b . If r is invertible element (unit), then $d = r^{-1} p \in \langle p \rangle$, so $\langle d \rangle \subseteq \langle p \rangle$, but $\langle d \rangle = \langle p, a \rangle$. Hence $a = td$, for some $t \in R$, but $d \in \langle p \rangle$, thus $a \in \langle p \rangle$, that is p/a . Hence either p/a or p/b . Therefore, p is a prime element in R .

EXAMPLES 5.1.12.

The ring $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}], +, \cdot)$ is not principle ideal domain, since $2 + \sqrt{-5}$ is an irreducible, but not prime element in $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$.

DEFINITION 5.1.13.

Let I be a principle ideal of a ring R . I is called maximal principle ideal, if there is no principle ideal J such that $I \subset J \subset R$.

EXAMPLES 5.1.14.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}[x], +, \cdot)$, $\langle x \rangle$ is maximal principle ideal, but not maximal ideal.

THEOREM 5.1.15.

Let R be an integral domain and $p \in R, p \neq 0$. Then

- 1- p is a prime element of R if and only if $\langle p \rangle$ is a prime ideal of R .
- 2- p is an irreducible element of R if and only if $\langle p \rangle$ is a maximal ideal of R .

Proof:

1) (\Rightarrow) Let $ab \in \langle p \rangle, a, b \in R$. Since p is a prime element, $\langle p \rangle \neq R$, which p is not invertible element. Hence p/ab . It follows that p/a or p/b , then $a \in \langle p \rangle$ or $b \in \langle p \rangle$.

(\Leftarrow) Let $\langle p \rangle$ is a prime element of R , then $\langle p \rangle \neq R$ and so p is not invertible element. Suppose p/ab , then $ab \in \langle p \rangle$ and so that p/ab , then $a \in \langle p \rangle$ or $b \in \langle p \rangle$. Hence p/a or p/b , then p is a prime element of R .

2) (\Rightarrow) If p is an irreducible element of R , then p is not invertible element of R , hence $\langle p \rangle \neq R$, assume $\exists a \in R$ such that $\langle p \rangle \subset \langle a \rangle \subseteq R$, this implies, $p = ra$, for some $r \in R$, but p is an irreducible element, so either r is invertible element or a is invertible element.

If r is invertible element, then $a = r^{-1} p \in \langle p \rangle$, so that $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle p \rangle$, which is a contradicts.

Hence a is an invertible element and so $\langle a \rangle = R$. Therefore $\langle p \rangle$ is a maximal ideal of R .

(\Leftarrow) If $\langle p \rangle$ is a maximal principle element of R , suppose $p = ab$, to prove a is unit or b is unit. Assume a is not unit, then $\langle p \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle \subset R$, but $\langle p \rangle$ is maximal principle element, so that $\langle p \rangle = \langle a \rangle$, thus $a = rp$, for some $r \in R$, so that $a = rab$, then $1 = rb$, thus b is unit.

COROLLARY 5.1.16.

Let R be a principle integral domain. Then

A nontrivial ideal $\langle p \rangle$ is maximal (prime) if and only if, p is an irreducible (prime) element of R .

COROLLARY 5.1.17.

Let R be a principle integral domain, let a be a nonzero element such that a is not unit. Then there exists p is a prime element such that p/a .

Proof:

Since a is not unit, $\langle a \rangle \neq R$, so that there exists a maximal ideal $\langle p \rangle$ such that $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle p \rangle$. This implies $a \in \langle p \rangle$ and $a = rp$, for some $r \in R$. Thus p/a element such that p/a .

THEOREM 5.1.18.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity 1, let P be a prime ideal of R , then $S = R - P$ is a multi subset of R and $S^{-1}R$ is a local ring with unique maximal ideal, where $S^{-1}P = \{a/s : a \in P, S \in R - P, \text{ (i.e., } S \notin P)\}$.

Note that $S^{-1}R$ is denoted by R_P (called the localization of R by $S = R - P$) and $S^{-1}P$ is denoted by P_S

Proof:

Let $x, y \in S$ such that $x \notin P, y \notin P$, since P is a prime ideal, $xy \notin P$. Thus $xy \in S$.

To proof P_S is an ideal of R_P ?

Let $\bar{x}, \bar{y} \in P_S$, then $\bar{x} = x/s, x \in P, s \notin P$ and $\bar{y} = y/t, y \in P, t \notin P$.

$\bar{x} - \bar{y} = x/s - y/t = (xt - ys)/st$, but $st \notin P$ (i.e., $st \in S$) and $(xt - ys) \in P$. Thus $(\bar{x} - \bar{y}) \in P_S$.

Now, let $a/u \in R_P$, then $a \in R, u \notin P$. $\bar{x} \cdot a/u = (x/s) \cdot (a/u) = xa/su$. But $x \in P \Rightarrow xa \in P, s \notin P, u \notin P \Rightarrow su \notin P$. Hence $xa/su \in P_S$. Thus P_S is an ideal of R_P .

To proof P_S is a maximal ideal in R_P , let $\bar{r} \notin P_S$, then $\bar{r} = r/s, r \notin P, s \notin P$, so that $s/r \in R_P$ and $(r/s) \cdot (s/r) = rs/sr = \text{unity of } R_P$. Hence $\bar{r} = r/s$ is an invertible element, thus every element not in P_S is invertible. Then P_S is the unique maximum ideal of R_P .

5.2. Valuation Rings

DEFINITION 5.2.1.

A valuation ring (domain) V is a ring (domain) with the property that $\forall A, B$ ideals of V , either $A \subseteq B$ or $B \subseteq A$.

EXAMPLES 5.2.2.

- (1) $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is not valuation ring.
- (2) Every field is valuation ring.
- (3) Consider the field of rational $(\mathbb{Q}, +, \cdot)$. Let $D_p = \{a/b \in \mathbb{Q} : \text{g.c.d.}(p, b) = 1\}$, where p is a prime number. D_p is a valuation domain.

THEOREM 5.2.3.

For an integral domain V , the following statements are equivalent

- (1) V is a valuation ring.
- (2) $\forall a, b \in V$, either $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle b \rangle$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$.
- (3) $\forall x \in K$ (K is the total quotient field of V), then either $x \in V$ or $x^{-1} \in V$.

Proof:

(1) \Rightarrow (2) it is clear

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Let $x \in K$, then $x = a/b$ where $a, b \in V$ and $b \neq 0$. Hence either $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle b \rangle$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$.

If $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle b \rangle$, then $a = rb$, for some $r \in V$, thus $x = a/b = rb/b = r/1 \in V$.

If $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$, then $b = ra$, for some $r \in V$, thus $x = a/ra$ and hence $x^{-1} = ra/a = r/1 \in V$.

Hence either $x \in V$ or $x^{-1} \in V$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Let A, B be ideals of V . Suppose $A \not\subseteq B$, hence $\exists a \in A, a \notin B$, thus for any $b \in B, b \neq 0$.

Either $a/b \in V$ or $b/a \in V$, if $a/b \in V$, then $a = rb$, for some $r \in R$, so $a \in B$ which is contradicts. Thus $b/a \in V$, that is $b = ra \in A$. then $B \subseteq A$.

COROLLARY 5.2.4.

In V is an integral domain, every finitely generated ideal of V is principal ideal.

Proof :

The proof by induction, let I be an ideal of R , $I = \langle a_1, a_2 \rangle = \langle a_1 \rangle + \langle a_2 \rangle$, since R is a valuation ring, so either $\langle a_1 \rangle \subseteq \langle a_2 \rangle$ or $\langle a_2 \rangle \subseteq \langle a_1 \rangle$. Hence either $\langle a_1, a_2 \rangle = \langle a_2 \rangle$ or $\langle a_1, a_2 \rangle = \langle a_1 \rangle$. Thus I is principal ideal. Suppose every ideal generated by k -elements is principal ideal.

Let $I = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k, a_{k+1} \rangle \therefore I = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle + \langle a_{k+1} \rangle$, but $\langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle$ is principal ideal say $\langle c \rangle$. Hence $I = \langle c \rangle + \langle a_{k+1} \rangle = \langle d \rangle$ where $d = c$ or $d = a_{k+1}$. Hence I is a principal ideal.

REMARK 5.2.5.

$(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is a principal ideal domain, but not valuation domain .

PROPOSITION 5.2.6.

If R is a local domain and every finitely generated ideal is a principle ideal. Then R is a valuation domain

Proof :

Let $a, b \in R$, to prove $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle b \rangle$ or $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$.

If a is a unit $\Rightarrow \langle a \rangle = R$, so $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$.

If b is a unit $\Rightarrow \langle b \rangle = R$, so $\langle b \rangle \supseteq \langle a \rangle$.

If a and b are non units, then $\langle a \rangle \neq R$, $\langle b \rangle \neq R$. Let M be the unique maximal ideal of R (since R is local), so M is a set of all non units of R .

Now, $\langle a, b \rangle \subseteq M$, thus $\exists c$ (non units of R) such that $\langle a, b \rangle = \langle c \rangle$, since $\langle a, b \rangle$ finitely generated, then $c = r_1 a + r_2 b$. But $a \in \langle c \rangle \Rightarrow a = \alpha_1 c$ and $b \in \langle c \rangle \Rightarrow b = \alpha_2 c$. Implies that $c = r_1 \alpha_1 c + r_2 \alpha_2 c \Rightarrow c = (r_1 \alpha_1 + r_2 \alpha_2) c \Rightarrow 1 = r_1 \alpha_1 + r_2 \alpha_2$, since R is domain \Rightarrow at least one of terms $r_1 \alpha_1$ or $r_2 \alpha_2$ is unit, because if $r_1 \alpha_1$ and $r_2 \alpha_2$ non units, then $1 = r_1 \alpha_1 + r_2 \alpha_2$ non units which is contradicts.

If $r_1 \alpha_1$ unit, then α_1 is unit, so $c = \alpha_1^{-1} a \in \langle a \rangle$. Thus $\langle c \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$.

But $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle c \rangle$, hence $\langle a \rangle = \langle c \rangle$.

On the other hand, $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle c \rangle$, so $\langle b \rangle \subseteq \langle a \rangle$ hence $\langle a \rangle = \langle b \rangle$.

If $r_2 \alpha_2$ unit, then by similar proof $\langle a \rangle \subseteq \langle b \rangle$. Thus R is a valuation domain.

THEOREM 5.2.7.

If V is a valuation domain, then V is a local ring. i.e., set of non units form an ideal which is the unique maximal ideal of V .

Proof :

Let P be a set of non units of V , let $a, b \in P$ and $c \in V, b \neq 0$. Since a is non units, then ac is non unit, thus $ac \in P$.

Now, $a/b \in K$ (total quotient field of V), so $a/b \in V$ or $b/a \in V$.

If $a/b \in V$, then $a=rb$, for some $r \in R$, thus $a-b=rb-b=(r-1)b$, then $a-b$ is not unit, because if $a-b$ is unit, $\exists c \in R$ such that $(r-1)bc=1$ and so b is unit which is contradicts. Thus $a-b \notin P$.

Similarly, if $b/a \in V$, then $b=ra$, so $a-b=a-ra=a(1-r)$ is non unit. Thus P is an ideal of V .

P is a maximal ideal and V is local ring, if A is a proper ideal of V , so $\forall a \in A$, a is non unit. Hence $A \subseteq P$. Thus P is the unique maximal ideal of V .

DEFINITION 5.2.8.

Let R be an integral domain. R is called a Bezout domain, if every finitely generated ideal is principle ideal.

EXERCISE 5.2.9.

- (1) $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is a Bezout domain.
- (2) Every field is a Bezout domain.

REMARK 5.2.10.

R is a valuation Domain $\Rightarrow R$ is a Bezout domain. But the convers is not true.

Proof :

By theorem every finitely generated of valuation domain R is principle ideal, so R is a Bezout domain, by definition (5.2.8).

EXERCISE 5.2.11.

$(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is a Bezout domain, but not valuation domain.

EUCLIDEAN RINGS AND PRINCIPLE IDEAL DOMAINS

5.3. Euclidean rings and principle ideal domains

DEFINITION 5.3.1.

Let R be an integral domain. R is called Euclidean domain (ED), if \exists a mapping δ called norm or valuation from $R \setminus \{0\}$ to $Z_+ \cup \{0\}$ such that

- 1- For all nonzero $a, b \in R$, $\delta(a) \leq \delta(ab)$.
- 2- If $a, b \in R$, $b \neq 0$, then $\exists m, r \in R$ such that $a = mb + r$, where either $r=0$ or $r \neq 0$ and $\delta(r) \leq \delta(b)$.

EXAMPLES 5.3.2.

- 1) $(Z, +, \cdot)$ is an Euclidean domain (ED), if we set $\delta(z) = |z|$, $\forall z \in Z, z \neq 0$.
Let $\delta: Z \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow Z_+ \cup \{0\}$ such that $\delta(x) = |x| \Rightarrow |a| = |ab| \Rightarrow |a| \leq |ab| \Rightarrow \delta(a) \leq \delta(ab)$.
- 2) $(Q[x], +, \cdot)$ is an Euclidean domain (ED), if we set $\delta(f) = \deg f$, $\forall f \in Q[x], f \neq 0$.
Let $\delta: Z \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow Z_+ \cup \{0\}$ such that $\delta(f) = \deg f$, $\delta(fg) = \deg fg \Rightarrow \delta(f) = \delta(fg) \Rightarrow \forall f, g \in Q[x], f \neq 0, g \neq 0$.
- 3) Every field is an Euclidean domain (ED), if we set $\delta(a) = 1$, $\forall a \in F, a \neq 0$.
Let $\delta: Z \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow Z_+ \cup \{0\}$, if $\forall a, b \in F, a \neq 0, b \neq 0$. $\delta(a) = 1$ and $\delta(ab) = 1 \Rightarrow \delta(a) \leq \delta(ab)$.
If $\forall a, b \in F, a \neq 0, a = a b^{-1} b + 0$.

REMARK 5.3.3.

A domain may be Euclidean domain (ED) with respect to more, than one norm.

THEOREM 5.3.4.

A domains $Z[\sqrt{-1}]$, $Z[\sqrt{-2}]$, and $Z[\sqrt{p}] = \{u + vp \mid u, v \in Z\}$, where $p = (-1 + \sqrt{-3})/2$ are all Euclidean domain (ED).

THEOREM 5.3.6.

Let R be an Euclidean domain (ED) with respect to δ . Any two element a, b not both zeros have g.c.d. c , say, expressible in the form $c = sa + tb$, for some $s, t \in R$. Further, if d is also g.c.d. of a and b , then c, d are associates.

Proof:

Let $\delta = \{ ma + nb : m, n \in R \}$, then $a = 1.a + 0.b \in \delta$, $b = 0.a + 1.b \in \delta$; thus $\delta \neq 0$. From all nonzero element of δ . Choose $c = m_0a + n_0b$ with $\delta(c)$ as small as possible. Now, suppose $w = ua + vb \in \delta$, by definition(6.1.1), $w = kc + r$, for some $k, r \in R$, where either $r=0$ or $\delta(r) < \delta(c)$. Now, $r = w - kc = ua + vb - k(m_0a + n_0b) \Rightarrow r = (u - km_0)a + (v - kn_0)b \in \delta$. Thus $\delta(r)$ cannot be less than $\delta(c)$, so that $r=0$. Hence $w = kc$ and this implies c/w . i.e., c divide every element in S . Thus c/a and c/b .

Next, if $c_1 \in R$ and c_1/a and c_1/b , then $c_1/m_0a + n_0b = c$, this shows c is a g.c.d. of a and b .

Finally, if c and d are g.c.d. of a and b , then c/d and d/c , hence $c = cx$, $c = yd$, for some $x, y \in R$. Hence $d = yxd$ and so $1 = xy$. It follows that x, y are units. Therefore c, d are associate.

THEOREM 5.3.7.

Let R be an Euclidean domain (ED) with respect to δ . If $\pi \in R$ is an irreducible, then π is a prime.

Proof:

Suppose $b, c \in R$ and π/bc and $\pi \nmid b$, we must prove π/c .

Since π is an irreducible, then its divisors are of the form $u, u\pi$, where u is unit. Since $\pi \nmid b$, so the only common divisors to π, b are the unit, one of which 1_R .

Thus g.c.d. $(\pi, b) = 1$, so $\exists s, t \in R$ such that $1 = s\pi + tb$, then

$c = s\pi c + tbc = s\pi c + t\pi k$, ($\pi/bc \Rightarrow bc = \pi k$) $= (sc + tk)\pi$. Thus π/c .

THEOREM 5.3.8.

Let a, b be nonzero elements in R , b being is a non unit, then $\delta(a) < \delta(ab)$.

Proof:

By definition(6.3.1), $\delta(a) \leq \delta(ab)$. Suppose $\delta(a) = \delta(ab)$, then $\exists m, r \in R$ such that $a = m(ab) + r$, where $r=0$ or $\delta(r) < \delta(ab)$.

If $r \neq 0$, then $\delta(r) < \delta(a)$, but $r = a(1 - mb)$, so that $\delta(r) \geq \delta(a)$. (so $\delta(r) \geq \delta(ab)$), which is contradicts. Hence r must be zero and so $a = mab$.

THEOREM 5.3.9.

Any Euclidean domain (ED) is a principle integral domain.

Proof:

Let I be an ideal of a Euclidean domain R , if $I = \{0\}$, then it is clear that I is a principle ideal

If $I \neq \{0\}$, let $0 \neq d \in I$ be an element of I with the least value $\delta(d)$ among all nonzero elements in I .

We claim that $I = \langle d \rangle$, for any $c \in I$, $c = gd + r$, where $r = 0$ or $\delta(r) < \delta(d)$.

If $r \neq 0$, then $r = c - gd \in I$ and $\delta(r) < \delta(d)$ which contradicts the choice of d . Thus $r = 0$ and $c = gd \in \langle d \rangle$. Therefore $I = \langle d \rangle$ and R is a principle integral domain.

CHAPTER SIX

MODULES AND SUBMODULES

6.1. MODULES

DEFINITION 6.1.1.

Let R be a Commutative ring with unity 1. A nonempty set M with two binary operation addition (+) defined on m and scalar multiplication (\cdot). $(M, +, \cdot)$ is called a **left R -module over R** if and only if, the following are true :-

- 1- $(M, +)$ is an abelian group .
- 2- (\cdot) is a mapping from $R \times M$ into M such that $\forall r \in R$ and $r \cdot m \in M$ satisfying
 - i- $r \cdot (m_1 + m_2) = r \cdot m_1 + r \cdot m_2 \quad \forall r \in R, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$.
 - ii- $(r_1 + r_2) \cdot m = r_1 \cdot m + r_2 \cdot m \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M$.
 - iii- $(r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot m = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot m) \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M$.
 - iv- If (M, \cdot) has unity 1, then $1 \cdot x = x$.Then M is called a until left R -module.

REMARK 6.1.2.

1- Similarly , we can define right R -module over R if $m \cdot (r_1 \cdot r_2) = (m \cdot r_1) \cdot r_2$

- 1- $(M, +)$ is an abelian group .
- 2- (\cdot) is a mapping from $R \times M$ into M such that $\forall r \in R$ and $r \cdot m \in M$ satisfying
 - i- $(m_1 + m_2) \cdot r = m_1 \cdot r + m_2 \cdot r, \quad \forall r \in R, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$.
 - ii- $m \cdot (r_1 + r_2) = m \cdot r_1 + m \cdot r_2, \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M$.
 - iii- $m \cdot (r_1 \cdot r_2) = (m \cdot r_1) \cdot r_2, \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M$.
 - iv- If (M, \cdot) has unity 1, then $x \cdot 1 = x$.Then M is called a until right R -module.

DEFINITION 6.1.3.

That is an abelian group. $(M, +)$ is called a left R -module $\Leftrightarrow \exists$ a mapping $X: R \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r, m) \mapsto r.m, \forall r \in R, \forall m \in M$ satisfying :- $\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$

i- $(r, m_1 + m_2) = (r, m_1) + (r, m_2)$

ii- $(r_1 + r_2, m) = (r_1, m) + (r_2, m)$

iii- $(r_1.r_2, m) = (r_1, (r_2.m))$

iv- $(1, m) = m$

REMARK 6.1.4.

1. Every properties which hold for left modules are also hold for right modules.
2. Every left R -modules can be consider a right R -module if the ring is commutative.
3. If R is commutative ring then a left R -module ora right R -module is **ring R -module** and conversely is true.

EXAMPLES 6.1.5.

1. Every abelian group $(M, +)$ is a module over the ring Z (the ring of all integers) .

2- (every abelian group is a Z -module) Define $\alpha : Z \times M \rightarrow M$ such that

$\alpha(n, m) = m + m + \dots + m$ **n -time** $= n.m \in M$.

Proof :- $\alpha(n_1 m) = nm \quad \forall m \in M, \forall n \in Z, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$

i- $(n, m_1 + m_2) = r_1(m_1 + m_2)$

$= (m_1 + m_2) + (m_1 + m_2) + \dots + (m_1 + m_2)$ by define of α

$= m_1 + m_1 + m_1 + \dots + m_1 + m_2 + m_2 + \dots + m_2 = n m_1 + n m_2$

$= (n_1 m_1) + (n_1 m_2)$

ii- $(r_1 + r_2, m) = (r_1 + r_2)m$

$= m + m + \dots + m$

$= m + m + \dots + m + m + m + \dots + m = n_1 m + n_2 m = (n_1, m) + (n_2, m)$

iii- $(n_1 n_2, m) = (n_1 n_2) m$ by define of α

$= m + m + \dots + m = (m + m + \dots + m)$

$= (m + \dots + m) + \dots + (m + \dots + m)$

$= n_1 (m + m + \dots + m)$

$= n_1 (n_2 m) = (n_1, n_2 m) = (n_1, (n_2, m))$.

iv- $\forall m \in M, (1, m) = 1.m = m \therefore M$ is until Z -module.

3- (R an abelian group is a Z -module)

Since $(R, +)$ is an abelian group and define $\alpha : R \times R \rightarrow R \ni (a, b) = a.b \in R,$

$\forall a, b \in R$

i : $(a, b_1 + b_2) = a.(b_1 + b_2) = a.b_1 + a.b_2 = (a, b_1) + (a, b_2)$

- ii: $(a_1 + a_2, b) = (a_1 + a_2) \cdot b = a_1 \cdot b + a_2 \cdot b = (a_1, b) + (a_2, b)$
 iii: $(a_1, a_2, b) = (a_1 + a_2) \cdot b = a_1 \cdot (a_2 \cdot b) = (a_1, a_2 \cdot b) = (a_1, (a_2, b))$.
 iv: $(a \cdot 1, b \cdot 1) = (a, b) \cdot 1 = ((a, b), 1)$
 $\therefore R$ is a unital R -module.
 3- $(Q, +)$ is an abelian group $\Rightarrow Q$ is a Z -module.

EXAMPLES 6.1.6.

1- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring let $(R, +) = (M, +) \therefore R$ is a unital R -module.

2- Let $M_2(Z) = M$, $(M, +, \cdot)$ is a unital Z -module of matrix.

Solution:-

Let $r_1, r_2 \in Z$, $A, B \in M_2(Z)$

$$1- (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot A = (r_1 \cdot r_2) \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot a & (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot b \\ (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot c & (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot d \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= r_1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \cdot a & r_2 \cdot b \\ r_2 \cdot c & r_2 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot A).$$

$$2- (r_1 + r_2) \cdot A = (r_1 + r_2) \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (r_1 + r_2) \cdot a & (r_1 + r_2) \cdot b \\ (r_1 + r_2) \cdot c & (r_1 + r_2) \cdot d \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \cdot a & r_2 \cdot b \\ r_2 \cdot c & r_2 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \cdot a & r_2 \cdot b \\ r_2 \cdot c & r_2 \cdot d \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= r_1 \cdot A + r_2 \cdot A$$

$$3- r_1 \cdot (A + B) = r_1 \cdot \left(\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot (a + e) & r_1 \cdot (b + f) \\ r_1 \cdot (c + g) & r_1 \cdot (d + h) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot e & r_1 \cdot f \\ r_1 \cdot g & r_1 \cdot h \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot e & r_1 \cdot f \\ r_1 \cdot g & r_1 \cdot h \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= r_1 \cdot A + r_1 \cdot B$$

4- If has unity 1, then $1 \cdot A = A$

$$1 \cdot A = 1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = A$$

3- Is $(Z[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ a unital Z -module?

Solution:-

$r_1, r_2 \in Z$, $x = a + b\sqrt{2}$, $y = c + d\sqrt{2} \in Z[\sqrt{2}]$

$$1- (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot x = (r_1 \cdot r_2) (a + b\sqrt{2}) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) a + (r_1 \cdot r_2) b\sqrt{2}$$

$$= r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot a) + r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2} = r_1 \cdot ((r_2 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2})$$

$$= r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot x).$$

$$2- (r_1 + r_2) \cdot x = (r_1 + r_2) (a + b\sqrt{2}) = (r_1 + r_2) a + (r_1 + r_2) b\sqrt{2}$$

$$= ((r_1 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot a)) + ((r_1 \cdot b) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) = ((r_1 \cdot a) + (r_1 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) + ((r_2 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2})$$

$$= (r_1 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) + (r_2 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) = r_1 \cdot x + r_2 \cdot x.$$

$$3- r_1 \cdot (x + y) = r_1 \cdot ((a + b\sqrt{2}) + (c + d\sqrt{2})) \\ = r_1 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2}) + r_1 \cdot (c + d\sqrt{2}) = r_1 \cdot x + r_1 \cdot y.$$

4- If has unity 1, then $1 \cdot x = x$ and $x \cdot 1 = x$,

$$1 \cdot x = 1 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2}) = (1 \cdot a + 1 \cdot b\sqrt{2}) = (a + b\sqrt{2}) = x, \text{ and}$$

$$x \cdot 1 = (a + b\sqrt{2}) \cdot 1 = (a \cdot 1 + b \cdot 1\sqrt{2}) = (a + b\sqrt{2}) = x.$$

$(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ is a unital \mathbb{Z} -module.

4- Is $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ a unital $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}]$ -module ?

THEOREM 6.1.7. Let M be a R -module, then: 0_R is identity element of R , 0_M is identity element of M .

1-

$$0_R \cdot m = 0_M, \forall m \in M.$$

$$2- r \cdot 0_M = 0_M \text{ and } 0_M \cdot r = 0_M, \forall m \in M, \forall r \in R.$$

$$3- r \cdot (-m) = -(r \cdot m) = (-r) \cdot m, \forall m \in M, \forall r \in R.$$

$$4- x, y \in M; x - y = x + (-y), \text{ then } r(x - y) = rx - ry, \forall r \in R.$$

$$5- (-r) \cdot (-x) = r \cdot x \quad \forall x \in M, r \in R.$$

Proof:-

$$1- 0_R + 0_R = 0_R \text{ and } m \in M \Rightarrow (0_R + 0_R) \cdot m = 0_R \cdot m \Rightarrow 0_R \cdot m + 0_R \cdot m = 0_R \cdot m \Rightarrow 0_R \cdot m + 0_M \Rightarrow 0_R \cdot m = 0_M.$$

$$2- m + r \cdot 0_M = m \Rightarrow r \cdot (m + 0_M) = r \cdot m \Rightarrow r \cdot m + r \cdot 0_M = r \cdot m \Rightarrow r \cdot m + r \cdot 0_M = r \cdot m + 0_M \Rightarrow r \cdot 0_M = 0_M.$$

$$3- r \cdot m + (-r) \cdot m = (r + (-r)) \cdot m = 0_R \cdot m = 0_M \therefore r \cdot m + (-r) \cdot m = 0_M \Rightarrow$$

$$-r \cdot m = (-r) \cdot m \text{ and } r \cdot m + r \cdot (-m) = r \cdot (m + (-m)) = r \cdot 0_M = 0_M \therefore r \cdot m + r \cdot (-m) = 0_M \Rightarrow$$

$$-r \cdot m = r \cdot (-m) \Rightarrow r \cdot m + (-r) \cdot m = 0_M = r \cdot m + r \cdot (-m) \Rightarrow (-r) \cdot m = r \cdot (-m)$$

$$\therefore r \cdot (-m) = -(r \cdot m) = (-r) \cdot m$$

6.2. SUBMODULES

DEFINITION 6.2.1.

Let $(M, +, \cdot)$ be a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$, then $(S, +, \cdot)$ is called a **R -submodule of M** $\Leftrightarrow (S, +, \cdot)$ is a R -module.

THEOREM 6.2.2.

Let M a R -module, let $\emptyset \neq S \subseteq M$, then $(S, +, \cdot)$, then $(S, +, \cdot)$ is R -submodule of $M \Leftrightarrow$ (1) $a - b$ and (2) $r \cdot a \in S \quad \forall a, b \in S, r \in R$.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) S is R -submodules

1- $a \in S, b \in S \Rightarrow a \in S \wedge -b \in S \Rightarrow a + (-b) \in S$

2- $r \cdot a \in S$ form the definition

(\Leftarrow) $0 \cdot 0 = 0 \therefore S \neq \emptyset$ & $S \subseteq M$

$a + b = b + a \quad \wedge \quad a + (b + c) = (a + b) + c$

$\therefore (S, +)$ is commutative group

1- $(r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot x = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot x), \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, x \in S$.

2- $(r_1 + r_2) \cdot x = r_1 \cdot x + r_2 \cdot x$.

3- $r_1 \cdot (x + y) = r_1 \cdot x + r_1 \cdot y$.

4- If 1 is an unity, then $1 \cdot x = x, \forall x \in S$.

$\therefore S$ is a R -module $\Rightarrow S$ is a R -submodules.

REMARK 6.2.3.

1- If M is a R -module, $M \neq \{0_M\}$, then $M, \{0_M\}$ are R -submodules.

2- Let R be a commutative ring, let I be an ideal of R , then I is a R -submodule of R -module of R .

EXAMPLES 6.2.4.

Consider the Z -module $M_2(R) = M$. Let $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix} : a, b \in R \right\}$. Prove that S is a Z -submodule.

Solution:- $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S. \therefore S \neq \emptyset$ & $S \subseteq M_2(R)$.

Let $\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & b_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} a_2 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 \end{pmatrix} \in S$.

$$1- \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & b_1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} a_2 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 - a_2 & 0 \\ 0 & b_1 - b_2 \end{pmatrix} \in S.$$

$$2- r \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & b_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cdot a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & r \cdot b_1 \end{pmatrix} \in S, \forall r \in R.$$

$\therefore S$ is a Z -submodule.

PROPOSITION 6.2.5.

- 1) For any R -module M , there is at least two submodules since $\{0\}$ is a submodule of M and M is a submodule of M .
- 2) $\{0\}$ is called the trivial submodules of M .
- 3) If there is any other submodule N of M such that $N \neq M$, then N is called a proper submodules of M .
- 4) For each positive integer n , $n \cdot Z$ is a submodules of Z as a Z -modules.
- 5) If R is a ring, consider R as a R -module, the submodules of R are just the ideals of R .

DEFINITION 6.2.6.

A non-zero R -module M is called **simple** if M has no proper submodule.

EXAMPLES 6.2.7.

- 1- For each prime number p , Z_p is a simple Z -module. As Z_3 is a simple Z -module
- 2- For each not prime number p , Z_p is a not simple Z -module. As Z_4 is not simple Z -module.

PROPOSITION 5.2.8.

The intersection of two submodules of a R -module M is also a submodule of M .

Proof:-

Let N, K are two submodules of a R -module $N \subseteq M \Rightarrow N \cap K \subseteq M$, $N \cap K \neq \emptyset$, since $N \neq \emptyset$, $K \neq \emptyset$.

1- $\forall a, b \in N \cap K \Rightarrow a, b \in N$ and $a, b \in K$, by define of \cap .

$\Rightarrow a - b \in N$ and $a - b \in K$, since N, K are submodules $\Rightarrow a - b \in N \cap K$.

2- $\forall r \in R, a \in N \cap K \Rightarrow a \in N$ & $a \in K$, by define \cap

$\forall r \in R \Rightarrow r \cdot a \in N$ & $r \cdot a \in K$, since N, K are submodules $\Rightarrow r \cdot a \in N \cap K$.

$\therefore N \cap K$ is a submodule of M .

PROPOSITION 6.2.9.

The intersection of any collection of submodules of a R -module M is also a submodule of M .

Proof :-

- 1- Let $a, b \in \bigcap S_i \Rightarrow a, b \in S_i \forall i \Rightarrow a - b \in S_i \forall i \Rightarrow a - b \in \bigcap S_i$.
- 2- $r \in R, a \in \bigcap S_i \Rightarrow r \cdot a \in S_i \forall i \Rightarrow r \cdot a \in \bigcap S_i$.
- $\therefore \bigcap S_i$ is a R-submodule of R.

REMARK 6.2.10.

The union of two submodules of a R-module M is not necessary a submodule of M.

EXAMPLE 6.2.11.

- 1- $R = \mathbb{Z}_6, I = \{0, 3\}, J = \{0, 2, 4\}, 3 - 2 = 1 \notin I \cup J$.

$\therefore I \cup J$ is not R-submodule.

- 2- Let $M = \mathbb{Z}_{12}$ is a Z-module and let $N = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}, \bar{6}, \bar{8}, \bar{10}\}$ and $K = \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}, \bar{6}, \bar{9}\}$. Then N and K are submodules of M.

\oplus	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$
$\bar{0}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$
$\bar{2}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$
$\bar{4}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$
$\bar{6}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$
$\bar{8}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$
$\bar{10}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$

$a + b \in N, \forall a, b \in N$ and $r \cdot a \in N, \forall a \in N$ and $r \in R$.

$N \cup K = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{3}, \bar{4}, \bar{6}, \bar{8}, \bar{9}, \bar{10}\}, \bar{2}, \bar{3} \in N \cup K, \text{ but } \bar{2} \oplus_{12} \bar{3} = \bar{5} \notin N \cup K$.

REMARK 6.2.12.

If N and K are submodules of M, then $N \cup K$ is a submodules of M $\Leftrightarrow N \subseteq K$ or $K \subseteq N$.

6.3. HOMOMORPHISM OF MODULES

DEFINITION 6.3.1.

Let M, M' be two left R -modules, then mapping $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ is called

Left R -module homomorphism (R -homomorphism) if for all $x, y \in M, r \in R$, then

1- $f(x + y) = f(x) +' f(y), \forall x, y \in M,$

2- $f(r \cdot y) = r \cdot' f(y), \forall r \in R, \forall y \in M.$

i.e., f preserves addition and scalar multiplication between the two modules.

EXAMPLES 6.3.2.

Let M, M' be any two R -modules and $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a mapping. f is called **constant mapping zero**. i.e., $f(m) = {}_{M'}0, \forall m \in M$, then f is a R -homomorphism.

Note that:- This homomorphism is called the trivial homomorphism.

Proof:- $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \forall r \in R,$

1- $f(m_1 + m_2) = {}_{M'}0 = {}_{M'}0 + {}_{M'}0 = f(m_1) +' f(m_2),$

2- $f(r \cdot m_1) = r \cdot {}_{M'}0 = r \cdot' f(m_1).$

EXAMPLES 6.3.3.

Let M be any R -module, the identity map ${}_M I$ on M is a R -homomorphism on M .

${}_M I$ is called **the identity homomorphism on M** , ${}_M I: M \rightarrow M$ such that ${}_M I(m) = m, \forall m \in M.$

Proof:-

Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R,$

${}_M I(m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 = {}_M I(m_1) + {}_M I(m_2),$

${}_M I(r \cdot m) = r \cdot m = r \cdot {}_M I(m) \Rightarrow {}_M I$ is a R -homomorphism

EXAMPLES 6.3.4.

If M is any R -module and N is a submodule of M the inclusion map $I_N: N \rightarrow M$ such that $I_N(m) = m, \forall m \in N.$ I_N is a R -homomorphism. This homomorphism is called **the inclusion homomorphism**.

Proof:- Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R,$

$I_N(m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 = I_N(m_1) + I_N(m_2),$ and $I_N(r.m) = r.m = r.I_N(m).$

I_N is a R -homomorphism .

EXAMPLES 6.3.5.

If N is a submodule of a R -module M , the natural map $\pi : M \rightarrow M/N$ defined by $\pi(m) = m+N, \forall m \in M$ is a R -homomorphism . π is called **the natural homomorphism from M on to M/N .**

Proof:- Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R,$

1- $\pi(m_1 + m_2) = (m_1 + m_2) + N, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M.$

$= (m_1 + N) \oplus (m_2 + N),$ by define of \oplus

$= \pi(m_1) + \pi(m_2),$ by define of natural map

2- $\pi(r.m) = r.m + N, \forall m \in M. = r.(m+N) = r.\pi(m). \therefore \pi$ is a R -homomorphism .

DEFINITION 6.3.6.

Let M, N be two R -modules. Let $H = \text{Hom}_R(M, N) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow N \text{ is a}$

homomorphism\} = the set of all homomorphism from M into N . Define $(+)$ and $(.)$

on H such that $(f+g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and $(r.f)(m) = r.f(m), \forall f, g \in H, \forall r \in R,$

$m \in M$. Then It is called **the module of all homomorphism of M to N** and $(H, +, .)$

is an until M -module .

Proof:-

Closure, let $f, g \in H,$ since $f: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism and $g: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism,

$f + g: M \rightarrow N$ homomorphism, where

$(f + g)(a+b) = f(a+b) + g(a+b) = f(a) + f(b) + g(a) + g(b) = f(a) + g(a) + f(b) + g(b)$

$= (f + g)(a) + (f + g)(b). \therefore f + g$ is homomorphism.

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m)$

$= (f_1 + g_1)(m) .$

Assuasive, $[(f + g) + h](m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m)$

$= f(m) + (g(m) + h(m)) = f(m) + (g+h)(m) = [f + (g+h)](m).$

Identity, $f(m) = e_N, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e_N + g(m) = g(m)$

$(g + f)(m) = g(m) + f(m) = g(m) + e_N = g(m).$

Inverse, $f(m) + f(m^{-1}) = f(m + m^{-1}) = f(e_M) = e_N .$

$f(m^{-1}) + f(m) = f(m^{-1} + m) = f(e_M) = e_N. \therefore (f(m))^{-1} = f(m^{-1}).$

Commutative, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m),$ since $(M, +)$ is commutative group $= (g + f)(m) . \therefore f + g$ is commutative.

$(H, +)$ is commutative group.

Define $\alpha : M \times H \rightarrow H$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m). \forall f, g \in H, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M.$

i- Let $f, g \in H$ and $m \in M$,

$(f+g, m) = (f+g)(m) = f(m)+g(m)$ by define of $+$ on $H = (f, m)+(g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- Let $f, g \in H$ and $m \in M$,

$(r.f, m) = (r.f)(m)$ by define $\alpha = r.f(m)$ by define of \cdot on $H = (r, (f, m))$.

iii- Let $f \in H$ and $m_1+m_2 \in M$

$(f, m_1+m_2) = f(m_1+m_2) = f(m_1)+f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$.

iv- I_M is the identity mapping of H and $(I_M, m) = I_M(m) = m, \forall m \in M$.

$\therefore (H, +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module .

PROPOSITION 6.3.7.

Let M, N be two R -modules. Let $K = \text{End}_R(M) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow M \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}\}$ = the set of all homomorphism from M into M . Define $(+)$ and (\circ) on H . $K = \text{End}_R(M)$ is called **the endomorphism ring of M over R** .

Proof:-

By examples (1.1.15), $(K = \text{End}_R(M), +)$ is **commutative group**.

Define $\alpha : M \times K \rightarrow K$ such that $(f, m) \rightarrow f(m)$. $\forall f, g \in K, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$.

i- Let $f, g \in K$ and $m \in M$,

$(f+g, m) = (f+g)(m) = f(m)+g(m)$ by define of $+$ on $K = (f, m)+(g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- Let $f, g \in K$ and $m \in M$,

$(f \circ g, m) = (f \circ g)(m)$ by define $\alpha = f(g(m))$ by define of \cdot on $K = (f, g(m)) = (f, (g, m))$.

iii- Let $f \in K$ and $m_1+m_2 \in M$ $(f, m_1+m_2) = f(m_1+m_2) = f(m_1)+f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$.

iv- I_m is the identity mapping of K and $(I_m, m) = I_m(m) = m, \forall m \in M$.

$\therefore (K = \text{End}_R(M), +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module .

REMARK 6.3.8.

Let M, N be two R -modules. $\text{Hom}_R(M, N) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow N \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}\}$ = the set of all R -homomorphism from M into N .

In case $N = R$, then $\text{Hom}_R(M, R) = M^*$. It is a ring with respect to the operation $+$ and \circ .

$\text{End}_R(M)$ is called **the dual module of M** . A R -module M is called **the dualizable** if $M^* \neq 0$.

THEOREM 6.3.9.

Let M, M' be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a R -homomorphism, then

- 1- $f(0_M) = 0_M \wedge f(-a) = -f(a), \forall a \in M.$
- 2- $f(a - b) = f(a) - f(b), \forall a, b \in M$

Proof:- H.W.

DEFINITION 6.3.10.

Let M, N be two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ be a R -homomorphism.

- 1- The kernel of f denoted by $(\ker(f))$, it is the set $\{x : x \in M, f(x) = 0_M\} \subseteq M.$
- 2- The image of f denoted by $(\text{Im}(f))$, it is the set $\{f(m) : m \in M\} \subseteq N.$
- 3- The cokernel of f denoted by $(\text{Coker}(f))$, it is the set $\text{Coker}(f) = \text{CoDom}(f)/\text{Im}(f) = N/\text{Im}(f).$
- 4- The coimage of f denoted by $(\text{Coim}(f))$, it is the set $\text{Coim}(f) = \text{Dom}(f)/\ker(f) = M/\ker(f).$

REMARK 6.3.11.

- 1- If f is an injection (1-1) and homomorphism, then f is called a monomorphism.
- 2- If f is a surjection (onto) and homomorphism, then f is called an epimorphism.
- 3- If f is a bijection (1-1 and onto) and homomorphism, then f is called an isomorphism.
- 4- Two R -modules M and N are said to be isomorphic ($M \cong N$) if and only if, \exists an isomorphism from M into N or (from N into M).
- 5- If $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ is a R -homomorphism, then
 - a- $f(0) = 0'.$
 - b- $f(-x) = -f(x)$, for all $x \in M.$

THEOREM 6.3.12.

Let M, N be two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a R -homomorphism. Then:

1. $\ker f$ is a submodule of $M.$
2. $\text{Im}(f)$ is a submodule of $N.$
3. $\ker f = \{0\} \Leftrightarrow f$ is 1-1.
4. $\text{Im} f = N \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R -epimorphism.
5. f is a R -isomorphism if and only if \exists a R -homomorphism $g: N \rightarrow M$ such that $g \circ f = I_M$ and $f \circ g = I_N.$

Proof:-

1- $\ker f = \{m \in M : f(m) = 0_M\} \subseteq M, \ker f \neq \emptyset$ since $0 \in M \Rightarrow f(0) = 0 \in \ker f.$

Let $m_1, m_2 \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(m_1) = 0_M, f(m_2) = 0_M.$

$f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = 0_M + 0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow m_1 + m_2 \in \ker f, \forall r \in R, m \in \ker f$

$$\Rightarrow f(m) = 0_M$$

$f(r.m) = r.f(m) = r.0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow r.m \in \ker f$. Hence, $\ker f$ is a submodule of M .

2- $\text{Im } f = \{f(m); m \in M\} \subseteq N$, $\text{Im } f \neq \emptyset$, since $0 \in M \Rightarrow f(0) = 0 \in \text{Im } f$.

Let $x_1, x_2 \in \text{Im } f \Rightarrow x_1 = f(m_1)$, $x_2 = f(m_2)$, $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M$.

$x_1 + x_2 = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) \in \text{Im } f$, since $(M, +)$ is group $m_1 + m_2 \in M$, $\forall r \in R$, $x \in \text{Im } f \Rightarrow x = f(m)$.

$r.x = r.f(m) = f(r.m) \in \text{Im } f$, since $r.m \in M$ (M is a module). $\therefore \text{Im } f$ is a submodule of M .

3- $\ker f = \{0_M\} \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R -monomorphism.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\ker f = \{0_M\}$, $f(m) = 0_M$, $\forall m \in M$. Let $m_1, m_2 \in M$, $f(m_1) = f(m_2) \Rightarrow 0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow m_1 = m_2$, by hyp. $\therefore f$ is 1-1. $\Rightarrow f$ is a R -monomorphism.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is a R -monomorphism \Rightarrow If $f(m_1) = f(m_2)$, $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M \Rightarrow m_1 = m_2$. $\ker f = \{m \in M, f(m) = 0_N\}$, $m \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(m) = 0_N$, $f(0) = 0_N$, since f is a R -homomorphism

$\Rightarrow f(m) = f(0) = 0_N \Rightarrow m = 0_M$, since f is 1-1 $\Rightarrow \ker f = \{0_M\}$, $\forall m \in M$.

4- $\text{Im } f = N \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R -epimorphism

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\text{Im } f = N \Rightarrow \text{Im } f = \{f(m) : m \in M\} = N$, $\forall y \in N \Rightarrow \exists m \in M \ni f(m) = y \Rightarrow f$ is onto $\Rightarrow f$ is R -epimorphism.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is a R -epimorphism $\Rightarrow f$ is onto. To proof $\text{Im } f \subseteq N$, by define of $\text{Im } f$. Since f is onto. Let $y \in N \Rightarrow \exists m \in M \ni f(m) = y \Rightarrow y \in \text{Im } f \Rightarrow N \subseteq \text{Im } f \Rightarrow \text{Im } f = N$.

5- (\Rightarrow) Suppose that f is R -isomorphism, to proof $g: N \rightarrow M$ is R -homomorphism

$\Rightarrow \exists f^{-1}: N \rightarrow M$ such that $f^{-1} = g$. Since f is a R -isomorphism $\Rightarrow \exists m_1, m_2 \in M$ such that $f(m_1) = y_1$ and $f(m_2) = y_2 \forall y_1, y_2 \in f$ (since f onto)

$$1) g(y_1, y_2) = g(f(m_1) + f(m_2)) = f^{-1}(f(m_1 + m_2)) = f^{-1} \text{ of } (m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 \\ = f^{-1}(y_1) + f^{-1}(y_2) = g(y_1) + g(y_2).$$

$$2) g(r.y) = g(r.f(m)) = g(f(r.m)) = f^{-1}(f(r.m)) = r.m = r.f^{-1}(y) = r.g(y). \therefore g \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}$$

Let $x \in M$, $g \circ f(x) = g(f(x)) = f^{-1}(f(x)) = x = I_m$, $\forall x \in M$.

Let $y \in N$, $f \circ g(y) = f(g(y)) = f(f^{-1}(y)) = y = I_n$, $\forall y \in N$.

(\Leftarrow) To proof f is a R -isomorphism, to proof f is 1-1 and onto.

Since $f: M \rightarrow N$, $g: N \rightarrow M$, then

$g \circ f(x) = I_M: M \rightarrow M \Rightarrow f$ is 1-1 & g onto, since I_M is a R-isomorphism.

$f \circ g(x) = I_N: N \rightarrow N \Rightarrow g(x)$ is 1-1 & $f(x)$ onto, since I_N is a R-isomorphism.

$\therefore f$ is a R-isomorphism.

THEOREM 6.3.13.

Let M, M' be two R-modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a R-homomorphism, then

1- If N is submodule of M , then $f(N)$ is R-submodule of M' , where f is onto.

2- If W is submodule of M' , then $f^{-1}(W)$ is a R-submodule of M .

Proof:- H.W.

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